

SoildiverAgro

Soil biodiversity enhancement in European agroecosystems to promote their stability and resilience by external inputs reduction and crop performance increase

D2.1 – REPORT ON DATA COMPILATION FROM DISCUSSION GROUPS AND SURVEYS

Universidade de Vigo

D2.1 REPORT OF DATA COMPILATION FROM DISCUSSION GROUPS AND SURVEYS

Summary

Task 2.1 aims to identify the most relevant agri-environmental problems and related end-users' needs in each of the 15 case studies, and to assess the practical potential for the integration of farming practices that enhance soil biodiversity in the different cropping systems. This report summarizes the methodology and results of all activities carried out within task 2.1, including a survey to stakeholders and discussion groups with stakeholders. Results from the survey and discussion groups allow to identify those farming practices that they consider as the most effective to face the major agro-environmental problems in each case study, as well as the potential for their integration in the different cropping systems analysed in the project.

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UPCT		Javier Calatrava Leyva [UPCT] Alicia Morugán Coronado [UPCT] María Dolores Gómez López [UPCT]	
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1 Background and objectives

The main objective of SoildiverAgro is the adoption of new management practices and cropping systems that enhance soil genetic and functional biodiversity to reduce the use of external inputs while increasing crop production and quality, the delivery of ecosystem services and the EU agricultural stability and resilience. Within the project, WP2 aims to identify agronomic problems faced by practitioners in various European cropping systems using literature review, data mining, meta-analysis and surveys of end-users' needs, as well as possible management alternatives involving soil biodiversity enhancement and ecosystems services delivery. The management alternatives with realistic potential for meeting end users' needs through soil biodiversity enhancement will be tested in the case studies' on-field experiments within WP5 (Figure 1).

Figure 1. SoildiverAgro's Work Packages structure

WP2 is organized in three tasks:

- Task 2.1 (Development of surveys and compilation of information about challenges and end-users needs) focuses on the identification of main agronomic problems and related end-users' needs through surveys and discussion groups plus stakeholders' opinion about the practical potential for the implementation of possible farm management practices.
- Task 2.2 (Systematic review, data mining and meta-analysis), focuses on proposing alternative farm management practices.
- Task 2.3 (Selection of realistic management practices with high potential for solving agricultural problems together with soil biodiversity enhancement) that aims to provide the final list of proposed cropping systems and management practices for each pedoclimatic region to be combined for soil biodiversity enhancement.

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This deliverable summarizes the methodology and results of all activities carried out within task 2.1, including the survey to stakeholders and the discussion groups. The objectives of task 2.1 are:

- To identify the most relevant agri-environmental problems in each of the 15 case studies;
- To identify end-users' needs related to the identified problems;
- To assess the practical potential for the implementation of farming practices in the proposed cropping systems.
- To identify the strengths, opportunities, limitations and drawbacks of the different cropping systems in terms of integrating farming practices that enhance soil biodiversity.

Task 2.1 will therefore provide information for task 2.3 (Selection of realistic management practices with high potential for solving agricultural problems together with soil biodiversity enhancement) in order to define the final list of proposed cropping systems and management practices for each pedoclimatic region to be combined for soil biodiversity enhancement. All project's partners satisfactorily contributed to this task.

2 Methodology

Task 2.1 involved the compilation of the opinion of relevant stakeholders on the identification of main agronomic problems and related end-users' needs in the agroecosystems of the different case study areas. With this in mind, Task 2.1 comprises two actions to be carried out in each case study area: a survey to stakeholders and discussion groups with stakeholders. Survey answers will be analysed using univariate statistical techniques and multicriteria analysis and the results, in terms of the identified end users' needs and most effective farming practices, will be presented to stakeholders participating in discussion groups in each case study to serve as a starting point to initiate discussion.

2.1 Survey to stakeholders

The survey to stakeholders was implemented using a structured questionnaire. In the project's Kick-off meeting, it was decided to use a common questionnaire for all case studies, that will be adapted to each case study's particularities. Task leader UPCT developed a first version questionnaire in English based on case study 1 (potato production in Mediterranean South region), and taking into account the guidelines established in deliverable D9.2 regarding personal data protection. This questionnaire was circulated to regional coordinators and case study leaders that tested it and provided suggestions for its improvement.

The final questionnaire's structure included the following five sections:

Section 1. Brief explanation of the project and the purpose of the survey and the respondent's consent, required before the questionnaire can be filled.

Section 2. General respondent's information, e.g., name, gender, age, type of stakeholder, name and type of working institution, position in working institution, educational level, experience on cropping, etc.

Section 3. Identification of the most relevant agronomic problems of the crop in the area (choice from an open list) and qualitative assessment of their severity.

Section 4. Identification of end-users' needs through the qualitative assessment of the priority that should be given to different objectives in order to face the major agronomic problems of the crop in the area.

Section 5. Identification of the farming practices best suited to address the previously identified problems and assessment of the potential for their integration in different cropping systems. Farming practices were grouped in tillage, fertilization, soil conservation and pest and disease control practices. Cropping systems considered were organic versus conventional farming, monoculture versus diversified cropping systems and rainfed versus irrigated production.

A major feature of the developed questionnaire is that it evolves with the interviewee's answers, as some questions are built based on the answers provided to previous questions. This adaptive design has the advantage of simplifying the questionnaire by focusing only on the specific aspects that each interviewee finds relevant. This reduces the risk of the expert getting tired of answering the survey by avoiding irrelevant issues and shortening the duration of the survey.

Once the final version of the common questionnaire was finished, it was adapted to the specificities of each case study with the involvement of each corresponding partner and based on his/her knowledge from previous researches and results of task 2.2's data mining results. To adapt the questionnaire to each case study area, the common structure of the questionnaire was maintained but the lists of agronomic problems and farming practices were fitted to each case study's particularities. When the questionnaire was adapted to each case study, it was translated by each partner to each country's native language to reach all stakeholders in their regions.

Regarding the implementation of the survey, and as time was a major constraint for this task's activities, it was decided in the Kick-off meeting to implement the survey questionnaire online. The online option is cheaper and faster than face-to-face interviews and no codification of the answers is needed. However, it requires a simpler questionnaire, poses some restrictions to the design of questions, and allows no interaction with respondents. If some partners opted to do face to face interviews, the interviewer can fill the questionnaire online as the interviewee answers it. Surveys were implemented on a commercial online surveying platform (Survey Monkey). Interviewees could answer the survey online using a computer/tablet/smartphone. A web link providing the access to the questionnaire in Survey Monkey was sent to participating stakeholders. The answers to the questionnaire provided by each person were directly received by the task leader (UPCT), immediately after it had been filled. Survey answers were downloaded in Excel format template for its validation and analysis.

The survey was not intended for all type of stakeholders but for those directly involved in the issues discussed in it. Consequently, three major types of stakeholders were ask to fill the survey questionnaire: 1) farmers producing the crop in each case study; 2) agricultural technical advisors from cooperatives, public advisory/extension services, private advisors, input supplying companies, etc. with expertise on the crop in each case study; and 3) Other stakeholders such as researchers, public officers from the agricultural administration, environmental NGOs, etc., with experience on the corresponding cropping system. Other type of stakeholders would be involved in other posterior participatory activities of the project (discussion groups, workshops, etc.). SoildiverAgro's multi-actor approach includes the involvement of stakeholders and the creation of communities of practitioners (task 8.3), so it is interesting that the people answering the survey questionnaire continue participating in other activities throughout the project. Surveyed stakeholders were selected and contacted by each partner with help from farmers' associations and agricultural cooperatives and companies. As a guidance for partners, it was recommended to target at a minimum of 20 farmers and 10 agricultural technical advisors and between 5 and 10 of other stakeholders. Agricultural technical advisors are of special interest for WP6 activities, so partners were asked to try to involve as many as possible.

The answers to the survey questionnaire have been summarised using univariate statistical techniques and multicriteria analysis techniques. In most questions, the percentage of stakeholders selecting each possible answer was considered. In the case of the identification of the most relevant agronomic problems and related end-users' needs (sections 3 and 4 of the questionnaire), respondents qualitatively assessed the severity or priority using linguistic labels that were numerically converted to a 0 to 5 scale and the weighted average value of such scale was used to identify the most relevant ones. Regarding farming practices, stakeholders assessed the effectiveness of farming practices, within each group of farming practices, to address each need (objective). Stakeholders assess each farming practice depending on the objective in question. In order to identify the most effective farming practices for each case study, one of the main outputs of the survey, Multicriteria Decision Making Methods (MCDM) were used. More specifically, MCDM were used to establish the order of preferences for stakeholders regarding farming practices. MCDM were chosen because they allow to integrate the knowledge of experts who can enrich the decision with their judgments regarding the decision-making problem. Any multi-criteria decision problem (MCDP) can be expressed by means of the following five elements:

$$\{C, D, r, I, \prec\}$$

Where:

- $C = \{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_m\}$ It is the set of m criteria that represent the tools which enable alternatives to be compared from a specific point of view, in this case, the priority given by stakeholders to each end-users' need (objective).
- $D = \{D_1, D_2, \dots, D_n\}$ It is the set of feasible alternatives (farming practices) for the decision-maker, and from which the decision-maker must choose one. In this case, the sets C and D are finite sets. This allows us to avoid convergence, integrability and measurability problems.
- $r: D \times C \rightarrow R$ is a function where a real interval corresponds to every decision d_i and to every criterion C_j .

$$(D_i, C_j) \rightarrow r(D_i, C_j) = r_{ij}$$

Once that set of criteria and alternatives have been selected, then we need a measure of the effect produced by each alternative with respect to each criterion, i.e., the effectiveness of each farming practice to achieve each objective. By means of linguistic terms, the decision-maker represents the goodness of an alternative; the different values of r can be represented by means of a matrix called the Matrix of decision-making. A relation of preferences \prec by the decision maker. We shall suppose a coherent decision-maker; therefore, he shall try to maximize his profits or else minimize his losses. In this case, the decision-maker needs to obtain the best alternative set. The decision-maker gives linguistic information about the importance for each alternative. In this specific case, and by means of direct assignment, the importance for criteria was obtained, being the valuation scale: Very low: 1; Low: 2; Medium-low: 3; Medium-high: 4; High: 5; Very high: 6.

Mathematical calculation of the aptitude of each alternative provided by the surveys was done by the Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS). The TOPSIS technique is based upon the concept that the chosen alternative should have the shortest distance from the positive ideal solution (PIS) and the farthest from the negative ideal solution (NIS). The final ranking was obtained by means of the closeness index.

2.2 Discussion groups

The discussion groups within task 2.1 activities were the first contact with stakeholders, thus initiating the implementation of the project's multi-actor approach (WP8). Consequently, partners were provided with guidelines to organize the discussion groups prepared by FEUGA as WP8's leader. These guidelines included recommendations about the number of participating stakeholders (between 20 and 40) and the type of stakeholders (Farmers, researchers, agronomic technicians in companies, agribusiness, manufacturers, NGOs, public administration, suppliers, logistics, retailers, consumers associations, etc), and about the possible structure and program of the first discussion group.

The objectives of the first discussion group, which involve several WPs, were:

- To have a first contact with stakeholders, present them the project's activities and explain them their role in the project (multi-actor approach in WP8);
- Present the results of the WP2's survey to discuss them with stakeholders and validate and complement these results (WP2 activities);
- Present and discuss the practices that will be implemented in the case studies to validate the proposed experimental design (WP5 activities) and assess their sustainability (WP6 activities).

In relation with the activities within WP2 (identification of main challenges and end-user needs and effective farming practices in each case study regions), that is the focus of the present deliverable, the proposed structure for the discussion group consisted on:

- Presentation and discussion of the survey results regarding agronomic problems and end-users' needs to obtain feedback from stakeholders, asking them about their agreement with the severity of agronomic problems and other agronomic problems that should have been considered and about the reasons for their disagreement (in case they disagree);
- Presentation and discussion of the survey results regarding the effectiveness of farming practices to address the identified problems, asking stakeholders about their agreement with the ranking of preferences regarding farming practices obtained (and the reasons in case they disagree), about potential problems that can be expected upon the implementation of these practices, and about the effectiveness of these practices within different cropping systems (organic versus conventional, diversified versus non-diversified cropping systems and irrigated versus rainfed cropping systems);

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- Presentation and discussion of the survey results regarding potential barriers that can limit the implementation of farming practices;
- The presentation and discussion of the survey results was to be done separately for each group of farming practices.

Discussion groups were organised for each case study or case study region. Each partner identified and selected the participants, trying to involve as much different types of stakeholders as possible (e.g., farmers, technical advisors, public officers, researchers, input suppliers, value-chain stakeholders, NGO representatives, etc.). The survey respondents were also invited to participate in the discussion groups. Participants in discussion groups were introduced to the SoildiverAgro project, including its objectives and the different case studies. Results from the survey were used as a basis to initiate discussion. Discussion focused on the potential of different farming practices to improve cropping systems in their area, their feasibility and potential barriers for their implementation. After each discussion group was celebrated, each partner provided UPCT with the minutes describing their development and the outcome of the discussion related to the WP2 survey, which are presented in annex 2.

Discussion groups were to be celebrated in march 2020. However, due to the COVID outbreak, some discussion groups were celebrated with significant delay. The final celebration dates were:

- Boreal case studies: 5th March 2020
- Lusitanian case studies: 11th March 2020
- Atlantic Central case studies: 19th May 2020 and 30th June 2020
- Nemoral case studies: 3rd July 2020
- Mediterranean South case studies: 15th and 16th September 2020
- Continental case studies: 3rd November 2020

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3 Results

3.1. Stakeholders participating in the survey

Table 1 shows the number of survey respondents per case study and type of stakeholder. In some case studies there were difficulties to reach a greater number of stakeholders because some respondents left many questions unanswered, as they claimed that they did not have enough knowledge about the issues at stake and did not feel confident to answer them. It must be also noted that some of the surveyed private technical advisors are also farmers but have been considered as technical advisors.

Table 1. Number of survey respondents by case study

CASE STUDIES	Farmers	Advisory services	Researcher / Academic	NGO representatives	TOTAL RESPONDENTS	Average respondent's age (years)
POTATO, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	15	5	3	0	23	41.3
WHEAT, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	14	5	3	0	22	45.1
POTATO, LUSITANEAN, SPAIN	48	10	4	1	63	45.7
WHEAT, LUSITANEAN, SPAIN	46	6	4	2	58	45.8
POTATO, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	9	3	8	0	20	45.3
VEGETABLES, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	18	3	9	0	30	45.8
WHEAT, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	56	4	5	1	66	51.7
POTATO, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	12	4	2	0	18	48.0
WHEAT, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	14	1	1	1	17	45.0
POTATO, NEMORAL, ESTONIA	16	4	8	1	29	50.8
POTATO, BOREAL, FINLAND	24	18	4	2	48	51.1
WHEAT, BOREAL, FINLAND	31	8	7	2	48	49.9

3.2. Assessment of the most relevant agro-environmental problems in each crop/area

Respondents were asked to qualitatively assess the severity of agro-environmental problems in their crop and area of study on a six-interval scale ranging from very low to very high. Their qualitative answers were converted to a 0 to 5 scale and are presented in Figure 2 and Table 2. The results for each case study are commented in the corresponding annex.

In general, the stakeholders interviewed in the potato case studies do not perceive, on average, any agronomic **problem** as being of high or very high severity (Table 2). The most severe problems are perceived, on average, as of a medium-high severity, and differ significantly from one case study to another. However, the expressed stakeholders' perception of the severity of agro-environmental problems is consistent with the specific nature of the agricultural systems analysed. For example, rainfall scarcity during the growing period is identified as one of the most severe problems in the Atlantic Central, Continental, Nemoral and Boreal case studies, where most potato production is rainfed. The high incidence of pests and fungal diseases and, to a lesser extent, the high use of plant protection products are also among the most acute problems in most study areas (Lusitanian, Atlantic Central, Continental and Nemoral case studies), while these are barely perceived as relevant in the Boreal case study. High weed pressure is also identified as a major problem in the Mediterranean South and Continental case studies. More related to soil management, the loss of soil organic matter content and soil compaction are among the most severe problems in the Mediterranean South, Boreal and Nemoral case studies. There is also concern with soil waterlogging in the Lusitanian and Boreal case studies. Regarding low soil biodiversity, this is only among the most severe identified problems in the Mediterranean South and Boreal case studies, while they are among the less severe problems in the Atlantic Central and Continental case studies. Overall, the less severe problems for stakeholders are water pollution by leaching or run-off of nutrients, soil acidification, development of resistance to plant protection products and soil erosion, which is only perceived of some severity in the Mediterranean South case study.

Turning to wheat, the stakeholders interviewed in the five wheat case studies do not perceive, on average, any agronomic **problem** as being of high or very high severity (Table 2). The most severe problems are perceived, on average, as of a medium-high severity. Despite the different answers given in each case study, the stakeholders' perception of the severity of agro-environmental problems is consistent with each agricultural system. For example, rainfall scarcity during the growing season is identified as one of the most severe problems in the Mediterranean South, Continental and Boreal case studies, while excess rainfall and problems of soil waterlogging and/or inadequate drainage is identified as a major problem in the Lusitanian and Boreal case studies. The high incidence of pests, fungal diseases and weeds, and the resulting high level of use of phytosanitary products, is identified as one of the major problems in the Lusitanian, Atlantic Central and Continental case studies, while these are among the less severe problems for stakeholders in the Mediterranean case study. Regarding soil management, the reduction in soil organic matter content and soil compaction are perceived as severe problems in the Mediterranean South and Boreal case studies, being less severe for stakeholders in the other wheat case studies. As in the potato case studies, the agro-environmental problems that are less severely perceived by stakeholders relate to water pollution from nutrients leaching

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and/or run-off, soil biodiversity and fertility, soil acidification and soil erosion. The exceptions are again the Mediterranean South case study, where soil erosion is among the most relevant problems, and the Boreal case study, where low soil biodiversity is perceived as a more severe problems than in the other case studies.

Last, the most severe problems identified by stakeholders in the Belgian Atlantic Central vegetables case study are rainfall scarcity in the growing period and irrigation water scarcity, followed by the high incidence of weeds, pests and fungal diseases. In contrast, the problems considered as less severe are soil erosion, water pollution by leaching and/or run-off of nutrients and soil acidification (Table 2).

Figure 2. Stakeholders' qualitative subjective assessment of the severity of different agronomic problems in their area (measured on a 0 to 5 scale: 0=very low/null, 5= Very high)

Table 2. Stakeholders' qualitative subjective assessment of the severity of different agronomic problems in their area (measured on a 0 to 5 scale: 0=very low/null, 5= Very high)

PROBLEMS	POTATO / MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	WHEAT, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	POTATO / LUSITANEAN, SPAIN	WHEAT, LUSITANEAN, SPAIN	POTATO / ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	VEGETABLES, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	WHEAT, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	POTATO / CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	WHEAT, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	POTATO / NEMORAL, ESTONIA	POTATO / BOREAL, FINLAND	WHEAT, BOREAL, FINLAND
Low and/or variable yields	2.45	2.95	3.21	3.23	2.40	2.33	2.32	3.18	2.87	2.93	2.50	2.92
Low soil fertility	2.41	2.67	2.89	2.95	1.95	2.67	2.18	2.22	1.60	2.63	2.40	2.48
Rainfall scarcity in growing period	2.91	3.10	2.75	2.59	3.71	3.55	2.29	3.56	3.00	2.96	2.93	2.71
Irrigation water scarcity	2.52	2.60	3.02	2.40	3.00	3.37	1.31					
High incidence of pests	2.68	2.10	3.41	2.91	3.00	3.10	2.35	3.17	1.80	2.21	1.47	1.43
High incidence of fungal diseases	2.77	2.20	3.33	2.93	3.47	2.93	2.81	3.11	2.40	2.75	2.44	1.81
High use of phytosanitary products	2.55	1.63	3.24	2.76	3.41	2.50	2.59	2.28	2.20	2.25	1.59	1.68
Development of resistance to phytosanitary products	2.41	2.11	3.05	2.63	2.88	2.41	2.60	1.44	2.50	2.35	1.68	2.14
Low presence of beneficial invertebrates/insects in the soil	2.86	2.37	2.57	2.50	2.20	2.71	2.22	2.47	2.00	1.91	2.26	2.41
Low soil microbial biodiversity	3.17	2.22	2.62	2.41	2.27	2.72	2.17	1.88	1.79	2.60	2.34	2.64
Waterlogging/inadequate drainage			3.37	3.12	1.83	2.66	2.05			2.48	2.42	2.73
Excessive use of machinery	2.64	2.85	2.79	2.74	2.65	2.45	2.12	2.17	1.80	2.61	2.12	2.40
Soil compaction	3.14	3.10	2.77	2.75	2.95	2.50	2.20	2.41	1.60	2.78	2.74	3.17
Water pollution by leaching/ run-off	2.73	2.11	2.80	2.50	2.86	2.23	1.95	1.41		1.74	1.40	1.58
Soil erosion	2.74	2.95	2.33	2.35	2.67	1.89	1.49	1.89	1.33	1.58	2.10	1.79
Loss of organic matter	3.48	3.14	2.39	2.47	2.75	2.60	2.06	2.39	1.47	2.58	2.79	2.50
Soil acidification			2.42	2.44	2.06	2.30	1.88	1.65	1.00			
High incidence of bacterial diseases	2.64	1.90	2.57	2.30	2.41	2.47	1.72					
High weed pressure	3.04	2.55	2.98	2.84	2.42	3.13	2.12	3.35	3.00			
Low number of earthworms in soil	3.05	2.11	2.47	2.68	2.24	2.73	2.03	1.53	1.57	2.57	2.50	2.29
Rainfall excess			2.58	2.88				2.72	1.47	2.30	1.93	2.17

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3.3. Prioritization of objectives (end-users' needs)

Once the stakeholders had assessed the severity of agro-environmental problems, they were asked to qualitatively value the priority that should be given to different objectives in order to face the major agronomic problems of the crop in their area, measured on a six interval scale ranging from very low to very high. Their qualitative answers were converted to a 0 to 5 scale, and are shown in Figure 3 and Table 3. Their answers are, in general, consistent with the previous identification of relevant problems. Results for each case study are commented in the annex.

Table 3 shows that, in general, the stakeholders surveyed in the different potato case studies give the highest priority to actions targeted towards increasing soil organic matter content and improving soil structure to increase aeration, water retention and favour plant rooting, which are the most urgent needs in the Mediterranean South, Atlantic Central, Nemoral and Boreal case studies. Similar priority is given to reducing the incidence of pests and diseases and to the control of weeds, which are the most urgent needs in the Lusitanian and Continental case studies. The following priorities for stakeholders in all case studies are mobilizing soil nutrients during the plant growth stage, increasing soil fertility and, to a lesser extent, increasing soil biodiversity.

In the case of the wheat case studies, the priority given by stakeholders to different objectives for addressing the agronomic problems in each area (Table 3) points at increasing soil organic matter content, improving soil structure to increase aeration, water retention and favour plant rooting, mobilizing soil nutrients during plant growth stage and increasing soil fertility as the most urgent needs in all case studies, closely followed by increasing soil biodiversity and, to a lesser extent, by reducing the incidence of pests and diseases that is given special priority in the Lusitanian and Atlantic Central case studies.

Las, the priority given by the stakeholders to different **objectives** for addressing the agronomic problems in the Belgian Atlantic central vegetables case study (Table 3) points at increasing soil fertility, soil organic content and soil biodiversity and improving soil structure as the most urgent needs. On the other hand, the most severe problems for stakeholders are reducing soil pollution and improving water quality.

Figure 3. Stakeholders' qualitative subjective assessment of the priority of different objectives in their area (measured on a 0 to 5 scale; 0=very low/null, 5= Very high)

Table 3. Stakeholders' qualitative subjective assessment of the priority of different objectives in their area (measured on a 0 to 5 scale; 0=very low/null, 5= Very high)

OBJECTIVES	POTATO / MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	WHEAT, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	POTATO / LUSITANEAN, SPAIN	WHEAT, LUSITANEAN, SPAIN	POTATO / ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	VEGETABLES, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	WHEAT, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	POTATO / CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	WHEAT, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	POTATO / NEMORAL, ESTONIA	POTATO / BOREAL, FINLAND	WHEAT, BOREAL, FINLAND
Increase soil fertility	3.96	4.00	3.11	3.29	3.71	3.90	3.27	3.47	3.43	3.61	3.80	4.04
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	3.73	3.59	3.22	3.29	3.53	3.30	3.20	3.69	3.29	3.63	3.45	3.88
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	3.57	3.14	3.51	3.19	3.65	3.52	3.38	3.65	3.21	3.67	3.30	3.25
Increase soil organic matter content	4.00	4.14	2.92	2.95	4.00	3.84	3.49	3.24	3.50	3.70	3.88	4.00
Improve soil structure to improve aeration. water retention and rooting	4.00	4.09	3.11	3.12	3.86	3.77	3.34	3.13	3.50	3.78	4.09	4.38
Increase soil biodiversity	3.65	3.86	3.00	3.02	3.58	3.71	3.03	3.06	3.54	3.46	3.68	4.07
Reduce soil erosion	3.26	3.76	2.48	2.58	2.85	2.81	2.17	2.71	2.43	2.64	3.30	3.04
Reduce soil pollution	3.45	3.36	2.77	2.70	2.32	2.29	2.00	1.94	2.43	2.52	2.15	2.62
Reduce soil salinization	3.61	3.29	2.13	2.24								
Reduce soil acidification			2.49	2.73	2.67	2.81	2.49	2.13	2.29			
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	3.36	3.76	2.82	2.69				2.60	2.64	3.46	3.52	3.87
Improve water quality			2.75	2.67	3.35	2.68	2.58				2.77	3.13
Reduce the incidence of weeds			2.81	2.76				3.71	3.57	3.52	2.79	3.11
Increasing load carrying capacity										2.95	3.23	3.47

3.4. Identification of the most effective farming practices for each crop/study area

The surveyed stakeholders were asked to choose which farming practices, within a given group of farming practices, they consider as more effective to address the previously identified problems. Farming practices were grouped in tillage, fertilization, soil conservation and pest and disease control practices. Each respondent chose from a list of practices, although they could propose other practices not included in the proposed list. It must be noted that this question was only answered for those objectives previously assessed as of high or very high priority. A summary of stakeholders' responses for each crop and area are presented in the tables of the corresponding annex, while Table 4, Table 9, Table 14 and Table 19 show the order of preferences for each group of farming practices resulting from the multicriteria analysis. A higher ranking means that this practice is considered as more effective to achieve the identified priorities for action (objectives) by surveyed stakeholders.

Within each group of farming practices, stakeholders were also asked several questions that aimed to assess the potential of farming practices for their integration in different cropping systems. The cropping systems considered were organic versus conventional farming, monoculture versus diversified cropping systems and rainfed versus irrigated production. Results for all crops/areas are presented in the following tables: Table 5, Table 6, Table 7 and Table 8 for tillage practices; Table 10, Table 11, Table 12 and Table 13 for fertilization practices; Table 15, Table 16, Table 17 and Table 18 for soil conservation practices; and Table 20, Table 21, Table 22 and Table 23 for pest and disease control practices. The following sections summarise the results for each group of farming practices.

3.4.1. Tillage practices

Looking at **tillage practices**, stakeholders in each case study chose different tillage practices as the most adequate ones for each end-users' need to be fulfilled (objectives). Results for each case study are commented in the annex. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 4) show significant differences between crops and areas and highlight the existing debate between conventional intensive tillage and the different conservation tillage alternatives. However, in the majority of case studies, stakeholders give the highest ranking score either to conventional tillage or to minimum tillage, which basically consists on reducing the frequency of tillage. More sustainable tillage practices, such as shallow tillage or no tillage, are the second preferred alternative in some case studies but receive very low ranking scores in others.

In the case of potato production, conventional tillage is by far the most preferred tillage alternative in the Lusitanian and Nemoral case studies, while minimum tillage, closely followed by conventional tillage, is the most preferred alternative in the Atlantic Central and Continental case studies (Table 4). Stakeholders in the Mediterranean South and Boreal case studies give lower ranking scores to conventional tillage, selecting minimum and shallow tillage respectively as the preferred alternative, being no tillage with mechanical weed control the second most preferred alternative in both cases. However, it must be said that the option "None of these tillage practices is effective to face the problems in the area" receives the highest ranking score

in the Boreal case study and the second highest ranking alternative in the Lusitanian and Atlantic Central case studies.

In the case of the Atlantic Central vegetables production, respondents give the highest ranking score to minimum tillage, while shallow tillage receives the second highest ranking score, followed by conventional tillage.

Last, in the case of wheat production, the results of the multicriteria assessment (Table 4) show that conventional tillage receives the highest ranking score in the Lusitanian and Atlantic Central case studies, followed by shallow and minimum tillage. However, despite this, the ranking differences are not very large and the overall number of stakeholders choosing less intensive tillage options is greater than the number opting for conventional tillage, suggesting that the stakeholders' preference for less intensive tillage is clear. Stakeholders in the other three wheat case studies express more preference for more sustainable tillage. In the Mediterranean South case study, stakeholders give the by far the highest ranking score to minimum tillage, followed by contour tillage (consistently with the greater concern with the soil erosion problem), while in the Continental case study, respondents also give the highest ranking score to minimum tillage but followed by conventional tillage and no tillage with application of herbicides both with very similar ranking scores. In the Boreal case study shallow tillage is the preferred option, followed by no tillage with mechanical weed control and minimum tillage, both with very similar ranking scores.

Stakeholders were asked about the factors that can difficult the implementation of more sustainable tillage practices in the crop and study area. In the case of the potato case studies, although responses differ significantly from one case study to another, the majority of stakeholders pointed out at the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness and, to a lesser extent, the lack of tradition as the most relevant barriers (Table 5). Another frequently indicated barrier is the complexity of implementing more sustainable tillage practices if adequate technical advice is not available. Other relevant barriers are their lack of profitability, their incompatibility with other farming practices and with the existing farm machinery. However, in the Lusitanian and Boreal case studies, few stakeholders perceive these tillage practices as incompatible with other farming practices. On the other hand, most stakeholders do not perceive these tillage practices as difficult to implement with adequate technical advice and do not perceive that they are not profitable.

In the case of the Atlantic Central vegetables case study, the interviewed stakeholders consider that the implementation of more sustainable tillage practices is diffculted by the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness, the lack of tradition and because they feel that support from the government on technical issues is inadequate or insufficient (Table 5). On the other hand, most stakeholders do not perceive these tillage practices as difficult to implement with adequate technical advice and do not perceive that they are not profitable.

In the case of the wheat case studies, although responses differ significantly from one case study to another, the majority of stakeholders pointed out at the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness, the lack of tradition and the need for adequate technical advice as the most relevant barriers (Table 5). Other relevant barriers are their lack of profitability and of adequate support from the government of technical issues. On the other hand, most stakeholders do not perceive these tillage practices as difficult to implement with adequate technical advice and do

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not perceive that they are not profitable. A large number of stakeholders in the Continental and Boreal Wheat case studies also indicate that the existing farm machinery does not support these types of practices.

Regarding the effectiveness of more sustainable tillage practices when integrated within different cropping systems, for all crops and study areas, the majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that they are equally or more effective under organic production than under conventional farming (Table 6), more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 7) and more or equally effective under irrigation than under rainfed conditions (Table 8), with the exceptions of the Lusitanian, Atlantic central and Boreal wheat case studies, where stakeholders perceive that sustainable tillage practices are more effective under rainfed conditions.

Table 4. Stakeholders' assessment of the effectiveness of tillage practices in order to face the agro-environmental problems in the crops and areas of study (ranking of preferences from the multicriteria assessment)

CASE STUDIES	Conventional tillage	Tillage according level curves	Shallow tillage	Minimum tillage (reduced tillage frequency)	No tillage with herbicides	No tillage without herbicides (mechanical weed control)	None of these is effective
POTATO, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	0.1942	0.2402	0.4274	0.8197	0.1353	0.5305	0.3936
WHEAT, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	0.2412	0.4697	0.2001	0.7377	0.2709	0.3063	0.0988
POTATO, LUSITANEAN, SPAIN	0.7969	0.0240	0.3923	0.3161	0.1635	0.1973	0.5541
WHEAT, LUSITANEAN, SPAIN	0.6513	0.1078	0.4733	0.4196	0.1921	0.2355	0.5885
POTATO, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	0.3956	0.3013	0.2874	0.5888	0.0000	0.2979	0.5262
VEGETABLES, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	0.4380	0.2754	0.5770	0.7003	0.1513	0.2076	0.3328
WHEAT, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	0.6651	0.2265	0.4386	0.5612	0.2212	0.0000	0.1574
POTATO, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	0.5007	0.0000	0.2395	0.5163	0.3601	0.1925	0.3572
WHEAT, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	0.3709	0.1518	0.3420	0.5914	0.3652	0.2157	0.1090
POTATO, NEMORAL, ESTONIA	0.7125	0.1558	0.1779	0.4325	0.2367	0.2004	0.3820
POTATO, BOREAL, FINLAND	0.4342	0.0380	0.3350	0.5022	0.1247	0.4190	0.6903
WHEAT, BOREAL, FINLAND	0.3648	0.0986	0.6751	0.4232	0.3242	0.4277	0.3500

Table 5. Stakeholders' identification of problems that can difficult the implementation of more sustainable tillage practices (percentage of answers)

	POTATO, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	WHEAT, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	POTATO, LUSITANEAN, SPAIN	WHEAT, LUSITANEAN, SPAIN	POTATO, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	VEGETABLES, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	WHEAT, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	POTATO, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	WHEAT, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	POTATO, NEMORAL, ESTONIA	POTATO, BOREAL, FINLAND	WHEAT, BOREAL, FINLAND
Lack of knowledge among farmers about the effectiveness of farming practices	66.67%	73.68%	59.68%	51.72%	62.50%	56.00%	42.37%	50.00%	50.00%	23.08%	34.15%	54.55%
Lack of tradition in the region	42.86%	36.84%	46.77%	48.28%	50.00%	48.00%	38.98%	18.75%	30.00%	19.23%	31.71%	27.27%
Complex/difficult to carry out without technical advice	23.81%	36.84%	53.22%	62.07%	31.25%	28.00%	8.47%	31.25%	20.00%	15.38%	2.44%	15.91%
Complex/difficult to carry out even with technical advice	14.29%	5.26%	3.23%	0.00%	0.00%	4.00%	10.15%	31.25%	10.00%	11.54%	4.88%	2.27%
The existing machinery does not support this practice	19.05%	10.53%	4.84%	1.72%	37.50%	20.00%	23.73%	18.75%	70.00%	23.08%	19.51%	38.64%
Inadequate/insufficient support from the government on technical issues	14.29%	26.32%	16.13%	13.79%	12.50%	36.00%	18.64%	0.00%	40.00%	19.23%	2.44%	11.36%
Lack of enabling legislation/regulation	4.76%	5.26%	4.84%	1.72%	12.50%	20.00%	15.25%	18.75%	10.00%	0.00%	2.44%	6.82%
The costs are too high	33.33%	31.58%	12.90%	5.17%	18.75%	12.00%	40.68%	18.75%	60.00%	26.92%	14.63%	20.45%
The benefits do not outweigh the costs	23.81%	31.58%	4.84%	5.17%	18.75%	12.00%	35.59%	31.25%	30.00%	23.08%	24.39%	22.73%
Incompatibility with other farming practices	23.81%	0.00%	6.45%	3.45%	18.75%	4.00%	10.15%	0.00%	0.00%	26.92%	26.83%	4.55%

Table 6. Stakeholders' assessment of the effectiveness of tillage practices when integrated in in an organic cropping system (percentage of answers)

	POTATO, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	WHEAT, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	POTATO, LUSITANIAN, SPAIN	WHEAT, LUSITANIAN, SPAIN	POTATO, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	VEGETABLES, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	WHEAT, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	POTATO, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	WHEAT, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	POTATO, NEMORAL, ESTONIA	POTATO, BOREAL, FINLAND	WHEAT, BOREAL, FINLAND
More effective under organic production	42.86%	42.11%	3.23%	10.34%	6.25%	32.00%	1.69%	18.75%	10.00%	11.54%	21.95%	20.45%
Equally effective under organic and conventional farming	23.81%	21.05%	17.74%	15.52%	56.25%	28.00%	42.37%	50.00%	40.00%	42.31%	41.46%	40.91%
More effective under conventional farming	4.76%	10.53%	1.61%	5.17%	12.50%	12.00%	8.47%	18.75%	30.00%	23.08%	14.63%	20.45%
Not compatible with organic production	4.76%	5.26%	51.61%	48.28%	0.00%	4.00%	18.64%	0.00%	10.00%	0.00%	4.88%	11.36%
I do not know the problem well enough to answer	23.81%	21.05%	25.81%	20.69%	25.00%	24.00%	28.81%	12.50%	10.00%	23.08%	17.07%	6.82%

Table 7. Stakeholders' assessment of the effectiveness of tillage practices when integrated in a diversified cropping system (percentage of answers)

	POTATO, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	WHEAT, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	POTATO, LUSITANEAN, SPAIN	WHEAT, LUSITANEAN, SPAIN	POTATO, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	VEGETABLES, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	WHEAT, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	POTATO, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	WHEAT, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	POTATO, NEMORAL, ESTONIA	POTATO, BOREAL, FINLAND	WHEAT, BOREAL, FINLAND
More effective in a diversified cropping system	61.90%	68.42%	74.19%	70.69%	50.00%	60.00%	54.24%	56.25%	60.00%	73.08%	63.41%	68.18%
Equally effective in a diversified cropping system or under monoculture	9.52%	15.79%	6.45%	5.17%	25.00%	32.00%	20.34%	31.25%	10.00%	11.54%	24.39%	22.73%
More effective in a non-diversified monoculture cropping system	4.76%	0.00%	0.00%	1.72%	6.25%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	10.00%	0.00%	2.44%	2.27%
Not compatible with crop diversification	0.00%	5.26%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	4.00%	3.39%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	2.44%	0.00%
I do not know the problem well enough to answer	23.81%	10.53%	19.35%	22.41%	18.75%	4.00%	22.03%	12.50%	20.00%	15.38%	7.32%	6.82%

Table 8. Stakeholders' assessment of the effectiveness of tillage practices when integrated in a rainfed/irrigated cropping system (percentage of answers)

	POTATO, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	WHEAT, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	POTATO, LUSITANIAN, SPAIN	WHEAT, LUSITANIAN, SPAIN	POTATO, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	VEGETABLES, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	WHEAT, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	POTATO, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	WHEAT, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	POTATO, NEMORAL, ESTONIA	POTATO, BOREAL, FINLAND	WHEAT, BOREAL, FINLAND
More effective under irrigation	61.90%	42.11%	37.10%	13.79%	18.75%	16.00%	8.47%	31.25%	20.00%	30.77%	17.07%	4.55%
Equally effective in rainfed and irrigated conditions	28.57%	15.79%	27.42%	20.69%	12.50%	44.00%	28.81%	43.75%	70.00%	19.23%	31.71%	25.00%
More effective in rainfed conditions	0.00%	26.32%	4.84%	31.03%	6.25%	20.00%	10.17%	6.25%	0.00%	11.54%	14.63%	34.09%
I do not know the problem well enough to answer	9.52%	15.79%	30.65%	34.48%	62.50%	20.00%	52.54%	18.75%	10.00%	38.46%	36.59%	36.36%

3.4.2. Fertilization practices

With respect to the **fertilization practices**, stakeholders chose the fertilization practices that they consider as the most adequate for each end-user's need to be fulfilled (the previously assessed objectives). Results for each case study are commented in detail in the annex. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 9) show some differences between crops and areas but more consensus than with tillage practices. Across case studies, stakeholders give the highest ranking scores to the addition of solid organic matter and manures and to green manure with relatively similar scores. Incorporating crop residues in the soil and the use of precision agriculture techniques to optimise the application of fertilizers also receive relatively high ranking scores in some case studies. The use of biostimulants, biofertilizers, mycorrhizas and new generation fertilizers does not receive very high ranking scores, with the exception of the Mediterranean South potato case study, where it is the preferred fertilization alternative, and the Continental potato case study where it is the third highest-scored option. It should be also worth mentioning that the "None of these practices are effective for the problems in the study area" receives the highest ranking score in the Lusitanian case studies and the third preferred option in the Nemoral potato case study.

In the case of potato production, the addition of soil organic matter/manures and the use of green manure are the two preferred alternatives in all case studies, except the Mediterranean South, where they are the second and third alternatives behind the use of biostimulants, biofertilizers, mycorrhizas and new generation fertilizers. The third highest ranking scores correspond to the use of precision agriculture techniques in the Lusitanian, Nemoral and Boreal case studies, and to the use of biostimulants, biofertilizers, mycorrhizas and new generation fertilizers in the Atlantic Central and Continental case studies.

In the case of the Atlantic Central vegetables production, the respondents also give the highest ranking score to both the addition of soil organic matter/manures and the use of green manure, followed by the combination of solid manure with mineral fertilizers (Table 9).

In the case of wheat production, stakeholders in all case studies give the highest ranking score to the addition of soil organic matter/manures, followed by the use of green manure, with the exception of the Boreal case study where it is the other way around. In the case of the Mediterranean South case study, the second and third preferred alternatives are the incorporation of crop residues to the soil and the use of precision agriculture techniques to optimize fertilization. The third preferred alternative in the other wheat case studies are Incorporating crop residues into the soil in the Continental and Atlantic Central case study and the combination of manure and mineral fertilizers in the Lusitanian and Atlantic Central case studies.

Stakeholders were asked about barriers that they perceive that can difficult the adoption of more sustainable fertilization practices in the crop and study area. In the case of the potato case studies, although responses differ significantly from one case study to another, the majority of stakeholders pointed out at the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness and, to a lesser extent, the lack of tradition as the most relevant barriers (Table 10). A significant number of stakeholders also point out at the complexity of their implementation without the help of technical advisory services (Mediterranean South and Lusitanian case studies) and to their lower

profitability (Mediterranean South and Boreal case studies). Stakeholders in the Atlantic Central and Continental case studies also highlight the lack of enabling regulation. Last, stakeholders in the Atlantic Central and Nemoral case studies point out also to their incompatibility with other farming practices. On the other hand, only a minority of stakeholders perceive these fertilization practices as difficult to implement with support of adequate technical advice. With the exception of the Mediterranean South and Boreal case studies, few stakeholders consider the lack of profitability as a barrier for the implementation of more sustainable fertilization practices.

In the case of the Atlantic Central vegetables case study, the interviewed stakeholders consider that the implementation of more sustainable fertilization practices is diffculted by the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness, which is viewed as the most important obstacle, followed by the lack of enabling regulation, the inadequate support from the government on technical issues and the lack of tradition in the region (Table 10). On the other hand, most stakeholders do not perceive these tillage practices as difficult to implement with adequate technical advice and do not perceive that they are not profitable.

In the wheat case studies, although responses differ significantly from one case study to another, the majority of stakeholders pointed out at the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness and the lack of tradition as the most relevant barriers (Table 10). A significant number of stakeholders also point out at the complexity of their implementation without the help of technical advisory services (Mediterranean South and Lusitanian case studies) and to their lower profitability (Mediterranean South and Boreal case studies). Stakeholders in the Atlantic Central and Continental case studies also highlight the lack of technical support from the government and the lack of enabling regulation in the first case study. On the other hand, only a minority of stakeholders perceive these fertilization practices as difficult to implement with support of adequate technical advice. With the exception of the Mediterranean South and Boreal case studies, few stakeholders consider the lack of profitability as a barrier for the implementation of more sustainable fertilization practices.

Regarding the effectiveness of more sustainable fertilization practices when integrated within different cropping systems, in general, and for all crops and study areas, the majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that they are equally or more effective under organic production than under conventional farming (Table 11), more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 12) and more or equally effective under irrigation than under rainfed conditions (Table 13), with the exceptions of the Lusitanian and Boreal Potato case studies, where stakeholders have very differing views about the effectiveness of sustainable fertilization practices when integrated under organic and conventional farming. In the case of wheat, the majority of stakeholders perceive sustainable fertilization practices to be of similar effectiveness under irrigation and rainfed conditions.

Table 9. Stakeholders' assessment of the effectiveness of fertilization practices in order to face the agro-environmental problems in the crops and areas of study (ranking of preferences from the multicriteria assessment)

CASE STUDIES	Incorporating crops residues into the soil	Addition of solid organic matter/manures	Use of green manure	Combination of manure and mineral fertilizers	Precision agriculture to optimise fertilization	Use of biostimulants, biofertilizers, etc.	Addition of slurries	None of these is effective
POTATO, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	0.3426	0.4411	0.4565	0.2899	0.2504	0.5470	0.0000	0.2930
WHEAT, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	0.4651	0.6363	0.2938	0.3070	0.4450	0.2452	0.0000	0.0884
POTATO, LUSITANEAN, SPAIN	0.2450	0.4617	0.1170	0.2628	0.4312	0.2538	0.0000	0.6665
WHEAT, LUSITANEAN, SPAIN	0.2171	0.5977	0.5319	0.3939	0.3331	0.2585	0.0675	0.5954
POTATO, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	0.0926	0.6955	0.5475	0.1397	0.1633	0.2564	0.0000	0.3047
VEGETABLES, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	0.1714	0.6030	0.5962	0.3762	0.1666	0.2626	0.0867	0.1770
WHEAT, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	0.2721	0.7045	0.5912	0.2701	0.2509	0.2191	0.1457	0.1770
POTATO, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	0.3228	0.4620	0.6099	0.2580	0.2033	0.3449		0.2264
WHEAT, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	0.3553	0.5395	0.5081	0.1893	0.3103	0.0000		0.1169
POTATO, NEMORAL, ESTONIA	0.1805	0.4272	0.7099	0.2300	0.3127	0.3092	0.0000	0.4362
POTATO, BOREAL, FINLAND	0.1962	0.6636	0.6272	0.2264	0.3031	0.0600	0.0000	0.2825
WHEAT, BOREAL, FINLAND	0.1927	0.4488	0.8498	0.1616	0.1853	0.1053	0.0274	0.1835

Table 10. Stakeholders' identification of problems that can difficult the implementation of more sustainable fertilization practices (percentage of answers)

	POTATO, MEDITERANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	WHEAT, MEDITERANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	POTATO, LUSITANEAN, SPAIN	WHEAT, LUSITANEAN, SPAIN	POTATO, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	VEGETABLES, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	WHEAT, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	POTATO, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	WHEAT, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	POTATO, NEMORAL, ESTONIA	POTATO, BOREAL, FINLAND	WHEAT, BOREAL, FINLAND
Lack of knowledge among farmers about the effectiveness of farming practices	57.89%	57.89%	56.45%	49.12%	50.00%	52.00%	38.18%	46.67%	20.00%	36.00%	46.34%	52.50%
Lack of tradition in the region	47.37%	36.84%	37.10%	38.60%	28.57%	32.00%	23.64%	26.67%	30.00%	40.00%	34.15%	40.00%
Complex/difficult to carry out without technical advice	31.58%	26.32%	62.90%	57.89%	14.29%	8.00%	9.09%	13.33%	20.00%	16.00%	14.63%	15.00%
Complex/difficult to carry out even with technical advice	15.79%	10.53%	3.23%	5.26%	7.14%	4.00%	14.55%	33.33%	10.00%	0.00%	12.20%	7.50%
The existing machinery does not support this practice	5.26%	5.26%	0.00%	1.75%	21.43%	12.00%	14.55%	20.00%	30.00%	12.00%	21.95%	17.50%
Inadequate/insufficient support from the government on technical issues	15.79%	5.26%	12.90%	10.53%	14.29%	32.00%	29.09%	0.00%	40.00%	16.00%	9.76%	7.50%
Lack of enabling legislation/regulation	0.00%	5.26%	6.45%	5.26%	28.57%	40.00%	34.54%	26.67%	10.00%	4.00%	4.88%	2.50%
The costs are too high	31.58%	36.84%	8.06%	7.02%	7.14%	24.00%	32.73%	13.33%	10.00%	28.00%	24.39%	30.00%
The benefits do not outweigh the costs	31.58%	26.32%	1.61%	1.75%	0.00%	16.00%	16.36%	13.33%	40.00%	16.00%	29.27%	22.50%
Incompatibility with other farming practices	15.79%	15.79%	3.23%	0.00%	28.57%	8.00%	9.09%	13.33%	0.00%	24.00%	14.63%	2.50%

Table 11. Stakeholders' assessment of the effectiveness of fertilization practices when integrated in an organic production system (percentage of answers)

	POTATO, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	WHEAT, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	POTATO, LUSITANIAN, SPAIN	WHEAT, LUSITANIAN, SPAIN	POTATO, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	VEGETABLES, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	WHEAT, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	POTATO, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	WHEAT, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	POTATO, NEMORAL, ESTONIA	POTATO, BOREAL, FINLAND	WHEAT, BOREAL, FINLAND
More effective under organic production	36.84%	26.32%	0.00%	7.02%	21.43%	32.00%	5.45%	20.00%	10.00%	16.00%	26.83%	25.00%
Equally effective under organic and conventional farming	21.05%	52.63%	22.58%	19.30%	64.29%	36.00%	45.45%	53.33%	50.00%	52.00%	29.27%	52.50%
More effective under conventional farming	5.26%	5.26%	9.68%	3.51%	14.29%	12.00%	10.91%	13.33%	30.00%	0.00%	26.83%	12.50%
Not compatible with organic production	5.26%	0.00%	37.10%	42.11%	0.00%	12.00%	12.73%	6.67%	0.00%	0.00%	7.32%	7.50%
I do not know the problem well enough to answer	31.58%	15.79%	30.65%	28.07%	0.00%	8.00%	25.45%	6.67%	10.00%	32.00%	9.76%	2.50%

Table 12. Stakeholders' assessment of the effectiveness of fertilization practices when integrated in a diversified cropping system (percentage of answers)

	POTATO, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	WHEAT, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	POTATO, LUSITANIAN, SPAIN	WHEAT, LUSITANIAN, SPAIN	POTATO, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	VEGETABLES, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	WHEAT, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	POTATO, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	WHEAT, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	POTATO, NEMORAL, ESTONIA	POTATO, BOREAL, FINLAND	WHEAT, BOREAL, FINLAND
More effective in a diversified cropping system	68.42%	63.16%	61.29%	66.67%	64.29%	48.00%	45.45%	53.33%	60.00%	72.00%	58.54%	72.50%
Equally effective in a diversified cropping system or under monoculture	15.79%	21.05%	11.29%	5.26%	14.29%	32.00%	29.09%	33.33%	20.00%	16.00%	29.27%	25.00%
More effective in a non-diversified monoculture cropping system	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	7.14%	0.00%	0.00%	6.67%	10.00%	0.00%	2.44%	2.50%
Not compatible with crop diversification	0.00%	5.26%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	8.00%	3.64%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
I do not know the problem well enough to answer	15.79%	10.53%	27.42%	28.07%	14.29%	12.00%	21.82%	6.67%	10.00%	12.00%	9.76%	0.00%

Table 13. Stakeholders' assessment of the effectiveness of fertilization practices when integrated in a rainfed/irrigated cropping system (percentage of answers)

	POTATO, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	WHEAT, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	POTATO, LUSITANIAN, SPAIN	WHEAT, LUSITANIAN, SPAIN	POTATO, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	VEGETABLES, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	WHEAT, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	POTATO, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	WHEAT, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	POTATO, NEMORAL, ESTONIA	POTATO, BOREAL, FINLAND	WHEAT, BOREAL, FINLAND
More effective under irrigation	63.16%	36.84%	30.65%	14.04%	14.29%	16.00%	9.09%	26.67%	20.00%	36.00%	26.83%	15.00%
Equally effective in both rainfed and irrigated conditions	21.05%	31.58%	25.81%	14.04%	42.86%	52.00%	32.73%	53.33%	40.00%	24.00%	34.15%	35.00%
More effective in rainfed production	5.26%	26.32%	4.84%	31.58%	7.14%	8.00%	12.73%	6.67%	20.00%	8.00%	9.76%	25.00%
I do not know the problem well enough to answer	10.53%	5.26%	38.71%	40.35%	35.71%	24.00%	45.45%	13.33%	20.00%	32.00%	29.27%	25.00%

3.4.3. Soil conservation practices

Regarding **soil conservation practices**, stakeholders chose the soil conservation practices that they consider as the most adequate for each end-users' need to be fulfilled (the previously assessed objectives). The results from the multicriteria assessment are shown in Table 14, while more detailed results for each case study are commented in the annex. Significant differences between crops and areas are found.

In the case of potato production, stakeholders in the Mediterranean South, Lusitanian, Nemoral and Boreal potato case studies give the highest ranking score as the preferred soil conservation practices to crop diversification, followed by the addition of organic matter, the latter being also selected as one of the preferred fertilization practices in most case studies (Table 14). In the Continental case study, crop diversification and vegetation covers (natural or cultivated) are the most preferred alternatives, while in the Atlantic Central case study catch crops receive the highest ranking score, followed by mulching and maintaining natural vegetation covers or cover crops. In general, the third highest ranking score is given to soil cover alternatives, such as mulching, natural vegetation covers or cover crops, although some case studies find more effective avoiding plant protection products or the use of catch crops.

A similar result is obtained in the case of the Atlantic Central vegetables case study, where catch crops receive the highest ranking score, closely followed by mulching and, to a lesser extent, by natural vegetation covers or cover crops.

In the wheat case studies, results are more dispersed than in the potato case studies. The most preferred alternatives for soil conservation are crop diversification in the Lusitanian, Continental and Boreal case studies, vegetation soil covers in the Mediterranean South case study and catch crops in the Atlantic Central case studies (Table 14). The following most preferred alternatives relate to soil cover alternatives, such as mulching or cover crops, and to the addition of organic matter that is the second most preferred alternative in the Mediterranean South and Lusitanian and Boreal case studies.

Stakeholders were asked about barriers that they perceive that can difficult the adoption of soil conservation practices in the crop and study area. In the case of the potato case studies, although responses differ significantly from one case study to another, the majority of stakeholders point out at the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness and, to a lesser extent, the lack of tradition as the most relevant barriers (Table 15). A significant number of stakeholders in Mediterranean South and Lusitanian case studies also point out at the complexity of their implementation without the help of technical advisory services. The lack of technical support from the government and the lack of enabling regulation is also highlighted by stakeholders in the Atlantic Central case study. On the other hand, only a minority of stakeholders perceive soil conservation practices as difficult to implement with support of adequate technical advice or unprofitable.

In the case of the Atlantic Central vegetables case study, the interviewed stakeholders consider that the implementation of soil conservation practices is difficulted by the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness, which is viewed as the most important obstacle, followed by the lack of enabling regulation, the lack of tradition in the region and the high

implementation costs (Table 15). On the other hand, most stakeholders do not perceive these tillage practices as difficult to implement with adequate technical advice and any of them perceive that they are not profitable.

In the wheat case studies, although responses differ significantly from one case study to another, the majority of stakeholders pointed out at the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness and the lack of tradition as the most relevant barriers (Table 15). A significant number of stakeholders in the Mediterranean South and Lusitanian case studies also point out at the complexity of their implementation without the help of technical advisory services, while stakeholders in the Atlantic Central also highlight the lack of enabling regulation. Stakeholders in the Atlantic Central and Continental case studies also highlight the high implementation cost of soil conservation practices. On the other hand, only a minority of stakeholders perceive these fertilization practices as difficult to implement with support of adequate technical advice or consider the lack of profitability as a barrier for the implementation of more soil conservation practices.

Regarding the effectiveness of more sustainable soil conservation practices when integrated within different cropping systems, in general, and for all crops and study areas, the majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that they are equally or more effective under organic production than under conventional farming (Table 16), more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 17) and more or equally effective under irrigation than under rainfed conditions (Table 18), with the exceptions of the Lusitanian potato and wheat case studies, where stakeholders have very differing views about the effectiveness of soil conservation practices when integrated under organic and conventional farming. In the case of wheat, the majority of stakeholders perceive sustainable fertilization practices to be of similar effectiveness under both conventional and organic farming and under both irrigation and rainfed conditions.

Table 14. Stakeholders' assessment of the effectiveness of soil conservation practices in order to face the agro-environmental problems in the crops and areas of study (ranking of preferences from the multicriteria assessment)

CASE STUDIES	Mulching (with crushed offcuts from pruning, etc.)	Maintain vegetati on cover (natural or cover crops)	Maintain strips of vegetation between lines	Hedges or natural vegetation on the edges of the plots	Erosion barriers or margins with vegetation	Additio n of organic matter	Crop diversification	Use of catch crops to reduce N/P leaching	Avoiding plant protectio n products	None of these is effective
POTATO, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	0.3375	0.2955	0.2342	0.0899	0.2985	0.5625	0.6658	0.1813		0.3422
WHEAT, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	0.5644	0.6823	0.2046	0.2160	0.3433	0.5761	0.4458		0.0810	0.0000
POTATO, LUSITANEAN, SPAIN	0.1223	0.2360	0.0550	0.0589	0.0767	0.3671	0.7062	0.2220	0.2621	0.5474
WHEAT, LUSITANEAN, SPAIN	0.1489	0.3029	0.0000	0.0335	0.0000	0.3464	0.7556	0.2253	0.1595	0.5239
POTATO, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	0.4255	0.3941	0.1943	0.2897	0.1717			0.6185	0.3888	0.2859
VEGETABLES, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	0.5682	0.3349	0.1577	0.1862	0.0944			0.6281	0.2260	0.3134
WHEAT, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	0.4521	0.4034	0.1222	0.2555	0.0353			0.7785	0.0756	0.1579
POTATO, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	0.2903	0.6359	0.1130	0.0000			0.6351	0.3331	0.1854	0.3394
WHEAT, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	0.0000	0.3757	0.2638	0.0878			1.0000	0.1327	0.0000	0.1027
POTATO, NEMORAL, ESTONIA						0.3974	0.7969		0.2224	0.0722
POTATO, BOREAL, FINLAND						0.4283	0.8319		0.1301	0.0998
WHEAT, BOREAL, FINLAND						0.3432	0.8347	0.3102	0.1731	0.0970

Table 15. Stakeholders' identification of problems that can difficult the implementation of more sustainable soil conservation practices (percentage of answers)

	POTATO, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	WHEAT, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	POTATO, LUSITANEAN, SPAIN	WHEAT, LUSITANEAN, SPAIN	POTATO, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	VEGETABLES, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	WHEAT, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	POTATO, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	WHEAT, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	POTATO, NEMORAL, ESTONIA	POTATO, BOREAL, FINLAND	WHEAT, BOREAL, FINLAND
Lack of knowledge among farmers about the effectiveness of farming practices	66.67%	63.16%	61.29%	49.12%	50.00%	63.64%	34.78%	33.33%	22.22%	52.00%	48.78%	60.53%
Lack of tradition in the region	44.44%	42.11%	45.16%	40.35%	50.00%	40.91%	26.09%	20.00%	11.11%	20.00%	31.71%	31.58%
Complex/difficult to carry out without technical advice	38.89%	52.63%	54.84%	63.16%	21.43%	13.64%	10.87%	26.67%	44.44%	12.00%	14.63%	15.79%
Complex/difficult to carry out even with technical advice	5.56%	5.26%	1.61%	3.51%	7.14%	9.09%	13.04%	26.67%	0.00%	4.00%	4.88%	5.26%
The existing machinery does not support this practice	5.56%	10.53%	3.23%	0.00%	0.00%	4.55%	13.04%	13.33%	22.22%	16.00%	21.95%	21.05%
Inadequate/insufficient support from the government on technical issues	16.67%	10.53%	14.52%	10.53%	42.86%	31.82%	19.57%	6.67%	22.22%	24.00%	14.63%	13.16%
Lack of enabling legislation/regulation	11.11%	10.53%	4.84%	3.51%	42.86%	36.37%	28.26%	6.67%	11.11%	4.00%	7.32%	5.26%
The costs are too high	27.78%	21.05%	3.23%	3.51%	28.57%	31.82%	26.09%	6.67%	33.33%	20.00%	21.95%	21.05%
The benefits do not outweigh the costs	16.67%	15.79%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	9.09%	21.74%	20.00%	11.11%	12.00%	21.95%	15.79%
Incompatibility with other farming practices	22.22%	15.79%	3.23%	3.51%	7.14%	22.73%	10.87%	6.67%	0.00%	16.00%	7.32%	2.63%

Table 16. Stakeholders' assessment of the effectiveness of soil conservation practices when integrated in in an organic farming production system (percentage of answers)

	POTATO, MEDITERANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	WHEAT, MEDITERANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	POTATO, LUSITANEAN, SPAIN	WHEAT, LUSITANEAN, SPAIN	POTATO, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	VEGETABLES, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	WHEAT, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	POTATO, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	WHEAT, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	POTATO, NEMORAL, ESTONIA	POTATO, BOREAL, FINLAND	WHEAT, BOREAL, FINLAND
More effective under organic production	50.00%	36.84%	1.61%	8.77%	7.14%	27.27%	4.35%	20.00%	22.22%	4.00%	24.39%	15.79%
Equally effective under organic and conventional farming	33.33%	57.89%	32.26%	15.79%	85.71%	40.91%	52.17%	66.67%	55.56%	84.00%	53.66%	73.68%
More effective under conventional farming	5.56%	0.00%	4.84%	5.26%	0.00%	27.27%	13.04%	6.67%	11.11%	0.00%	9.76%	5.26%
Not compatible with organic production	5.56%	0.00%	33.87%	36.84%	0.00%	0.00%	13.04%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	4.88%	2.63%
I do not know the problem well enough to answer	5.56%	5.26%	27.42%	33.33%	7.14%	4.55%	17.39%	6.67%	11.11%	12.00%	7.32%	2.63%

Table 17. Stakeholders' assessment of the effectiveness of soil conservation when integrated in a diversified cropping system (percentage of answers)

	POTATO, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	WHEAT, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	POTATO, LUSITANIAN, SPAIN	WHEAT, LUSITANIAN, SPAIN	POTATO, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	VEGETABLES, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	WHEAT, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	POTATO, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	WHEAT, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	POTATO, NEMORAL, ESTONIA	POTATO, BOREAL, FINLAND	WHEAT, BOREAL, FINLAND
More effective in a diversified cropping system	77.78%	68.42%	62.90%	63.16%	64.29%	45.45%	52.17%	53.33%	77.78%	72.00%	53.66%	52.63%
Equally effective in a diversified cropping system or under monoculture	16.67%	15.79%	9.68%	3.51%	21.43%	27.27%	30.43%	33.33%	0.00%	12.00%	29.27%	39.47%
More effective in a non-diversified monoculture cropping system	0.00%	5.26%	0.00%	0.00%	7.14%	13.64%	0.00%	6.67%	11.11%	4.00%	4.88%	7.89%
Not compatible with crop diversification	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	4.55%	4.35%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
I do not know the problem well enough to answer	5.56%	10.53%	27.42%	33.33%	7.14%	9.09%	13.04%	6.67%	11.11%	12.00%	12.20%	0.00%

Table 18. Stakeholders' assessment of the effectiveness of soil conservation practices when integrated in a rainfed/irrigated cropping system (percentage of answers)

	POTATO, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	WHEAT, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	POTATO, LUSITANIAN, SPAIN	WHEAT, LUSITANIAN, SPAIN	POTATO, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	VEGETABLES, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	WHEAT, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	POTATO, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	WHEAT, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	POTATO, NEMORAL, ESTONIA	POTATO, BOREAL, FINLAND	WHEAT, BOREAL, FINLAND
More effective under irrigation	61.11%	31.58%	29.03%	7.02%	7.14%	22.73%	15.22%	26.67%	11.11%	28.00%	14.63%	5.26%
Equally effective in both rainfed and irrigated conditions	33.33%	52.63%	32.26%	19.30%	42.86%	50.00%	36.96%	53.33%	55.56%	32.00%	48.78%	44.74%
More effective in rainfed production	0.00%	10.53%	4.84%	33.33%	7.14%	9.09%	6.52%	6.67%	11.11%	8.00%	9.76%	23.68%
I do not know the problem well enough to answer	5.56%	5.26%	33.87%	40.35%	42.86%	18.18%	41.30%	13.33%	22.22%	32.00%	26.83%	26.32%

3.4.4. Pest and disease control practices

Moving to the results from the multicriteria assessment of **pest and disease control practices**, these are shown in Table 19, while more detailed results for each case study are commented in the corresponding annex. Significant differences between crops and areas are found. In some case studies, stakeholders have given the highest ranking score to crop diversification while others have opted for the use of pest alerts, in both cases with significant differences in the ranking scores given to these practices and to those with the second highest ranking scores. In some case studies, the second preferred alternative is the use of pesticides but with significant lower ranking scores than the preferred alternative.

Crop diversification is considered as the most effective pest and disease control practice in the Mediterranean South, Continental, Lusitanian, Nemoral and Boreal cases, followed by the increase of soil invertebrates biodiversity in the first two cases and the use of pesticides in the last three ones (Table 19). In the Atlantic Central case studies, the majority of stakeholders chose the “none of these practices are effective” that is the highest ranked alternative, more than doubling up the ranking score given to the use of pest alerts and trap crops in the vegetables and wheat case studies and to Allelopathic crops and pest alerts in the potato case study.

Stakeholders were asked about barriers that they perceive that can difficult the adoption of more sustainable pest and disease control practices in the crop and study area. In the case of the potato case studies, although responses differ from one case study to another, the majority of stakeholders point out at the lack of farmers’ knowledge regarding their effectiveness, the need to have adequate technical advice due to their complexity and their higher costs as the most relevant barriers (Table 20). The lack of enabling legislation/regulation is also highlighted by stakeholders in the Atlantic Central case study. On the other hand, only a minority of stakeholders perceive more sustainable pest and disease control practices as difficult to implement with support of adequate technical advice or think that they are not profitable.

In the case of the Atlantic Central vegetables case study, a majority of stakeholders consider that the implementation of more sustainable pest and disease control practices is difficulted by the lack of farmers’ knowledge regarding their effectiveness, which is viewed as the most important obstacle, followed by the lack of tradition in the area and the lack of enabling legislation/regulation (Table 20). On the other hand, most stakeholders do not perceive these tillage practices as difficult to implement.

In the wheat case studies, although responses differ from one case study to another, the majority of stakeholders point out at the lack of farmers’ knowledge regarding their effectiveness, the need to have adequate technical advice due to their complexity and the lack of tradition in the area (Table 20). The lack of enabling legislation/regulation is also highlighted by stakeholders in the Atlantic Central case study, while their high implementation costs are highlighted as a relevant barrier in the Mediterranean South, and Continental case studies. On the other hand, only a minority of stakeholders perceive more sustainable pest and disease control practices as difficult to implement with support of adequate technical advice or think that they are not profitable.

Regarding the effectiveness of more sustainable pest and disease control practices when integrated within different cropping systems, in general, and for all crops and study areas, the

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majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that they are equally or more effective under organic production than under conventional farming (Table 21), more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 22) and more or equally effective under irrigation than under rainfed conditions (Table 23), with the exceptions of the Lusitanian potato and wheat case studies, where stakeholders have very differing views about the effectiveness of more sustainable pest and disease control practices when integrated under organic and conventional farming. In the case of wheat, the majority of stakeholders perceive more sustainable pest and disease control practices to be of similar effectiveness under both conventional and organic farming and under both irrigation and rainfed conditions.

Table 19. Stakeholders' assessment of the effectiveness of pest and diseases control practices in order to face the agro-environmental problems in the crops and areas of study (ranking of preferences from the multicriteria assessment)

CASE STUDIES	Pests alerts	Crop diversification	Trap crops	Increase soil invertebrates biodiversity	Use of biostimulants and mycorrhizae	Use of pesticides	Ploughing	Allelopathic crops	None of these is effective
POTATO, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	0.1707	0.9252	0.1685	0.3779	0.3207	0.2059		0.0000	0.3064
WHEAT, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	0.1933	0.7580	0.1887	0.4924	0.3598	0.0000		0.1217	0.2630
POTATO, LUSITANEAN, SPAIN	0.1874	0.7878	0.0658	0.2486	0.2381	0.3254	0.2864		0.4946
WHEAT, LUSITANEAN, SPAIN	0.1547	0.9383	0.0822	0.1793	0.2147	0.2290	0.2249		0.3803
POTATO, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	0.3271		0.0790			0.2155		0.4005	0.7535
VEGETABLES, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	0.2630		0.3146			0.2120		0.1281	0.7947
WHEAT, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	0.3459		0.3757			0.3316		0.3355	0.7316
POTATO, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	0.0000	0.6459	0.2226	0.3911	0.3589	0.3710		0.1206	0.2210
WHEAT, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	0.2174	0.6703	0.0000	0.3438	0.2503	0.2623		0.0000	0.3754
POTATO, NEMORAL, ESTONIA	0.1960	0.7868				0.2998	0.1579		0.1387
POTATO, BOREAL, FINLAND	0.0331	1.0000				0.1499	0.1491		0.1348
WHEAT, BOREAL, FINLAND	0.0190	1.0000				0.0713	0.1018		0.1639

Table 20. Stakeholders' identification of problems that can difficult the implementation of more sustainable pest and disease control practices (percentage of answers)

	POTATO, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	WHEAT, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	POTATO, LUSITANEAN, SPAIN	WHEAT, LUSITANEAN, SPAIN	POTATO, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	VEGETABLES, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	WHEAT, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	POTATO, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	WHEAT, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	POTATO, NEMORAL, ESTONIA	POTATO, BOREAL, FINLAND	WHEAT, BOREAL, FINLAND
Lack of knowledge among farmers about the effectiveness of farming practices	44.44%	52.63%	48.39%	45.61%	42.86%	59.09%	38.10%	28.57%	28.57%	44.00%	41.46%	44.74%
Lack of tradition in the region	22.22%	31.58%	33.87%	36.84%	14.29%	27.27%	19.05%	14.29%	14.29%	16.00%	39.02%	42.11%
Complex/difficult to carry out without technical advice	38.89%	57.89%	62.90%	73.68%	14.29%	18.18%	26.19%	21.43%	28.57%	12.00%	14.63%	15.79%
Complex/difficult to carry out even with technical advice	5.56%	15.79%	4.84%	3.51%	7.14%	13.64%	11.90%	35.71%	14.29%	12.00%	4.88%	10.53%
The existing machinery does not support this practice	0.00%	0.00%	1.61%	0.00%	0.00%	4.55%	9.52%	14.29%	14.29%	12.00%	12.20%	18.42%
Inadequate/insufficient support from the government on technical issues	16.67%	15.79%	14.52%	14.04%	7.14%	22.73%	21.43%	7.14%	14.29%	12.00%	12.20%	7.89%
Lack of enabling legislation/regulation	27.78%	5.26%	6.45%	3.51%	28.57%	27.27%	30.95%	21.43%	0.00%	12.00%	7.32%	2.63%
The costs are too high	38.89%	26.32%	11.29%	5.26%	7.14%	22.73%	23.81%	14.29%	42.86%	28.00%	21.95%	18.42%
The benefits do not outweigh the costs	16.67%	21.05%	1.61%	1.75%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	7.14%	14.29%	20.00%	21.95%	15.79%
Incompatibility with other farming practices	16.67%	5.26%	3.22%	1.75%	0.00%	4.55%	14.29%	0.00%	0.00%	4.00%	12.20%	2.63%

Table 21. Stakeholders' assessment of the effectiveness of pest and disease control practices when integrated in an organic farming production system (percentage of answers)

	POTATO, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	WHEAT, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	POTATO, LUSITANIAN, SPAIN	WHEAT, LUSITANIAN, SPAIN	POTATO, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	VEGETABLES, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	WHEAT, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	POTATO, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	WHEAT, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	POTATO, NEMORAL, ESTONIA	POTATO, BOREAL, FINLAND	WHEAT, BOREAL, FINLAND
More effective under organic production	33.33%	26.32%	6.45%	8.77%	0.00%	36.36%	4.76%	14.29%	14.29%	16.00%	17.07%	21.05%
Equally effective under organic and conventional farming	27.78%	52.63%	19.35%	14.04%	50.00%	36.36%	42.86%	64.29%	57.14%	48.00%	46.34%	63.16%
More effective under conventional farming	16.67%	15.79%	8.06%	7.02%	14.29%	9.09%	9.52%	7.14%	14.29%	8.00%	17.07%	10.53%
Not compatible with organic production	0.00%	0.00%	40.32%	40.35%	21.43%	9.09%	21.43%	7.14%	0.00%	4.00%	7.32%	2.63%
I do not know the problem well enough to answer	22.22%	5.26%	25.81%	29.82%	14.29%	9.09%	21.43%	7.14%	14.29%	24.00%	12.20%	2.63%

Table 22. Stakeholders' qualitative assessment of the effectiveness of pest and disease control practices when integrated in a diversified cropping system (percentage of answers)

	POTATO, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	WHEAT, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	POTATO, LUSITANEAN, SPAIN	WHEAT, LUSITANEAN, SPAIN	POTATO, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	VEGETABLES, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	WHEAT, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	POTATO, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	WHEAT, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	POTATO, NEMORAL, ESTONIA	POTATO, BOREAL, FINLAND	WHEAT, BOREAL, FINLAND
More effective in a diversified cropping system	77.78%	78.95%	59.68%	64.91%	50.00%	45.45%	45.24%	57.14%	71.43%	52.00%	46.34%	42.11%
Equally effective in a diversified cropping system or under monoculture	5.56%	21.05%	11.29%	3.51%	21.43%	22.73%	28.57%	28.57%	0.00%	24.00%	34.15%	44.74%
More effective in a non-diversified monoculture cropping system	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	14.29%	9.09%	2.38%	7.14%	14.29%	4.00%	4.88%	7.89%
Not compatible with crop diversification	5.56%	0.00%	1.61%	0.00%	0.00%	9.09%	4.76%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
I do not know the problem well enough to answer	11.11%	0.00%	27.42%	31.58%	14.29%	13.64%	19.05%	7.14%	14.29%	20.00%	14.63%	5.26%

Table 23. Stakeholders' assessment of the effectiveness of pest and disease control practices when integrated in a rainfed/irrigated cropping system (percentage of answers)

	POTATO, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	WHEAT, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	POTATO, LUSITANIAN, SPAIN	WHEAT, LUSITANIAN, SPAIN	POTATO, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	VEGETABLES, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	WHEAT, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	POTATO, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	WHEAT, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	POTATO, NEMORAL, ESTONIA	POTATO, BOREAL, FINLAND	WHEAT, BOREAL, FINLAND
More effective under irrigation	50.00%	36.84%	29.03%	7.02%	21.43%	18.18%	9.52%	35.71%	14.29%	16.00%	12.20%	2.63%
Equally effective in both rainfed and irrigated conditions	33.33%	47.37%	30.65%	21.05%	28.57%	50.00%	38.10%	42.86%	57.14%	44.00%	43.90%	44.74%
More effective in rainfed production	0.00%	5.26%	6.45%	28.07%	0.00%	9.09%	7.14%	7.14%	14.29%	4.00%	12.20%	15.79%
I do not know the problem well enough to answer	16.67%	10.53%	33.87%	43.86%	50.00%	22.73%	45.24%	14.29%	14.29%	36.00%	31.71%	36.84%

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3.4.5. Summary of the proposed farming practices

The farming practices with the highest scores in each case study are highlighted in bold font in Table 4, Table 9, Table 14 and Table 19, while Table 24 summarises the most effective practice per type based on the results from Table 4, Table 9, Table 14 and Table 19, illustrating the perception of the interviewed stakeholders regarding how each cropping system could be oriented towards a more sustainable production.

Table 24. Most effective farming practices according to the stakeholders' qualitative assessment (based on the ranking of preferences from the multicriteria assessment that is shown in brackets)

CASE STUDIES	TILLAGE PRACTICES	FERTILIZATION PRACTICES	SOIL CONSERVATION PRACTICES	PEST AND DISEASE CONTROL PRACTICES
POTATO, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	Minimum tillage (0.82); No tillage without herbicides (0.53)	Use of biostimulants, biofertilizers... (0.55); Green manure (0.46); Addition of solid organic matter (0.44)	Crop diversification (0.67); Addition of organic matter (0.56)	Crop diversification (0.93); Increase soil invertebrate biodiversity (0.38)
WHEAT, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH, SPAIN	Minimum tillage (0.74); Contour tillage (0.47)	Addition of solid organic matter (0.64); Incorporating crops residues to soil (0.47); Precision agriculture (0.45)	Vegetation covers (0.68); Addition of organic matter (0.58); Mulching (0.56)	Crop diversification (0.76); Increase soil invertebrate biodiversity (0.49)
POTATO, LUSITANEAN, SPAIN	Conventional tillage (0.80); Shallow tillage (0.39)	Addition of solid organic matter/manures (0.46); Precision agriculture (0.43)	Crop diversification (0.71); Addition of organic matter (0.37)	Crop diversification (0.79); Use of pesticides (0.32)
WHEAT, LUSITANEAN, SPAIN	Conventional tillage (0.65); Shallow tillage (0.47)	Addition of solid organic matter/manures (0.60); Use of green manure (0.53)	Crop diversification (0.76); Addition of organic matter (0.35)	Crop diversification (0.94); Use of pesticides (0.23)
POTATO, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	Minimum tillage (0.59); Conventional tillage (0.40)	Addition of solid organic matter/manures (0.70); Use of green manure (0.55)	Catch crops to reduce N/P leaching (0.62); Mulching / Vegetation covers (0.43)	Allelopathic crops (0.40); Pest alerts (0.33)
VEGETABLES, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	Minimum tillage (0.70); Shallow tillage (0.58)	Addition of solid organic matter/manures (0.60); Use of green manure (0.60)	Catch crops to reduce N/P leaching (0.63); Mulching (0.57)	Trap crops (0.31); Pest alerts (0.26)
WHEAT, ATLANTIC CENTRAL, BELGIUM	Conventional tillage (0.66); Minimum tillage (0.56)	Addition of solid organic matter/manures (0.70); Use of green manure (0.59)	Catch crops to reduce N/P leaching (0.78); Mulching (0.55)	Trap crops (0.38); Pest alerts (0.36)

CASE STUDIES	TILLAGE PRACTICES	FERTILIZATION PRACTICES	SOIL CONSERVATION PRACTICES	PEST AND DISEASE CONTROL PRACTICES
POTATO, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	Minimum tillage (0.52); Conventional tillage (0.50)	Use of green manure (0.61); Addition of solid organic matter/manures (0.46)	Vegetation covers (0.64); Crop diversification (0.64)	Crop diversification (0.66); Increase soil invertebrate biodiversity (0.39)
WHEAT, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY	Minimum tillage (0.59); Conventional tillage (0.37)	Addition of solid organic matter/manures (0.54); Use of green manure (0.51)	Crop diversification (1.00); Vegetation covers (0.38)	Crop diversification (0.67); Increase soil invertebrate biodiversity (0.34)
POTATO, NEMORAL, ESTONIA	Conventional tillage (0.71); Minimum tillage (0.43)	Use of green manure (0.71); Addition of solid organic matter/manures (0.43)	Crop diversification (0.80); Addition of organic matter (0.40)	Crop diversification (0.79); Use of pesticides (0.30)
POTATO, BOREAL, FINLAND	Minimum tillage (0.50); Conventional tillage (0.43); No tillage w/o herbic (0.42)	Addition of solid organic matter/manures (0.66); Use of green manure (0.63)	Crop diversification (0.83); Addition of organic matter (0.43)	Crop diversification (1.00)
WHEAT, BOREAL, FINLAND	Shallow tillage (0.68); No tillage w/o herbicides / Minimum tillage (0.42)	Use of green manure (0.85); Addition of solid organic matter/manures (0.45)	Crop diversification (0.84); Addition of organic matter (0.34)	Crop diversification (1.00)

3.5. Discussion groups

The results of the survey were presented to a wider audience of different stakeholders in discussion groups with the aim of validating and complementing such results, following the format already described in section 2.2 of this document. The minutes describing the development of each of the discussion group and their outcomes regarding the validity of the survey results are included in annex 2 (Outcomes of discussion groups in relation with the survey to stakeholders).

In general, participants in discussion groups confirmed the validity of the results from the survey. A general consensus with the major agronomic problems and end-users' needs identified in the survey across case study areas come out from the different discussion groups. Additionally, participants in some discussion groups pointed at the importance of economic problems (marketing and profitability issues) that were not addressed in the survey, which focused on agronomic problems.

Participants in discussion groups also confirmed the general suitability of the preferred farming practices selected by survey respondents to cope with the major agro-environmental problems in each crop and case study area. However, participants pointed out to some problems with the selected practices, such as the need to use local manure to avoid importing plagues or the increased incidence of weeds when using minimum tillage.

The most fruitful discussion related to the barriers for the adoption of more sustainable farming practices. Despite the general consensus existing with the survey results, participants pointed out at additional issues. Participants in several discussion groups identified the small farm size as a very relevant barrier to crop diversification. The need to contract harvesting machinery for rotation crops in potato farms, what increases production costs, and the lack of marketing channels for these diversified crops were also identified as relevant barriers for crop diversification. Additionally, the lack of government support, the fact that many technical advisors work for input suppliers, and the inadequate legislation concerning manure use were pointed out by some discussion groups as other very relevant barriers for the adoption of the proposed farming practices.

4 Concluding remarks

This report summarizes the methodology and results of all activities carried out within task 2.1, including a survey to stakeholders and discussion groups with stakeholders. The survey to stakeholders has helped to identify the most relevant agri-environmental problems and related end-users' needs in each of the 15 case studies of SoildiverAgro and to assess the practical potential for the integration of farming practices that enhance soil biodiversity in the different cropping systems. The agri-environmental problems and objectives for actions identified are consistent with the specific nature of the agricultural system analysed in each case study. Most relevant priorities for action identified by stakeholders are concerned with the improvement of soil conditions, namely organic matter content, structure and fertility, but also with the control of pest, diseases and weeds.

The survey results illustrate how stakeholders perceive that each agricultural system could be oriented towards a more sustainable production. Although there is a controversy between the use of conventional tillage and less intensive tillage options, and conventional tillage is the preferred tillage alternative in some of the case studies, a majority of stakeholders consider that shifting to less intensive tillage alternatives is a must to face the agri-environmental problem in their corresponding study area, with a preference for minimum and shallow tillage.

Regarding fertilization practices, stakeholders across most case studies coincide in choosing both the addition of solid organic matter and manures and the use of green manure as the most effective fertilization alternatives. Incorporating crop residues in the soil and the use of precision agriculture techniques to optimise the application of fertilizers are also perceived as effective alternatives. This is consistent with the relevance given by stakeholders to the need for improving soil conditions. Other promising alternatives, such as the use of biostimulants, biofertilizers, mycorrhizas and new generation fertilizers are not perceived as very effective alternatives with the exception of stakeholders in the Mediterranean South and Continental potato case studies, what could be caused by the lack of knowledge regarding these alternatives in other case studies. In any case, stakeholders in general point at the need for a shift towards the use of organic fertilization sources (crop residues, compost, manure, etc.).

The preferred soil conservation practices seem to be, in general, more oriented towards improving soil conditions than to avoiding soil loss. More precisely, crop diversification and the addition of solid organic matter are perceived as the most effective alternatives in many case studies. Soil cover alternatives, such as such as mulching, natural vegetation covers or cover crops, are also pointed out as effective options in several case studies, while catch crops are the preferred alternative in the Atlantic Central case studies.

Regarding the control of pest and diseases, while stakeholders in several case studies clearly opt for crop diversification and increasing invertebrates soil biodiversity, in other case studies they opt for the use of pest alerts and trap crops as more effective alternatives.

Stakeholders were also asked about barriers that they perceive that can difficult the adoption of more sustainable farming practices. Although there are significance differences between case studies, the majority of stakeholders point out at the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding the effectiveness of practices, the lack of tradition among farmers and the need to have adequate technical advice due to the complexity of some farming practices as the most relevant barriers.

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In some cases, stakeholders highlight the lack of support of the government on technical issues, what is directly related with the need for technical advice to implement more sustainable farming practices. The lack of enabling legislation/regulation is also highlighted by stakeholders in some case studies, especially with respect to pest and disease control practices. Although some stakeholders point out at the relatively higher implementation cost of some farming practices, in general, only a minority of stakeholders perceive more sustainable farming practices as difficult to implement with support of adequate technical advice or think that they are not profitable. These results highlight the need for improved technical advice to foster the adoption of more sustainable farming practices.

Last, regarding the effectiveness of more sustainable farming practices when integrated within different cropping systems, in general, the vast majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that farming practices are more effective in addressing each cropping system's needs when integrated within a diversified cropping system. With some exceptions, a majority also think that such effectiveness is greater, or at least, similar, in organic farming than in conventional farming, and also under irrigation than under rainfed conditions.

The survey results were presented to a wider audience of stakeholders in discussion groups in each case study area, where they engaged into a plenary discussion about them. Discussion groups confirmed the validity of the results from the survey, including the identification of the major agronomic problems and end-users' needs in each study area and the suitability of the preferred farming practices selected by survey respondents to cope with the major agro-environmental problems in each crop and case study area, although some drawbacks of the selected practices were identified in some case study areas. The participants in the discussion groups agreed with the identification of the main barriers for the adoption of more sustainable farming practices done through the survey but highlighted the identified need for more government support and more adequate legislation and also identified some additional issues of relevance for the adoption of crop diversification practices.

5 Annex 1: Survey results for each crop/area

A1. POTATO, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH (SPAIN)

Problems and objectives for action

The stakeholders interviewed in the Spanish Mediterranean potato case study do not perceive, on average, any agronomic **problems** as being of high or very high severity (Table 2). The most severe problems, perceived on average as of a medium-high severity, are the loss of soil organic matter, the low soil microbial biodiversity and soil compaction, closely followed by the low number of earthworms in the soil and the high weed pressure. On the other hand, the less severe problems for stakeholders are the low soil fertility, crop yields and the risk of development of resistance to phytosanitary products.

The priority given by stakeholders to different **objectives** for addressing the agronomic problems in the Spanish Mediterranean potato case study (Table 3) points at increasing soil organic matter content and improving soil structure to increase aeration, water retention and favour plant rooting as the most urgent need, followed by increasing soil fertility and increasing soil biodiversity. These results are qualitatively very similar to those in the Spanish Mediterranean wheat case study but the wheat stakeholders give a slightly greater importance to these objectives.

Identification of farming practices

Regarding **tillage practices**, results in Table A1.1 show that the respondents choose different tillage practices as the most adequate one depending on the end-users' need to be fulfilled (objectives). Minimum tillage is the tillage practice selected by more stakeholders as the most effective for most objectives, with the exception of shallow tillage that is chosen by more respondents as the most adequate option to mobilise soil nutrients and no tillage that is chosen as the best alternative to reduce soil erosion. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 4 and Table 24) confirm these findings, as respondents provide by far the highest ranking score to minimum tillage, followed by no tillage with mechanical weed control.

The interviewed stakeholders think that the implementation of more sustainable tillage practices in potato production in the area of study is mostly diffculted by the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness and, to a lesser extent, the lack of tradition (Table 5). On the other hand, most stakeholders do not perceive these tillage practices as difficult to implement with adequate technical advice and do not perceive that they are not profitable. Regarding the effectiveness of more sustainable tillage practices when integrated within different cropping systems, the majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that they are more effective under organic production or equally effective than under conventional farming (Table 6), more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 7) and more effective under irrigation (Table 8).

With respect to **fertilization practices**, the interviewed stakeholders choose different tillage practices as the most adequate one depending on the end-users' need to be fulfilled (objectives) (Table A1.2). The use of biostimulants, biofertilizers, mycorrhizas and new generation fertilisers is selected as the most effective fertilization practice to reduce the incidence of pest and diseases and to increase soil biodiversity, while the use of green manure is the most chosen alternative to mobilise soil nutrients and improve soil structure. The addition of solid organic matter is obviously the most chosen fertilization practice to increase soil organic matter content. Incorporating crop residues in the soil is the most chosen alternative to reduce soil erosion and to reduce soil pollution (together with the use of green manure and the use of biostimulants, biofertilizers, mycorrhizas and new generation fertilisers). None of the respondents consider that the addition of slurries is an adequate practice at all. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 9 and Table 24) confirm these findings as the respondents give the highest ranking score to the use of biostimulants, biofertilizers, mycorrhizas and new generation, followed by the use of green manure and the addition of soil organic matter/manures.

Turning to the barriers for the implementation of more sustainable fertilization practices in potato production, the interviewed stakeholders point at the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness and the lack of tradition, as the major difficulties, as well as the complexity of their implementation with adequate technical advice and their lower profitability (Table 10). Regarding the effectiveness of more sustainable fertilization practices when integrated within different cropping systems, the majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that that they are more or equally effective under organic production than under conventional farming (Table 11). A majority of respondents also think that they would be more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 12) and under irrigation (Table 13).

Regarding **soil conservation practices**, results in Table A1.3 show that the interviewed stakeholders think that crop diversification is the best soil conservation alternative for many of the objectives, such as increasing soil fertility and soil organic matter content and mobilising soil nutrients. On the other hand, crop diversification is chosen as the most adequate soil conservation practice to mobilise soil nutrients, reducing the incidence of pests and diseases, increasing soil biodiversity. Additionally, mulching is the second best alternative to increase soil fertility and soil organic matter content. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 14 and Table 24) confirm these findings as crop diversification, closely followed by the addition of organic matter, receives the highest ranking score as the preferred soil conservation practices.

Again, the interviewed stakeholders think that the implementation of more sustainable soil conservation practices in potato production in the area of study is diffculted by the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness, the lack of tradition and the complexity of their implementation with adequate technical advice (Table 15). In relation with the integration of more sustainable soil conservation practices within different cropping systems, the majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that they are more effective under organic farming (Table 16), when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 17) and under irrigation (Table 18).

Last, with respect to **pest and disease control practices**, results in Table A1.4 show that the vast majority of interviewed stakeholders think that crop diversification is the most effective alternative to reduce the incidence of pests and diseases for all objectives, with the exception of increasing soil invertebrates biodiversity that is the most chosen alternative to mobilise soil nutrients. Additionally, the use of biostimulants, mycorrhiza, etc. is the second most chosen

alternative to increase soil biodiversity and to improve soil structure. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 19 and Table 24) confirm these findings as respondents give the highest score ranking to crop diversification, almost tripling the ranking score given to the second higher score alternative which is increasing soil invertebrates biodiversity.

A majority of interviewed stakeholders think that the implementation of more innovative pest control practices in potato production in the area is difficulted by the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness, the need to have adequate technical advice due to their complexity and their higher costs (Table 20). A significant number of respondents also point at lack of enabling regulation/legislation. Regarding the integration of more sustainable pest control practices within different cropping systems, the majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that that they are more or equally effective under organic production than under conventional farming (Table 21). A majority of respondents also think that they would be more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 22) and under irrigation (Table 23).

Table A1.1. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective tillage practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for potato production in Mediterranean Spain (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Conventional tillage	Tillage according level curves	Shallow tillage	Minimum tillage (reduced tillage frequency)	No tillage with herbicides	No tillage without herbicides (mechanical weed control)	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	17	5.88%	11.76%	5.88%	47.06%	0.00%	11.76%	5.88%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	13	7.69%	0.00%	30.77%	23.08%	0.00%	7.69%	7.69%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	12	8.33%	0.00%	16.67%	16.67%	8.33%	8.33%	8.33%
Increase soil organic matter content	15	6.67%	0.00%	6.67%	33.33%	0.00%	26.67%	13.33%
Improve soil structure	14	7.14%	7.14%	14.29%	35.71%	0.00%	14.29%	7.14%
Increase soil biodiversity	12	8.33%	0.00%	8.33%	25.00%	8.33%	25.00%	8.33%
Reduce soil erosion	10	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil pollution	11	0.00%	0.00%	9.09%	27.27%	0.00%	18.18%	27.27%
Reduce soil salinization	12	0.00%	0.00%	16.67%	16.67%	0.00%	8.33%	25.00%
Reduce soil acidification								
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	12	0.00%	16.67%	8.33%	25.00%	0.00%	16.67%	8.33%
Improve water quality								
Reduce the incidence of weeds								
Increasing load carrying capacity								

Table A1.2. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective fertilization practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for potato production in Mediterranean Spain (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Incorporating crops residues into the soil	Addition of solid organic matter/manures	Use of green manure	Combination of manure and mineral fertilizers	Precision agriculture to optimise fertilization	Use of biostimulants, biofertilizers, etc.	Addition of slurries	Alelopathic crops / green manure, such as Brassicae	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	15	13.33%	20.00%	20.00%	26.67%	0.00%	13.33%	0.00%		0.00%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	11	0.00%	0.00%	36.36%	9.09%	9.09%	27.27%	0.00%		0.00%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	12	0.00%	0.00%	8.33%	0.00%	16.67%	41.67%	0.00%		16.67%
Increase soil organic matter content	14	7.14%	71.43%	0.00%	14.29%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%		0.00%
Improve soil structure	13	7.69%	15.38%	30.77%	7.69%	0.00%	15.38%	0.00%		7.69%
Increase soil biodiversity	12	0.00%	8.33%	8.33%	0.00%	0.00%	75.00%	0.00%		0.00%
Reduce soil erosion	10	30.00%	0.00%	10.00%	10.00%	10.00%	0.00%	0.00%		10.00%
Reduce soil pollution	11	18.18%	9.09%	18.18%	0.00%	9.09%	18.18%	0.00%		0.00%
Reduce soil salinization	12	8.33%	16.67%	8.33%	8.33%	16.67%	16.67%	0.00%		8.33%
Reduce soil acidification										
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	11	9.09%	9.09%	9.09%	0.00%	0.00%	18.18%	0.00%		27.27%
Improve water quality										
Reduce the incidence of weeds										
Increasing load carrying capacity										

Table A1.3. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective soil conservation practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for potato production in Mediterranean Spain (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Mulching (with crushed offcuts from pruning, etc.)	Maintain vegetation cover (natural or cover crops)	Maintain strips of vegetation between lines	Hedges or natural vegetation on the edges of the plots	Erosion barriers or margins with vegetation	Addition of organic matter	Crop diversification	Use of catch crops to reduce N/P leaching	Avoiding plant protection products	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	14	21.43%	7.14%	7.14%	0.00%	0.00%	42.86%	21.43%	0.00%		0.00%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	10	10.00%	0.00%	10.00%	0.00%	0.00%	30.00%	30.00%	10.00%		10.00%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	11	0.00%	9.09%	9.09%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	36.36%	0.00%		45.45%
Increase soil organic matter content	13	23.08%	7.69%	7.69%	0.00%	7.69%	38.46%	15.38%	0.00%		0.00%
Improve soil structure	12	16.67%	8.33%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	41.67%	33.33%	0.00%		0.00%
Increase soil biodiversity	11	9.09%	18.18%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	18.18%	54.55%	0.00%		0.00%
Reduce soil erosion	9	0.00%	11.11%	11.11%	0.00%	44.44%	0.00%	11.11%	11.11%		11.11%
Reduce soil pollution	10	0.00%	20.00%	10.00%	0.00%	10.00%	20.00%	20.00%	0.00%		20.00%
Reduce soil salinization	11	9.09%	9.09%	9.09%	9.09%	0.00%	9.09%	27.27%	9.09%		18.18%
Reduce soil acidification											
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	10	10.00%	10.00%	10.00%	0.00%	10.00%	10.00%	20.00%	10.00%		0.00%
Improve water quality											
Reduce the incidence of weeds											
Increasing load carrying capacity											

Table A1.4. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective pest and disease control practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for potato production in Mediterranean Spain (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Pests alerts	Crop diversification	Trap crops	Increase soil invertebrates biodiversity	Use of biostimulants and mycorrhiza, etc.	Use of pesticides	Ploughing	Alelopathic crops, such as Brassicae	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	14	14.29%	21.43%	7.14%	7.14%	21.43%	0.00%		0.00%	7.14%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	10	0.00%	30.00%	0.00%	40.00%	10.00%	0.00%		0.00%	0.00%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	11	9.09%	18.18%	9.09%	18.18%	9.09%	9.09%		0.00%	18.18%
Increase soil organic matter content	13	0.00%	38.46%	15.38%	0.00%	23.08%	7.69%		0.00%	7.69%
Improve soil structure	12	0.00%	58.33%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	8.33%		0.00%	8.33%
Increase soil biodiversity	11	0.00%	45.45%	0.00%	27.27%	9.09%	0.00%		0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil erosion	9	0.00%	22.22%	0.00%	11.11%	0.00%	0.00%		0.00%	11.11%
Reduce soil pollution	10	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	10.00%	10.00%	10.00%		0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil salinization	11	0.00%	36.36%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	9.09%		0.00%	18.18%
Reduce soil acidification										
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	10	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	10.00%		0.00%	20.00%
Improve water quality										
Reduce the incidence of weeds										
Increasing load carrying capacity										

A2. WHEAT, MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH (SPAIN)

Problems and objectives for action

The stakeholders interviewed in the Spanish Mediterranean wheat case study do not perceive, on average, any agronomic **problems** as being of high or very high severity (Table 2). The most severe problems, perceived on average as of a medium-high severity, are the loss of soil organic matter, soil compaction and rain fall scarcity, closely followed by soil erosion and crop yields. On the other hand, the less severe problems for stakeholders are the high use of phytosanitary products, the incidence of pest and diseases, water pollution and the number of earthworms in soil.

The priority given by stakeholders to different **objectives** for addressing the agronomic problems in the Spanish Mediterranean potato case study (Table 3) points at increasing soil organic matter content and improving soil structure to increase aeration, water retention and favour plant rooting as the most urgent needs, followed by increasing soil fertility and increasing soil biodiversity. These results are very similar to those in the Spanish Mediterranean potato case study but the potato stakeholders give a slightly lower importance to these objectives.

Identification of farming practices

Regarding **tillage practices**, results in Table A2.1 show that the respondents choose different tillage practices as the most adequate one depending on the end-users' need to be fulfilled (objectives). Minimum tillage is the tillage practice selected by more stakeholders as the most effective for most objectives, with the exception of tillage following contour lines that is chosen by more respondents as the most effective option to reduce soil erosion and improve water infiltration and no tillage without application of herbicides that is chosen as the best alternative to reduce soil pollution. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 4 and Table 24) confirm these findings, as respondents provide by far the highest ranking score to minimum tillage, followed by contour tillage.

The interviewed stakeholders think that the implementation of more sustainable tillage practices in potato production in the area of study is mostly diffculted by the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness and, to a lesser extent, the lack of tradition, the need for adequate technical advice and their lack of profitability (Table 5). Regarding the effectiveness of more sustainable tillage practices when integrated within different cropping systems, the majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that they are more effective under organic production or equally effective than under conventional farming (Table 6), more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 7) and more effective under irrigation (Table 8).

With respect to **fertilization practices**, the interviewed stakeholders choose different tillage practices as the most adequate one depending on the end-users' need to be fulfilled (objectives) (Table A2.2). The addition of solid organic matter/manure is the most chosen fertilization practice to increase soil organic matter content, soil fertility and biodiversity and to improve soil structure. Incorporating crop residues in the soil is the most chosen alternative to reduce soil

erosion and to reduce soil pollution (together with the use of precision agriculture to optimise fertilization). Precision agriculture techniques is the most chosen alternative to reduce soil salinization and pollution and mobilise soil nutrients. None of the respondents consider that the addition of slurries is an adequate practice at all. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 9 and Table 24) confirm these findings as the respondents give the highest ranking score to the addition of soil organic matter/manures and the incorporation of crop residues to the soil and to the use of precision agriculture techniques to optimise fertilization.

Turning to the barriers for the implementation of more sustainable fertilization practices in potato production, the interviewed stakeholders point at the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness, the lack of tradition and their higher costs, as the major difficulties, as well as the need for adequate technical advice and their lower profitability (Table 10). Regarding the effectiveness of more sustainable fertilization practices when integrated within different cropping systems, the majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that that they are equally effective under organic production than under conventional farming (Table 11). A majority of respondents also think that they would be more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 12) and equally effective under irrigation and under rainfed conditions (Table 13).

Regarding **soil conservation practices**, results in Table A2.3 show that the interviewed stakeholders think that the addition of organic matter and maintaining vegetation cover in the soil are the best soil conservation alternatives for many of the objectives, such as increasing soil fertility and soil organic matter content, reducing soil salinity and mobilising soil nutrients. Maintaining a vegetation cover is selected as the most effective alternative to reduce the incidence of pests and diseases (together with vegetated plot's margins), to increase soil biodiversity (together with crop diversification) and to reduce soil erosion (together with mulching). Additionally, mulching is chose as the best alternative to improve soil structure. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 14 and Table 24) confirm these findings as vegetation soil covers, followed by the addition of organic matter and mulching, receive the highest ranking score as the preferred soil conservation practice.

Again, the interviewed stakeholders think that the implementation of more sustainable soil conservation practices in potato production in the area of study is diffculted by the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness, the need for adequate technical advice and the lack of tradition (Table 15). In relation with the integration of more sustainable soil conservation practices within different cropping systems, the majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that they are equally effective under organic farming and under conventional farming (Table 16), more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 17) and equally effective under irrigation and under rainfed conditions (Table 18).

Last, with respect to **pest and disease control practices**, results in Table A2.4 show that the vast majority of interviewed stakeholders think that crop diversification is the most effective alternative to increase soil organic matter content and soil biodiversity, to improve soil structure and water infiltration and to reduce soil erosion and pollution. Increasing soil invertebrates biodiversity is the most chosen alternative to mobilise soil nutrients and to reduce the incidence of pests and diseases. Additionally, the use of biostimulants, mycorrhiza, etc. is the most chosen alternative to increase soil fertility and the second best option to increase soil organic matter content and to reduce soil erosion and pollution. The results from the multicriteria assessment

(Table 19 and Table 24) confirm these findings as respondents give the highest score ranking to crop diversification, followed by increasing soil invertebrates biodiversity.

A majority of interviewed stakeholders think that the implementation of more innovative pest control practices in potato production in the area is diffculted by the need to have adequate technical advice due to their complexity and the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness, followed by the lack of traditions and their higher costs (Table 20). Regarding the integration of more sustainable pest control practices within different cropping systems, the majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that that they are equally effective under organic production and under conventional farming (Table 21). A majority of respondents also think that they would be more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 22) and that they are equally effective under irrigation and under rainfed conditions (Table 23).

Table A2.1. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective tillage practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for wheat production in Mediterranean Spain (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Conventional tillage	Tillage according level curves	Shallow tillage	Minimum tillage (reduced tillage frequency)	No tillage with herbicides	No tillage without herbicides (mechanical weed control)	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	15	13.33%	13.33%	6.67%	46.67%	6.67%	0.00%	0.00%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	9	0.00%	11.11%	11.11%	44.44%	0.00%	0.00%	11.11%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	7	14.29%	14.29%	0.00%	28.57%	14.29%	14.29%	0.00%
Increase soil organic matter content	15	26.67%	6.67%	6.67%	46.67%	6.67%	6.67%	0.00%
Improve soil structure	13	7.69%	15.38%	7.69%	61.54%	7.69%	0.00%	0.00%
Increase soil biodiversity	13	0.00%	15.38%	7.69%	38.46%	15.38%	15.38%	7.69%
Reduce soil erosion	10	0.00%	40.00%	10.00%	20.00%	20.00%	10.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil pollution	11	0.00%	18.18%	0.00%	18.18%	9.09%	27.27%	0.00%
Reduce soil salinization	7	0.00%	14.29%	14.29%	28.57%	14.29%	14.29%	0.00%
Reduce soil acidification								
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	11	9.09%	45.45%	9.09%	9.09%	9.09%	18.18%	0.00%
Improve water quality								
Reduce the incidence of weeds								
Increasing load carrying capacity								

Table A2.2. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective fertilization practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for wheat production in Mediterranean Spain (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Incorporating crops residues into the soil	Addition of solid organic matter/manures	Use of green manure	Combination of manure and mineral fertilizers	Precision agriculture to optimise fertilization	Use of biostimulants, biofertilizers, etc.	Addition of slurries	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	15	13.33%	53.33%	6.67%	6.67%	13.33%	6.67%	0.00%	0.00%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	9	22.22%	22.22%	0.00%	0.00%	33.33%	22.22%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	7	14.29%	0.00%	0.00%	28.57%	14.29%	14.29%	0.00%	0.00%
Increase soil organic matter content	15	13.33%	60.00%	6.67%	6.67%	0.00%	13.33%	0.00%	0.00%
Improve soil structure	13	15.38%	46.15%	7.69%	7.69%	15.38%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Increase soil biodiversity	13	7.69%	30.77%	23.08%	15.38%	0.00%	15.38%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil erosion	10	50.00%	10.00%	20.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil pollution	11	36.36%	0.00%	9.09%	9.09%	36.36%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil salinization	7	14.29%	28.57%	0.00%	0.00%	42.86%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil acidification									
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	11	9.09%	18.18%	18.18%	18.18%	18.18%	0.00%	0.00%	9.09%
Improve water quality									
Reduce the incidence of weeds									
Increasing load carrying capacity									

Table A2.3. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective soil conservation practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for wheat production in Mediterranean Spain (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Mulching (with crushed offcuts from pruning, etc.)	Maintain vegetation cover (natural or cover crops)	Maintain strips of vegetation between lines	Hedges or natural vegetation on the edges of the plots	Erosion barriers or margins with vegetation	Addition of organic matter	Crop diversification	Use of catch crops to reduce N/P leaching	Avoiding plant protection products	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	15	20.00%	20.00%	0.00%	6.67%	6.67%	33.33%	13.33%		0.00%	0.00%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	9	0.00%	33.33%	11.11%	0.00%	0.00%	33.33%	22.22%		0.00%	0.00%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	7	0.00%	28.57%	14.29%	0.00%	28.57%	0.00%	14.29%		0.00%	0.00%
Increase soil organic matter content	15	13.33%	33.33%	13.33%	0.00%	0.00%	33.33%	6.67%		0.00%	0.00%
Improve soil structure	13	38.46%	7.69%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	30.77%	23.08%		0.00%	0.00%
Increase soil biodiversity	13	23.08%	23.08%	7.69%	0.00%	15.38%	0.00%	23.08%		7.69%	0.00%
Reduce soil erosion	10	30.00%	40.00%	0.00%	10.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%		0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil pollution	11	18.18%	27.27%	0.00%	9.09%	0.00%	0.00%	27.27%		0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil salinization	7	14.29%	14.29%	0.00%	14.29%	14.29%	28.57%	0.00%		0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil acidification											
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	11	18.18%	18.18%	0.00%	9.09%	9.09%	27.27%	9.09%		0.00%	0.00%
Improve water quality											
Reduce the incidence of weeds											
Increasing load carrying capacity											

Table A2.4. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective pest and disease control practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for wheat production in Mediterranean Spain (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Pests alerts	Crop diversification	Trap crops	Increase soil invertebrates biodiversity	Use of biostimulants and mycorrhiza, etc.	Use of pesticides	Ploughing	Alelopathic crops. such as Brassicae	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	15	20.00%	20.00%	13.33%	6.67%	33.33%	0.00%		6.67%	0.00%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	9	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	55.56%	11.11%	0.00%		0.00%	0.00%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	7	14.29%	14.29%	14.29%	42.86%	0.00%	0.00%		0.00%	0.00%
Increase soil organic matter content	15	0.00%	53.33%	0.00%	20.00%	20.00%	0.00%		0.00%	0.00%
Improve soil structure	13	0.00%	53.85%	7.69%	15.38%	15.38%	0.00%		0.00%	0.00%
Increase soil biodiversity	13	7.69%	53.85%	7.69%	23.08%	7.69%	0.00%		0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil erosion	10	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	10.00%	20.00%	0.00%		0.00%	20.00%
Reduce soil pollution	11	9.09%	36.36%	0.00%	18.18%	18.18%	0.00%		0.00%	9.09%
Reduce soil salinization	7	0.00%	14.29%	14.29%	14.29%	0.00%	0.00%		14.29%	28.57%
Reduce soil acidification										
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	11	0.00%	36.36%	0.00%	27.27%	9.09%	0.00%		0.00%	18.18%
Improve water quality										
Reduce the incidence of weeds										
Increasing load carrying capacity										

A3. POTATO, LUSITANEAN (SPAIN)

Problems and objectives for action

The stakeholders interviewed in the Spanish Lusitanian potato case study do not perceive, on average, any agronomic **problems** as being of high or very high severity (Table 2). The most severe problems, perceived on average as of a medium-high severity, are the high incidence of pests and fungal diseases and soil waterlogging, closely followed by the high use of plant protection products and the low and/or variable yields. On the other hand, the less severe problems for stakeholders are soil erosion, the loss of organic matter, soil acidification and the low number of earthworm in the soil.

The priority given by stakeholders to different **objectives** for addressing the agronomic problems in the Spanish Lusitanian potato case study (Table 3) points at reducing the incidence of pests and diseases as the most urgent need, followed by mobilizing soil nutrients during the plant growth stage, increasing soil fertility, improving soil structure to increase aeration, water retention and favour plant rooting and increasing soil biodiversity. These results are qualitatively very similar to those in the Spanish Lusitanian wheat case study but the potato stakeholders give a greater importance to reducing the incidence of pests and diseases than wheat stakeholders do.

Identification of farming practices

Regarding **tillage practices**, results in Table A3.1 show that the respondents choose different tillage practices as the most adequate one depending on the end-users' need to be fulfilled (objectives). Conventional intensive tillage is the tillage practice selected by more stakeholders as the most effective for most objectives. However, the percentage of respondents that think that none of tillage practices are effective are relatively high for many objectives, such as reducing the incidence of pests and diseases, increasing soil organic matter and reducing soil erosion, pollution, salinization and acidification. Alternatively, shallow tillage and minimum tillage are frequently pointed out by many stakeholders as adequate practices to increase soil organic matter and reduce soil erosion. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 4 and Table 24) confirm these findings, as respondents provide the highest ranking score to conventional tillage. The option of tillage not being really effective to address the agronomic problems of potato crop in the area receives the second highest ranking score, followed by shallow tillage and, to a lesser extent, minimum tillage.

The interviewed stakeholders think that the implementation of more sustainable tillage practices in potato production in the area of study is diffculted by the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness, the lack of tradition and their complexity if technical advice is not available (Table 5). On the other hand, stakeholders do not perceive these tillage practices as difficult to implement with adequate technical advice and do not perceive that they are not profitable. Regarding the effectiveness of more sustainable tillage practices when integrated within different cropping systems, the majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that they are not compatible with organic production (Table 6), but more effective when integrated within

a diversified cropping system (Table 7) and similarly, or even more, effective under irrigation than under rainfed conditions (Table 8).

With respect to **fertilization practices**, the interviewed stakeholders are sceptic about the potential of fertilization practices to address most of the problems in potato production in the area (Table A3.2), such as reducing the incidence of pests and diseases, reducing soil erosion, salinization and acidification, improving water infiltration and water quality and reducing the incidence of weeds. The addition of solid organic matter is the most chosen fertilization practice to increase soil organic matter content, mobilise soil nutrients and improve soil structure. Incorporating crop residues in the soil are the most chosen one to increase soil fertility, closely followed by the addition of soil organic matter. Precision agriculture is the most selected fertilization practice to reduce soil pollution and to improve soil water quality and soil infiltration. The use of biostimulants, biofertilizers, mycorrhizas and new generation fertilisers was selected as the second most effective fertilization practice to mobilise soil nutrients and to increase soil biodiversity. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 9 and Table 24) confirm these findings as the respondents give the highest ranking score to the option of the little effectiveness of fertilization to face agronomic problems in the area, followed by the addition of soil organic matter/manures and the use of precision agriculture techniques.

Turning to the barriers for the implementation of more sustainable fertilization practices in potato production, the interviewed stakeholders point at the complexity of their implementation with adequate technical advice and the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness as the major difficulties, as well as the lack of tradition (Table 10). Regarding the effectiveness of more sustainable fertilization practices when integrated within different cropping systems, the majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that that they are not compatible with organic production (Table 11). They also think that they would be more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 12) and that their effectiveness is similar, or even greater, under irrigation than under rainfed conditions (Table 13).

Regarding **soil conservation practices**, results in Table A3.3 show that the interviewed stakeholders think that crop diversification is the best alternative for soil conservation for many of the objectives, followed by the addition of organic matter and, for some objectives, of the use of catch crops. The addition of organic matter is perceived as the most effective alternative to increase soil organic matter content and soil fertility. Avoiding the use of plant protection products is selected as one of the most effective practices to reduce soil pollution and water pollution. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 14 and Table 24) confirm these findings as crop diversification receives a ranking score that doubles that of the following highest ranked practice, which is the addition of organic matter that was also selected as one of the preferred fertilization practices.

Again, the interviewed stakeholders think that the implementation of more sustainable soil conservation practices in potato production in the area of study is diffculted by the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness, the complexity of their implementation with adequate technical advice and the lack of tradition (Table 15). In relation with the integration of more sustainable soil conservation practices within different cropping systems, the interviewed stakeholders are divided between those that think that they are equally effective under organic than under conventional farming and those that think that they are not compatible of organic production (Table 16). Again, a majority of respondents perceived them as more effective when

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integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 17). Respondents think that their effectiveness is similar, or even greater, under irrigation than under rainfed conditions (Table 18).

Table A3.1. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective tillage practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for potato production in Lusitanian Spain (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Conventional tillage	Tillage according level curves	Shallow tillage	Minimum tillage (reduced tillage frequency)	No tillage with herbicides	No tillage without herbicides (mechanical weed control)	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	20	80.00%	5.00%	5.00%	0.00%	0.00%	5.00%	5.00%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	14	50.00%	0.00%	14.29%	14.29%	0.00%	0.00%	21.43%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	25	28.00%	0.00%	12.00%	12.00%	8.00%	0.00%	40.00%
Increase soil organic matter content	15	33.33%	0.00%	26.67%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	33.33%
Improve soil structure	16	50.00%	0.00%	12.50%	12.50%	0.00%	0.00%	25.00%
Increase soil biodiversity	14	28.57%	0.00%	14.29%	14.29%	0.00%	14.29%	21.43%
Reduce soil erosion	9	11.11%	0.00%	33.33%	11.11%	0.00%	0.00%	44.44%
Reduce soil pollution	15	26.67%	0.00%	13.33%	20.00%	0.00%	13.33%	26.67%
Reduce soil salinization	6	16.67%	0.00%	16.67%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	33.33%
Reduce soil acidification	7	28.57%	0.00%	14.29%	14.29%	0.00%	0.00%	28.57%
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	13	38.46%	0.00%	15.38%	23.08%	0.00%	0.00%	7.69%
Improve water quality	11	18.18%	0.00%	18.18%	9.09%	9.09%	18.18%	18.18%
Reduce the incidence of weeds	12	33.33%	0.00%	8.33%	8.33%	16.67%	0.00%	8.33%
Increasing load carrying capacity								

Last, with respect to **pest and disease control practices**, results in Table A3.4 show that the vast majority of interviewed stakeholders think that the use of pesticides is the most effective alternative to reduce the incidence of pests and diseases and that crop diversification is the most effective one for the other objectives, together with ploughing to reduce soil erosion and to control weeds. Other frequently selected alternatives are: the use of biostimulants, mycorrhiza, etc. to mobilise soil nutrients; increasing invertebrates biodiversity to improve soil structure, water infiltration and soil biodiversity; and the use of pest alerts to reduce the incidence of pests and diseases, increase soil biodiversity and reduce soil pollution. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 19 and Table 24) confirm these findings as respondents give the highest possible score ranking to crop diversification, more than doubling the ranking score given to the use of pesticides.

A majority of interviewed stakeholders think that the implementation of more innovative pest control practices in potato production in the area is diffculted by the need to have adequate technical advice due to their complexity (Table 20). A significant number of respondents also point at the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness and the lack of tradition in the area. Regarding the integration of more sustainable pest control practices within different cropping systems, a majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that they are not compatible with organic farming (Table 21) and that their effectiveness is similar under both rainfed and irrigated conditions or even greater under irrigation (Table 23). Last, they think that they would be more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 22).

Table A3.2. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective fertilization practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for potato production in Lusitanian Spain (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Incorporating crops residues into the soil	Addition of solid organic matter/manures	Use of green manure	Combination of manure and mineral fertilizers	Precision agriculture to optimise fertilization	Use of biostimulants, biofertilizers, etc.	Addition of slurries	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	20	35.00%	30.00%	5.00%	20.00%	5.00%	5.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	14	7.14%	28.57%	0.00%	21.43%	14.29%	21.43%	0.00%	7.14%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	25	0.00%	4.00%	4.00%	8.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	64.00%
Increase soil organic matter content	15	6.67%	53.33%	0.00%	13.33%	13.33%	0.00%	0.00%	6.67%
Improve soil structure	16	0.00%	31.25%	0.00%	12.50%	18.75%	6.25%	0.00%	25.00%
Increase soil biodiversity	14	7.14%	7.14%	7.14%	0.00%	21.43%	21.43%	0.00%	35.71%
Reduce soil erosion	9	11.11%	11.11%	0.00%	11.11%	11.11%	0.00%	0.00%	44.44%
Reduce soil pollution	15	0.00%	13.33%	13.33%	0.00%	26.67%	6.67%	0.00%	26.67%
Reduce soil salinization	6	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	16.67%	0.00%	66.67%
Reduce soil acidification	7	0.00%	14.29%	0.00%	0.00%	14.29%	14.29%	0.00%	57.14%
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	13	0.00%	23.08%	0.00%	7.69%	30.77%	0.00%	0.00%	38.46%
Improve water quality	11	0.00%	9.09%	0.00%	0.00%	36.36%	9.09%	0.00%	45.45%
Reduce the incidence of weeds	12	8.33%	8.33%	0.00%	8.33%	16.67%	8.33%	0.00%	41.67%
Increasing load carrying capacity									

Table A3.3. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective soil conservation practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for potato production in Lusitanian Spain (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Mulching (with crushed offcuts from pruning, etc.)	Maintain vegetation cover (natural or cover crops)	Maintain strips of vegetation between lines	Hedges or natural vegetation on the edges of the plots	Erosion barriers or margins with vegetation	Addition of organic matter	Crop diversification	Use of catch crops to reduce N/P leaching	Avoiding plant protection products	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	20	0.00%	5.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	30.00%	0.00%	0.00%	15.00%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	14	0.00%	21.43%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	35.71%	0.00%	0.00%	14.29%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	25	0.00%	8.00%	4.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%	4.00%	44.00%
Increase soil organic matter content	15	6.67%	6.67%	6.67%	0.00%	0.00%	46.67%	6.67%	0.00%	0.00%	6.67%
Improve soil structure	16	0.00%	6.25%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	6.25%	37.50%	0.00%	6.25%	25.00%
Increase soil biodiversity	14	7.14%	7.14%	0.00%	7.14%	0.00%	0.00%	35.71%	0.00%	14.29%	14.29%
Reduce soil erosion	9	11.11%	11.11%	0.00%	0.00%	11.11%	11.11%	11.11%	0.00%	0.00%	33.33%
Reduce soil pollution	15	0.00%	13.33%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	33.33%	6.67%	26.67%	13.33%
Reduce soil salinization	6	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	16.67%	16.67%	0.00%	16.67%
Reduce soil acidification	7	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	42.86%	14.29%	0.00%	28.57%
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	13	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	38.46%	15.38%	7.69%	23.08%
Improve water quality	11	9.09%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	27.27%	18.18%	27.27%	18.18%
Reduce the incidence of weeds	12	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	8.33%	33.33%	8.33%	0.00%	25.00%
Increasing load carrying capacity											

Table A3.4. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective pest and disease control practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for potato production in Lusitanian Spain (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Pests alerts	Crop diversification	Trap crops	Increase soil invertebrates biodiversity	Use of biostimulants and mycorrhiza, etc.	Use of pesticides	Ploughing	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	20	0.00%	70.00%	0.00%	0.00%	5.00%	10.00%	10.00%	5.00%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	14	0.00%	35.71%	0.00%	0.00%	28.57%	0.00%	14.29%	21.43%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	25	16.00%	24.00%	0.00%	0.00%	4.00%	56.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Increase soil organic matter content	15	0.00%	33.33%	6.67%	13.33%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	46.67%
Improve soil structure	16	0.00%	37.50%	0.00%	12.50%	6.25%	0.00%	12.50%	31.25%
Increase soil biodiversity	14	14.29%	35.71%	0.00%	28.57%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	7.14%
Reduce soil erosion	9	0.00%	22.22%	0.00%	0.00%	11.11%	0.00%	22.22%	11.11%
Reduce soil pollution	15	13.33%	26.67%	6.67%	6.67%	6.67%	6.67%	0.00%	26.67%
Reduce soil salinization	6	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	16.67%
Reduce soil acidification	7	0.00%	28.57%	0.00%	0.00%	14.29%	0.00%	0.00%	28.57%
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	13	0.00%	30.77%	0.00%	15.38%	0.00%	7.69%	7.69%	23.08%
Improve water quality	11	0.00%	45.45%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	54.55%
Reduce the incidence of weeds	12	8.33%	25.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	8.33%	25.00%	8.33%
Increasing load carrying capacity									

A4. WHEAT, LUSITANEAN (SPAIN)

Problems and objectives for action

The stakeholders interviewed in the Spanish Lusitanian wheat case study do not perceive, on average, any agronomic **problems** as being of high or very high severity (Table 2). The most severe problems, perceived on average as of a medium-high severity, are the low and/or variable yields and soil waterlogging. There is also some concern with the low soil fertility, the high incidence of pests, fungal diseases and weeds and the excess of rainfall. On the other hand, the less severe problems for stakeholders are soil erosion, irrigation water scarcity and high incidence of bacterial diseases. However, the differences in the qualitative assessment of the severity of each problem are not very large.

The priority given by stakeholders to different **objectives** for addressing the agronomic problems in the Spanish Lusitanian wheat case study (Table 3) points at increasing soil fertility and mobilizing soil nutrients during plant growth stage as the most urgent need, followed by reducing the incidence of pests and diseases, improving soil structure to increase aeration, water retention and favour plant rooting and increasing soil biodiversity. These results are qualitatively very similar to those in the Spanish Lusitanian potato case study but the potato stakeholders give a greater importance to reducing the incidence of pests and diseases than wheat stakeholders do.

Identification of farming practices

Regarding **tillage practices**, results in Table A4.1 show that the respondents choose different tillage practices as the most adequate one depending on the end-users' need to be fulfilled (objectives). There is not a clear consensus about the most effective tillage practices. The percentage of respondents that think that none of the tillage practices are effective are relatively high for many objectives, such as reducing the incidence of pests and diseases, reducing soil erosion, pollution, salinization and acidification and improving water infiltration and water quality. Conventional intensive tillage is the tillage practice selected by more stakeholders as the most effective to increase soil fertility and improve soil structure. Alternatively, shallow tillage is the most selected tillage practice to mobilise soil nutrients and to reduce soil salinization, while minimum tillage is the most selected tillage practice to increase soil organic content and reduce soil erosion and soil acidification. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 4 and Table 24) confirm these findings, as respondents provided the highest ranking score to conventional tillage. The option of tillage not being effective to address the agronomic problems in the area receives the highest second ranking score, followed by shallow tillage and minimum tillage.

As in the potato Spanish Lusitanian case study, the interviewed stakeholders think that the implementation of more sustainable tillage practices in potato production in the area of study is diffculted by the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness, the lack of tradition and their complexity if technical advice is not available (Table 5). On the other hand, stakeholders do not perceive these tillage practices as difficult to implement with adequate technical advice and do not perceive that they are not profitable. Regarding the effectiveness of more sustainable

tillage practices when integrated within different cropping systems, the majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that they are not compatible with organic production (Table 6), but more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 7) and similarly, or even more, effective under rainfed conditions than under irrigation (Table 8).

With respect to **fertilization practices**, there is little consensus about the most effective ones to address most of the problems in potato production in the area (Table A4.2). For many objectives, stakeholders have selected different fertilization alternatives. The interviewed stakeholders are sceptic about the potential of fertilization practices to reduce the incidence of pests and diseases, improving water infiltration and water quality and reducing the incidence of weeds. The addition of solid organic matter is the most chosen fertilization practice to increase soil organic matter content and improve soil structure. On the other hand, the use of green manure is the most selected practice to increase soil biodiversity, improve water quality and reduce soil erosion, pollution and salinization. For other objectives, such as increasing soil fertility, mobilising soil nutrients and reducing soil acidification, stakeholders chose several fertilization practices in similar proportions. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 9 and Table 24) confirm these findings, as the respondents give the second highest ranking score to the option of the little effectiveness of fertilization to face agronomic problems in the area, corresponding the highest ranking score to the addition of soil organic matter/manures and the third one to the use of green manure.

Turning to the barriers for the implementation of more sustainable fertilization practices in wheat production, the interviewed stakeholders point at the complexity of their implementation with adequate technical advice and the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness as the major difficulties, as well as the lack of tradition (Table 10). Regarding the effectiveness of more sustainable fertilization practices when integrated within different cropping systems, the majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that that they are not compatible with organic production (Table 11). They also think that they would be more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 12) and that their effectiveness is similar, or even greater, under rainfed conditions than under irrigation (Table 13).

Table A4.1. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective tillage practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for wheat production in Lusitanian Spain (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Conventional tillage	Tillage according level curves	Shallow tillage	Minimum tillage (reduced tillage frequency)	No tillage with herbicides	No tillage without herbicides (mechanical weed control)	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	21	66.67%	4.76%	9.52%	14.29%	0.00%	0.00%	4.76%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	18	27.78%	0.00%	38.89%	5.56%	5.56%	0.00%	16.67%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	15	20.00%	0.00%	6.67%	6.67%	13.33%	6.67%	40.00%
Increase soil organic matter content	11	9.09%	0.00%	9.09%	27.27%	9.09%	0.00%	18.18%
Improve soil structure	16	31.25%	6.25%	18.75%	12.50%	0.00%	6.25%	18.75%
Increase soil biodiversity	13	30.77%	0.00%	23.08%	15.38%	7.69%	7.69%	0.00%
Reduce soil erosion	8	12.50%	12.50%	12.50%	25.00%	0.00%	12.50%	25.00%
Reduce soil pollution	10	30.00%	0.00%	10.00%	10.00%	10.00%	10.00%	30.00%
Reduce soil salinization	8	12.50%	0.00%	25.00%	12.50%	0.00%	12.50%	25.00%
Reduce soil acidification	11	9.09%	0.00%	18.18%	27.27%	0.00%	0.00%	45.45%
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	13	23.08%	0.00%	15.38%	15.38%	0.00%	15.38%	30.77%
Improve water quality	14	21.43%	0.00%	7.14%	7.14%	7.14%	7.14%	35.71%
Reduce the incidence of weeds	13	15.38%	0.00%	23.08%	7.69%	7.69%	15.38%	23.08%
Increasing load carrying capacity								

Regarding **soil conservation practices**, results in Table A4.3 show that the interviewed stakeholders think that crop diversification is the best alternative for soil conservation for many of the objectives, followed by the addition of organic matter and, for some objectives, by the use of catch crops. The addition of organic matter is perceived as the most effective alternative to increase soil organic matter content and soil fertility. Avoiding the use of plant protection products is selected as one of the most effective practices to reduce soil pollution and water pollution. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 14 and Table 24) confirm these findings as crop diversification receives a ranking score that doubles that of the following highest ranked practice, which is the addition of organic matter, which was also selected as one of the preferred fertilization practices.

Again, the interviewed stakeholders think that the implementation of more sustainable soil conservation practices in wheat production in the area of study is diffculted by the complexity of their implementation with adequate technical advice, the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness and the lack of tradition (Table 15). In relation with the integration of more sustainable soil conservation practices within different cropping systems, the interviewed stakeholders are divided between those that think that they are not compatible of organic production and those that think the opposite (Table 16). Again, a majority of respondents perceived them as more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 17). Respondents think that their effectiveness is similar, or even greater, under rainfed conditions than under irrigation (Table 18).

Last, with respect to **pest and disease control practices**, results in Table A4.4 show that the vast majority of interviewed stakeholders think that the use of pesticides is the most effective alternative to reduce the incidence of pests and diseases and that crop diversification is the most effective one for the other objectives, together with the use of biostimulants, mycorrhiza, etc. to mobilise soil nutrients and improve soil structure. Other frequently selected alternatives are: increasing invertebrates biodiversity to increase soil fertility and soil structure; using pest alerts and trap crops to reduce soil pollution; and ploughing to reduce soil erosion, improve water infiltration, mobilise soil nutrients and control weeds. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 19 and Table 24) confirm these findings as respondents have given the highest possible score ranking to crop diversification, nearly quadrupling the ranking score given to the use of pesticides that is the second highest scored alternative.

The vast majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that the implementation of more innovative pest control practices in potato production in the area is diffculted by the need to have adequate technical advice due to their complexity (Table 20). A significant number of respondents also point at the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness and the lack of tradition in the area. Regarding the integration of more sustainable pest control practices within different cropping systems, a majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that they are not compatible with organic farming (Table 21) and that their effectiveness is similar under both rainfed and irrigated conditions or even greater under rainfed production (Table 23). Last, they think that they would be more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 22).

Table A4.2. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective fertilization practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for wheat production in Lusitanian Spain (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Incorporating crops residues into the soil	Addition of solid organic matter/manures	Use of green manure	Combination of manure and mineral fertilizers	Precision agriculture to optimise fertilization	Use of biostimulants, biofertilizers, etc.	Addition of slurries	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	20	25.00%	30.00%	0.00%	30.00%	5.00%	5.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	17	0.00%	17.65%	11.76%	11.76%	11.76%	17.65%	0.00%	17.65%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	15	0.00%	6.67%	13.33%	6.67%	13.33%	6.67%	0.00%	33.33%
Increase soil organic matter content	11	0.00%	45.45%	9.09%	9.09%	0.00%	0.00%	9.09%	18.18%
Improve soil structure	15	0.00%	40.00%	20.00%	6.67%	0.00%	6.67%	0.00%	13.33%
Increase soil biodiversity	12	0.00%	8.33%	25.00%	8.33%	8.33%	16.67%	0.00%	25.00%
Reduce soil erosion	7	14.29%	14.29%	28.57%	14.29%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	28.57%
Reduce soil pollution	10	0.00%	20.00%	30.00%	10.00%	10.00%	10.00%	0.00%	10.00%
Reduce soil salinization	7	0.00%	14.29%	28.57%	14.29%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	14.29%
Reduce soil acidification	10	0.00%	10.00%	20.00%	20.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	12	0.00%	25.00%	16.67%	8.33%	8.33%	0.00%	0.00%	41.67%
Improve water quality	13	0.00%	15.38%	23.08%	7.69%	7.69%	0.00%	0.00%	30.77%
Reduce the incidence of weeds	12	8.33%	8.33%	8.33%	8.33%	25.00%	0.00%	0.00%	33.33%
Increasing load carrying capacity									

Table A4.3. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective soil conservation practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for wheat production in Lusitanian Spain (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Mulching (with crushed offcuts from pruning, etc.)	Maintain vegetation cover (natural or cover crops)	Maintain strips of vegetation between lines	Hedges or natural vegetation on the edges of the plots	Erosion barriers or margins with vegetation	Addition of organic matter	Crop diversification	Use of catch crops to reduce N/P leaching	Avoiding plant protection products	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	20	10.00%	5.00%	0.00%	5.00%	0.00%	55.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	14	0.00%	11.76%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	11.76%	35.29%	5.88%	0.00%	29.41%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	25	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	53.33%	0.00%	0.00%	26.67%
Increase soil organic matter content	15	0.00%	9.09%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	18.18%	18.18%	0.00%	0.00%	36.36%
Improve soil structure	16	13.33%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	13.33%	26.67%	6.67%	0.00%	26.67%
Increase soil biodiversity	14	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	58.33%	0.00%	0.00%	25.00%
Reduce soil erosion	9	0.00%	28.57%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	28.57%	14.29%	0.00%	28.57%
Reduce soil pollution	15	0.00%	10.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil salinization	6	0.00%	14.29%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	28.57%	14.29%	0.00%	28.57%
Reduce soil acidification	7	0.00%	10.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	20.00%	10.00%	0.00%	20.00%
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	13	8.33%	25.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	8.33%	16.67%	16.67%	0.00%	25.00%
Improve water quality	11	0.00%	7.69%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	30.77%	15.38%	15.38%	7.69%
Reduce the incidence of weeds	12	8.33%	16.67%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	41.67%	0.00%	0.00%	25.00%
Increasing load carrying capacity											

Table A4.4. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective pest and disease control practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for wheat production in Lusitanian Spain (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Pests alerts	Crop diversification	Trap crops	Increase soil invertebrates biodiversity	Use of biostimulants and mycorrhiza, etc.	Use of pesticides	Ploughing	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	20	0.00%	60.00%	0.00%	15.00%	10.00%	0.00%	5.00%	10.00%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	17	0.00%	35.29%	0.00%	11.76%	23.53%	0.00%	17.65%	11.76%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	15	13.33%	33.33%	13.33%	0.00%	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Increase soil organic matter content	11	0.00%	54.55%	0.00%	9.09%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	27.27%
Improve soil structure	15	6.67%	26.67%	0.00%	13.33%	13.33%	0.00%	13.33%	13.33%
Increase soil biodiversity	12	8.33%	41.67%	0.00%	8.33%	8.33%	8.33%	0.00%	8.33%
Reduce soil erosion	7	0.00%	57.14%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	14.29%	14.29%
Reduce soil pollution	10	10.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	10.00%	0.00%	0.00%	20.00%
Reduce soil salinization	7	0.00%	57.14%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	14.29%
Reduce soil acidification	10	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	30.00%
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	12	8.33%	41.67%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	16.67%	16.67%
Improve water quality	13	7.69%	30.77%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	38.46%
Reduce the incidence of weeds	12	8.33%	41.67%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	8.33%	16.67%	8.33%
Increasing load carrying capacity									

A5. POTATO, ATLANTIC CENTRAL (BELGIUM)

Problems and objectives for action

The stakeholders interviewed in the Belgian Atlantic central potato case study do not identify any agronomic **problems** as being of high or very high severity (Table 2). The most severe problems, perceived, on average, as of a medium-high severity, are the rainfall scarcity in growing period, the high incidence of fungal diseases and the high use of phytosanitary products, followed by the irrigation water scarcity and the high incidence of pests. On the other hand, the less severe problems for stakeholders are soil fertility, soil waterlogging, soil acidification, low presence of insects in the soil and soil microbial diversity.

The urgency pointed out by the Flemish potato stakeholders to different **objectives** for addressing the agronomic problems in the Belgian Atlantic central potato case study (Table 3) remarks increasing soil organic matter content as the most important one, followed by improving soil structure to improve aeration, water retention and rooting, increasing soil fertility, reducing the incidence of pests and diseases and increasing soil biodiversity. These results are qualitatively very similar to those in the Belgian wheat case study but not to the Belgian vegetables case study where stakeholders give a greater importance to increasing soil fertility than wheat and potato stakeholders do.

Identification of farming practices

Concerning **tillage practices**, values in Table A5.1 show that the surveyed choose different tillage practices as the most adequate one depending on the end-users' need to be fulfilled (objectives). Minimum tillage is the tillage practice selected by more stakeholders as the most effective for the majority of the objectives, such as improving soil structure and water quality and increasing soil organic matter content and fertility. However, the percentage of respondents that think that conventional tillage practices are effective are moderately high for some objectives, such as mobilizing soil nutrients during plant growth and reducing the incidence of pests and diseases. Nevertheless, there are relatively high percentage that believe that none of these practices are effective to achieve this last objective. Additionally, tillage according level curves is pointed out as the most adequate practice to reduce soil erosion, while no tillage without herbicides is selected by a majority of respondents as the most effective alternative to reduce soil pollution. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 4 and Table 24) confirm these findings, as respondents provide the highest ranking score to minimum tillage. The option of tillage not being really effective to address the agronomic problems of potato crop in the area receives the highest second ranking score, followed by conventional tillage.

The interviewed stakeholders consider that the implementation of more sustainable tillage practices in potato production in the area of study is difficulted by the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness, the lack of tradition, incompatibilities with the existing machinery and the need for technical advice (Table 5). On the other hand, stakeholders do not perceive these tillage practices as difficult to implement with adequate technical advice and do not perceive that they are not profitable. Regarding the effectiveness of more sustainable tillage practices when integrated within different cropping systems, the majority of the interviewed

stakeholders think that they are equally effective under organic and conventional farming (Table 6), but more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 7) and equally or more effective under irrigation than under rainfed conditions (Table 8).

With respect to **fertilization practices**, the surveyed stakeholders think that the addition of solid organic matter/manures is the most effective alternative to satisfy many of the identified end users' needs in potato production in the area (Table A5.2), such as increasing soil organic matter content, soil biodiversity and soil fertility, mobilizing soil nutrients during plant growth and reducing soil pollution. The use of green manure is the best option selected to reduce soil erosion, soil pollution and to improve soil structure and water quality and the second best fertilization practice to increase soil biodiversity. Additionally, the use of biostimulants, biofertilizers, mycorrhizas and new generation fertilisers is the second more selected practice in order to mobilise soil nutrients. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 9 and Table 24) confirm these findings as the respondents give the highest ranking score to the option of the addition of soil organic matter/manures followed by the use of green manure.

Turning to the barriers for the implementation of more sustainable fertilization practices in potato production, the interviewed stakeholders point at the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness as the most important obstacle, followed by the lack of tradition in the area and the lack of enabling regulation (Table 10). Regarding the effectiveness of more sustainable fertilization practices when integrated within different cropping systems, the majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that that they are equally effective under organic and conventional farming (Table 11). Most of the respondents think that they would be more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 12) and that their effectiveness is similar, or even greater, under irrigation than under rainfed conditions (Table 13).

Relating to **soil conservation practices**, results in Table A5.3 show that the interviewed stakeholders think that use of catch crops to reduce N/P leaching is the most effective alternative for soil conservation for many of the objectives, together with mulching (with crushed offcuts from pruning, etc.) and, to a lesser extent, maintaining vegetation covers (natural or cover crops). The use of catch crops to reduce N/P leaching is pointed out as the most effective alternative to increase soil organic matter content and soil biodiversity and, together with mulching, to increase soil fertility and to improve soil structure. Installing hedges on the edges of the plots is selected as one of the most effective practice to reduce soil erosion and to reduce the incidence of pests and diseases. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 14 and Table 24) confirm these findings, as catch crops receive the highest ranking score, followed by mulching and maintaining natural vegetation covers or cover crops.

The interviewed stakeholders believe that the application of more sustainable soil conservation practices in potato production in the area of study is diffculted by the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness and the lack of tradition on this area, as well as by the insufficient governmental support on technical issues and the lack of enabling legislation (Table 15). Regarding the integration of more sustainable soil conservation practices within different cropping systems, the interviewed stakeholders think that that they are equally effective under organic and conventional farming (Table 16). Most of the respondents also believe that they would be more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 17) and that their effectiveness is similar under irrigation or under rainfed conditions (Table 18).

To finish, relating to **pest and disease control practices**, results in Table A5.4 show that most of the interviewed stakeholders think that none of the proposed pest and disease control practices are effective to reach most end users' objectives. However, despite such belief, many stakeholders think that use of pesticides is the most effective alternative to reduce the incidence of pests and diseases, while a lower number also points out at the use of trap crops. The use of allelopathic crops, such as *Brassicae* is selected as the best option to mobilise soil nutrients and to increase soil fertility, while the use of pest alerts is selected as the most effective alternative to reduce soil pollution and improve water quality. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 19 and Table 24) confirm these findings as respondents give the highest possible score ranking to none of these practice are effective to achieve this objective, nearly double up the ranking score given to the use of allelopathic crops, being trap crops the third highest ranked alternative. A majority of interviewed stakeholders think that the implementation of more innovative pest control practices in potato production in the area is difficulted by lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness and the lack of enabling legislation/regulation (Table 20). On the other hand, a significant number of respondents thinks that they are easy to implement practices. Concerning the integration of more sustainable pest control practices within different cropping systems, a majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that they are equally effective under organic and conventional farming (Table 21) and that their effectiveness is greater in diversified cropping system (Table 22) , while they perceive that they would be equally or more effective under irrigation than under rainfed conditions (Table 23).

Table A5.1. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective tillage practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for potato production in Flanders (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Conventional tillage	Tillage according level curves	Shallow tillage	Minimum tillage (reduced tillage frequency)	No tillage with herbicides	No tillage without herbicides (mechanical weed control)	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	11	18.18%	9.09%	9.09%	36.36%	0.00%	0.00%	9.09%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	5	40.00%	0.00%	20.00%	20.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	10	40.00%	0.00%	0.00%	10.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%
Increase soil organic matter content	12	0.00%	8.33%	16.67%	41.67%	0.00%	0.00%	25.00%
Improve soil structure	9	11.11%	11.11%	0.00%	55.56%	0.00%	0.00%	11.11%
Increase soil biodiversity	6	16.67%	16.67%	16.67%	16.67%	0.00%	16.67%	16.67%
Reduce soil erosion	4	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	25.00%	25.00%
Reduce soil pollution	2	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%
Reduce soil salinization								
Reduce soil acidification	3	0.00%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	66.67%
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems								
Improve water quality	5	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%	20.00%	40.00%
Reduce the incidence of weeds								
Increasing load carrying capacity								

Table A5.2. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective fertilization practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for potato production in Flanders (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Incorporating crops residues into the soil	Addition of solid organic matter/manures	Use of green manure	Combination of manure and mineral fertilizers	Precision agriculture to optimise fertilization	Use of biostimulants, biofertilizers, etc.	Addition of slurries	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	10	0.00%	50.00%	20.00%	10.00%	0.00%	10.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	5	0.00%	40.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	9	11.11%	22.22%	11.11%	0.00%	11.11%	11.11%	0.00%	33.33%
Increase soil organic matter content	11	0.00%	72.73%	18.18%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Improve soil structure	8	0.00%	37.50%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	12.50%	0.00%	0.00%
Increase soil biodiversity	5	0.00%	60.00%	40.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil erosion	3	0.00%	33.33%	66.67%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil pollution	2	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil salinization									
Reduce soil acidification	3	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	66.67%
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems									
Improve water quality	5	0.00%	20.00%	40.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce the incidence of weeds									
Increasing load carrying capacity									

Table A5.3. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective soil conservation practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for potato production in Flanders (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Mulching (with crushed offcuts from pruning, etc.)	Maintain vegetation cover (natural or cover crops)	Maintain strips of vegetation between lines	Hedges or natural vegetation on the edges of the plots	Erosion barriers or margins with vegetation	Addition of organic matter	Crop diversification	Use of catch crops to reduce N/P leaching	Avoiding plant protection products	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	10	30.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%			30.00%	10.00%	0.00%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	5	20.00%	40.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%			20.00%	20.00%	0.00%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	9	0.00%	0.00%	11.11%	33.33%	0.00%			22.22%	0.00%	22.22%
Increase soil organic matter content	11	18.18%	18.18%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%			45.45%	9.09%	0.00%
Improve soil structure	8	37.50%	25.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%			37.50%	0.00%	0.00%
Increase soil biodiversity	5	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%			40.00%	40.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil erosion	3	0.00%	0.00%	33.33%	33.33%	33.33%			0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil pollution	2	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%			0.00%	100.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil salinization											
Reduce soil acidification	3	33.33%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%			0.00%	0.00%	66.67%
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems											
Improve water quality	5	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%			60.00%	20.00%	0.00%
Reduce the incidence of weeds											
Increasing load carrying capacity											

Table A5.4. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective pest and disease control practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for potato production in Flanders (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Pests alerts	Crop diversification	Trap crops	Increase soil invertebrates biodiversity	Use of biostimulants and mycorrhiza, etc.	Use of pesticides	Ploughing	Alelopathic crops. such as Brassicae	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	10	10.00%		0.00%			0.00%		20.00%	60.00%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	5	0.00%		0.00%			0.00%		40.00%	60.00%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	9	11.11%		22.22%			44.44%		11.11%	11.11%
Increase soil organic matter content	11	0.00%		0.00%			9.09%		36.36%	54.55%
Improve soil structure	8	0.00%		0.00%			0.00%		25.00%	75.00%
Increase soil biodiversity	5	20.00%		0.00%			0.00%		20.00%	40.00%
Reduce soil erosion	3	0.00%		0.00%			0.00%		33.33%	33.33%
Reduce soil pollution	2	50.00%		0.00%			0.00%		0.00%	50.00%
Reduce soil salinization										
Reduce soil acidification	3	0.00%		0.00%			0.00%		0.00%	66.67%
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems										
Improve water quality	5	40.00%		0.00%			0.00%		0.00%	20.00%
Reduce the incidence of weeds										
Increasing load carrying capacity										

A6. VEGETABLES, ATLANTIC CENTRAL (BELGIUM)

Problems and objectives for action

The stakeholders interviewed in the Belgian Atlantic central vegetables case study do not perceive any agronomic **problems** as being of high or very high severity (Table 2). The most severe problems identified are, on average, as of a medium-high severity, rainfall scarcity in the growing period and irrigation water scarcity, followed by the high weed pressure and the high incidence of pests and fungal diseases. In contrast, the problems considered less essential for stakeholders are soil erosion, water pollution by leaching and/or run-off of nutrients, soil acidification and the low and/or variable yields (Table 2).

The priority given by the stakeholders to different **objectives** for addressing the agronomic problems in the Belgian Atlantic central vegetables case study (Table 3)) points at increasing soil fertility, soil organic content and soil biodiversity and improving soil structure as the most urgent needs. On the other hand, the most severe problems for stakeholders are reducing soil pollution and improving water quality. These results are qualitatively very similar to the others of Belgian (Atlantic Central) case studies, potato and wheat.

Identification of farming practices

Concerning **tillage practices**, results showed in Table A6.1 explain that the respondents choose different tillage practices as the most satisfactory one depending on the end-users' need to be achieved (objectives). Minimum tillage is the practice selected by more stakeholders as the most effective for the majority of the objectives, such as increasing soil fertility and biodiversity and improving soil structure and water quality. However, for other objectives, such as mobilising soil nutrients and reducing the incidence of pests, minimum tillage is selected by the same proportion of respondents than conventional tillage and shallow tillage (which is also selected as the most effective tillage practice to increase soil organic matter content). Additionally, tillage following level curves (contour tillage) is pointed out as the most adequate practice to reduce soil erosion. Despite the number of respondents that select conventional tillage, it is clear that a majority select some type of less intensive tillage as the most effective tillage alternative. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 4 and Table 24) confirm these findings, , as respondents give the highest ranking score to minimum tillage, while shallow tillage receives the second highest ranking score, followed by conventional tillage.

The interviewed stakeholders consider that the implementation of more sustainable tillage practices in vegetables production in the area of study is diffculted by the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness, the lack of tradition and because they feel that support from the government on technical issues is inadequate or insufficient (Table 5). On the other hand, stakeholders do not perceive these tillage practices as difficult to implement with adequate technical advice and do not perceive that they are not profitable. Regarding the effectiveness of more sustainable tillage practices when integrated within different cropping systems, the majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that they are more effective under

organic production (Table 6), but more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 7) and equally effective under irrigation than under rainfed conditions (Table 8).

With respect to **fertilization practices**, the surveyed stakeholders think that the addition of solid organic matter/manures is the most effective alternative to satisfy many of the identified end users' needs in vegetables production in the area (Table A6.2), such as increasing soil fertility and soil organic matter content, improving soil structure and reducing soil erosion, closely followed by the use of green manure, which is selected by more respondents as the most adequate fertilization practice to improve water quality, reduce soil pollution, increase soil biodiversity and improve soil structure. Additionally, combining manure and mineral fertilizers is the most selected fertilization practice to mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth period and to reduce soil acidification. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 9 and Table 24) confirm these findings as the respondents give the highest ranking score to both the addition of soil organic matter/manures and the use of green manure.

Turning to the barriers for the implementation of more sustainable fertilization practices in vegetables production, the interviewed stakeholders point at the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness as the most important obstacle, followed by the lack of enabling regulation, the lack of adequate technical support from the government and the lack of tradition in the region (Table 10). Regarding the effectiveness of more sustainable fertilization practices when integrated within different cropping systems, the majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that that they are equally or more effective under organic than under conventional farming (Table 11). Most of the respondents think that they would be more effective if integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 12) and equally effective under irrigation and under rainfed conditions (Table 13).

Relating to **soil conservation practices**, results in Table A6.3 show that a majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that use of catch crops is the most effective alternative for soil conservation for many of the objectives, together with mulching (with crushed offcuts from pruning, etc.) and, to a lesser extent, maintaining vegetation covers (natural or cover crops). The use of catch crops is the most selected soil conservation alternative to mobilise soil nutrients and increase soil fertility, improve soil structure and water quality and to reduce soil acidification, followed by mulching that is the most selected alternative to increase soil organic matter content. Additionally, maintaining vegetation covers is the most selected alternative to reduce soil erosion but also to increase soil biodiversity. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 14 and Table 24) confirm these findings, as catch crops receive the highest ranking score, closely followed by mulching and, to a lesser extent by natural vegetation covers or cover crops.

The interviewed stakeholders believe that the application of more sustainable soil conservation practices in vegetables production in the area of study is diffculted by the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness and the lack of tradition on this area, as well as by the lack of enabling legislation (Table 15). Regarding the integration of more sustainable soil conservation practices within different vegetables cropping systems, the interviewed stakeholders think that they would be equally effective under organic and conventional farming (Table 16). Most of the respondents also believe that they would be more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 17) and that their effectiveness is similar under irrigation or under rainfed conditions (Table 18).

To finish, relating to **pest and disease control practices**, results in Table A6.4 show that most of the interviewed stakeholders think that none of the proposed pest and disease control practices are effective to reach most end users' objectives. However, despite such belief, many stakeholders think that use of pesticides is the most effective alternative to reduce the incidence of pests and diseases, while a lower number also points out at the use of trap crops and/or pest alerts. Leaving that choice out, the use of trap crops is the most selected to increase soil biodiversity and reduce soil erosion, while the use of pest alerts is selected as the most effective alternative to reduce soil pollution and improve water quality. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 19 and Table 24) confirm these findings as respondents give the highest possible score ranking to the choice "none of these practice are effective to achieve this objective", more than doubling up the ranking score given to the use of trap crops, being pest alerts the third highest ranked alternative.

A majority of interviewed stakeholders think that the main constraints for the implementation of more innovative pest control practices in vegetables production in the area are lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness and, to a lesser extent, the lack of tradition and the lack of enabling legislation/regulation (Table 20). On the other hand, a significant number of respondents thinks that they are easy to implement farming practices. Concerning the integration of more sustainable pest control practices within different cropping systems, a majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that they are, at least, equally effective under organic than under conventional farming (Table 21) and that their effectiveness is greater if integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 22), while they would be equally effective under irrigation and rainfed conditions (Table 23).

Table A6.1. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective tillage practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for vegetables production in Flanders (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Conventional tillage	Tillage according level curves	Shallow tillage	Minimum tillage (reduced tillage frequency)	No tillage with herbicides	No tillage without herbicides (mechanical weed control)	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	16	25.00%	0.00%	18.75%	37.50%	0.00%	0.00%	6.25%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	7	28.57%	0.00%	28.57%	28.57%	14.29%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	14	21.43%	0.00%	21.43%	21.43%	0.00%	7.14%	21.43%
Increase soil organic matter content	19	15.79%	0.00%	42.11%	26.32%	5.26%	0.00%	5.26%
Improve soil structure	19	21.05%	5.26%	15.79%	36.84%	0.00%	0.00%	15.79%
Increase soil biodiversity	18	11.11%	5.56%	16.67%	38.89%	0.00%	16.67%	5.56%
Reduce soil erosion	6	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	16.67%	16.67%	16.67%	0.00%
Reduce soil pollution	3	0.00%	0.00%	66.67%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	33.33%
Reduce soil salinization								
Reduce soil acidification	6	16.67%	0.00%	16.67%	33.33%	0.00%	0.00%	33.33%
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems								
Improve water quality	8	0.00%	12.50%	25.00%	37.50%	0.00%	12.50%	0.00%
Reduce the incidence of weeds								
Increasing load carrying capacity								

Table A6.2. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective fertilization practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for vegetables production in Flanders (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Incorporating crops residues into the soil	Addition of solid organic matter/manures	Use of green manure	Combination of manure and mineral fertilizers	Precision agriculture to optimise fertilization	Use of biostimulants, biofertilizers, etc.	Addition of slurries	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	16	0.00%	62.50%	25.00%	12.50%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	7	14.29%	0.00%	0.00%	57.14%	0.00%	14.29%	14.29%	0.00%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	14	14.29%	0.00%	21.43%	21.43%	0.00%	28.57%	0.00%	7.14%
Increase soil organic matter content	19	10.53%	52.63%	36.84%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Improve soil structure	19	5.26%	42.11%	42.11%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	5.26%
Increase soil biodiversity	18	0.00%	33.33%	44.44%	0.00%	0.00%	16.67%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil erosion	6	0.00%	50.00%	33.33%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	16.67%
Reduce soil pollution	3	0.00%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	0.00%	33.33%
Reduce soil salinization									
Reduce soil acidification	6	0.00%	33.33%	16.67%	33.33%	16.67%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems									
Improve water quality	8	0.00%	25.00%	62.50%	12.50%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce the incidence of weeds									
Increasing load carrying capacity									

Table A6.3. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective soil conservation practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for vegetables production in Flanders (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Mulching (with crushed offcuts from pruning, etc.)	Maintain vegetation cover (natural or cover crops)	Maintain strips of vegetation between lines	Hedges or natural vegetation on the edges of the plots	Erosion barriers or margins with vegetation	Addition of organic matter	Crop diversification	Use of catch crops to reduce N/P leaching	Avoiding plant protection products	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	14	28.57%	14.29%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%		57.14%	0.00%	0.00%	
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	6	33.33%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%		50.00%	0.00%	16.67%	
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	12	16.67%	0.00%	16.67%	16.67%	0.00%		16.67%	8.33%	16.67%	
Increase soil organic matter content	16	75.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%		18.75%	0.00%	6.25%	
Improve soil structure	16	31.25%	12.50%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%		56.25%	0.00%	0.00%	
Increase soil biodiversity	15	26.67%	26.67%	0.00%	6.67%	0.00%		20.00%	13.33%	0.00%	
Reduce soil erosion	5	0.00%	60.00%	0.00%	0.00%	20.00%		20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	
Reduce soil pollution	2	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%		0.00%	50.00%	50.00%	
Reduce soil salinization											
Reduce soil acidification	4	25.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%		25.00%	0.00%	50.00%	
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems											
Improve water quality	6	16.67%	0.00%	0.00%	16.67%	0.00%		50.00%	16.67%	0.00%	
Reduce the incidence of weeds											
Increasing load carrying capacity											

Table A6.4. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective pest and disease control practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for vegetables production in Flanders (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Pests alerts	Crop diversification	Trap crops	Increase soil invertebrates biodiversity	Use of biostimulants and mycorrhiza, etc.	Use of pesticides	Ploughing	Alelopathic crops. such as Brassicae	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	14	14.29%		14.29%			14.29%		7.14%	50.00%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	6	0.00%		0.00%			0.00%		0.00%	100.00%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	12	25.00%		25.00%			33.33%		16.67%	0.00%
Increase soil organic matter content	16	6.25%		18.75%			0.00%		6.25%	62.50%
Improve soil structure	16	0.00%		12.50%			0.00%		0.00%	75.00%
Increase soil biodiversity	15	6.67%		26.67%			0.00%		6.67%	53.33%
Reduce soil erosion	5	0.00%		40.00%			0.00%		0.00%	60.00%
Reduce soil pollution	2	50.00%		0.00%			0.00%		0.00%	50.00%
Reduce soil salinization										
Reduce soil acidification	4	0.00%		0.00%			0.00%		0.00%	100.00%
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems										
Improve water quality	6	33.33%		16.67%			0.00%		0.00%	50.00%
Reduce the incidence of weeds										
Increasing load carrying capacity										

A7. WHEAT, ATLANTIC CENTRAL (BELGIUM)

Problems and objectives for action

The stakeholders interviewed in the Belgian Atlantic central wheat case study do not identify any agronomic **problems** as being of high or very high severity (Table 2). The most severe problems, perceived, on average, as of a medium-low severity, are the high incidence of fungal diseases, the high use of phytosanitary products and the development of resistance to phytosanitary products. In contrast, the less severe problems for stakeholders are irrigation water scarcity and soil erosion (Table 2).

The priority given by the Flemish stakeholders to different **objectives** for addressing the agronomic problems in the Belgian Atlantic central wheat case study (Table 3) points at increasing soil organic matter content as the most important one, followed by reducing the incidence of pests and disease, improving soil structure and increasing soil fertility. These results are qualitatively very similar to those in the Belgian potato and vegetables case studies.

Identification of farming practices

Concerning **tillage practices**, values in Table A7.1 show that the respondents choose different tillage practices as the most adequate one depending on the end-users' need to be fulfilled (objectives). Stakeholders' answer highlight again a dichotomy between the use of conventional tillage and less intensive tillage practice. Conventional tillage is the tillage practice selected by more stakeholders as the most effective for the majority for objectives such as increasing soil fertility, reducing the incidence of pests and disease, improving soil structure and reducing soil acidification, always followed by minimum tillage as the second most selected alternative. On the other hand, minimum tillage is the most selected tillage practice to mobilise soil nutrients, increase soil biodiversity and reduce soil pollution, while shallow tillage is the most selected alternative to increase soil organic matter and to reduce soil pollution (followed by conventional tillage). The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 4 and Table 24) confirm these findings, as respondents provide the highest ranking score to conventional tillage, while minimum tillage gets the highest second ranking score, followed by shallow tillage. However, the stakeholders' preference for less intensive tillage is clear.

The interviewed stakeholders consider that the implementation of more sustainable tillage practices in wheat production in the area of study is difficulted by the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness, their higher cost and the lack of tradition (Table 5). On the other hand, stakeholders do not perceive these tillage practices as difficult to implement with adequate technical advice and do not perceive that they are not profitable. Regarding the effectiveness of more sustainable tillage practices when integrated within different cropping systems, the majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that they are equally effective under organic and conventional farming (Table 6), but more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 7) and equally or more effective under irrigation than under rainfed conditions (Table 8).

With respect to **fertilization practices**, the surveyed stakeholders think that the addition of solid organic matter/manures is the most effective alternative to satisfy many of the identified end users' needs in wheat production in the area (Table A7.2), such as increasing soil organic matter content, soil biodiversity and soil fertility, improving soil structure and reducing soil structure, always followed by the use of green manure, which is the most selected alternative to reduce soil pollution and to improve water quality. Additionally, the incorporation of crops residues into the soil is the most selected fertilization practice in order to reduce the incidence of pests and diseases. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 9 and Table 24) confirm these findings as the respondents give the highest ranking score to the option of the addition of soil organic matter/manures followed by the use of green manure, similarly to the potato and vegetables Flemish case studies.

Turning to the barriers for the implementation of more sustainable fertilization practices in wheat production, the interviewed stakeholders point at the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness as the most important obstacle, followed by the lack of enabling regulation and the high costs (Table 10). Regarding the effectiveness of more sustainable fertilization practices when integrated within different cropping systems, the majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that they are equally effective under organic and conventional farming (Table 11). Most of the respondents think that they would be more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 12) and that their effectiveness is similar under irrigation and under rainfed conditions (Table 13).

Relating to **soil conservation practices**, results in Table A7.3 show that a majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that use of catch crops is the most effective alternative for soil conservation for many of the objectives, together with mulching (with crushed offcuts from pruning, etc.) and, to a lesser extent, maintaining vegetation covers (natural or cover crops). The use of catch crops is the most selected soil conservation alternative to mobilise soil nutrients and increase soil fertility, improve soil structure, reduce soil pollution and acidification and improve water quality, followed by mulching that is the most selected alternative to increase soil organic matter content. Additionally, maintaining vegetation covers is the most selected alternative to reduce soil erosion but also to increase soil biodiversity. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 14 and Table 24) confirm these findings, as catch crops receive the highest ranking score, followed by mulching and maintaining natural vegetation covers or cover crops.

The interviewed stakeholders believe that the application of more sustainable soil conservation practices in wheat production in the area of study is difficulted by the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness and the lack of enabling legislation, as well as by the lack of tradition in the area and their high cost for farmers (Table 15). Regarding the integration of more sustainable soil conservation practices within different cropping systems, the interviewed stakeholders think that they are equally effective under organic and conventional farming (Table 16). Most of the respondents also believe that they would be more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 17) and that their effectiveness is similar under irrigation or under rainfed conditions (Table 18).

To finish, relating to **pest and disease control practices**, results in Table A7.4 show that most of the interviewed stakeholders think that none of the proposed pest and disease control practices are effective to reach most end users' objectives. However, despite such belief, stakeholders select different alternatives depending on the objective in question. The use of pesticides is the

most selected alternative to reduce the incidence of pest and diseases, while pest alerts are the second one. Trap crops are the most selected one to reduce soil pollution and improve water quality, while allelopathic crops are selected as the best option to reduce soil erosion and soil pollution. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 19 and Table 24) confirm these findings as respondents give the highest possible score ranking to none of these practice are effective to achieve this objective, nearly double up the ranking score given to the use of trap crops, being pest alerts the third highest ranked alternative.

A majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that the implementation of more innovative pest control practices in wheat production in the area is difficulted by lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness and the lack of enabling legislation/regulation (Table 20). On the other hand, a significant number of respondents thinks that they are easy to implement practices if adequate technical advice is provided. Concerning the integration of more sustainable pest control practices within different cropping systems, a majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that they are equally effective under organic and conventional farming (Table 21) and that their effectiveness is greater in diversified cropping system (Table 22) , while they perceive that they would be equally or more effective under irrigation than under rainfed conditions (Table 23).

Table A7.1. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective tillage practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for wheat production in Flanders (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Conventional tillage	Tillage according level curves	Shallow tillage	Minimum tillage (reduced tillage frequency)	No tillage with herbicides	No tillage without herbicides (mechanical weed control)	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	23	43.48%	4.35%	8.70%	30.43%	8.70%	0.00%	4.35%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	22	27.27%	4.55%	13.64%	31.82%	4.55%	0.00%	9.09%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	26	53.85%	0.00%	3.85%	11.54%	11.54%	0.00%	15.38%
Increase soil organic matter content	23	26.09%	0.00%	52.17%	17.39%	4.35%	0.00%	0.00%
Improve soil structure	23	43.48%	4.35%	17.39%	21.74%	8.70%	0.00%	4.35%
Increase soil biodiversity	17	5.88%	11.76%	23.53%	47.06%	11.76%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil erosion	9	0.00%	22.22%	33.33%	22.22%	22.22%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil pollution	7	28.57%	0.00%	0.00%	42.86%	14.29%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil salinization								
Reduce soil acidification	12	50.00%	8.33%	16.67%	16.67%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems								
Improve water quality	13	23.08%	23.08%	0.00%	23.08%	7.69%	0.00%	7.69%
Reduce the incidence of weeds								
Increasing load carrying capacity								

Table A7.2. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective fertilization practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for wheat production in Flanders (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Incorporating crops residues into the soil	Addition of solid organic matter/manures	Use of green manure	Combination of manure and mineral fertilizers	Precision agriculture to optimise fertilization	Use of biostimulants, biofertilizers, etc.	Addition of slurries	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	22	9.09%	45.45%	22.73%	18.18%	0.00%	0.00%	4.55%	0.00%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	22	9.09%	18.18%	9.09%	13.64%	13.64%	18.18%	13.64%	0.00%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	25	24.00%	12.00%	8.00%	4.00%	16.00%	12.00%	0.00%	16.00%
Increase soil organic matter content	22	4.55%	59.09%	22.73%	9.09%	0.00%	4.55%	0.00%	0.00%
Improve soil structure	22	4.55%	54.55%	31.82%	4.55%	4.55%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Increase soil biodiversity	16	6.25%	56.25%	31.25%	6.25%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil erosion	9	0.00%	44.44%	44.44%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil pollution	7	0.00%	28.57%	57.14%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil salinization									
Reduce soil acidification	11	0.00%	18.18%	27.27%	27.27%	18.18%	0.00%	0.00%	9.09%
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems									
Improve water quality	13	0.00%	7.69%	69.23%	0.00%	15.38%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce the incidence of weeds									
Increasing load carrying capacity									

Table A7.3. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective soil conservation practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for wheat production in Flanders (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Mulching (with crushed offcuts from pruning, etc.)	Maintain vegetation cover (natural or cover crops)	Maintain strips of vegetation between lines	Hedges or natural vegetation on the edges of the plots	Erosion barriers or margins with vegetation	Addition of organic matter	Crop diversification	Use of catch crops to reduce N/P leaching	Avoiding plant protection products	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	20	25.00%	15.00%	0.00%	0.00%	5.00%			50.00%	0.00%	5.00%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	20	15.00%	10.00%	5.00%	0.00%	0.00%			50.00%	0.00%	15.00%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	20	10.00%	15.00%	10.00%	30.00%	0.00%			20.00%	5.00%	5.00%
Increase soil organic matter content	18	50.00%	16.67%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%			27.78%	0.00%	5.56%
Improve soil structure	18	22.22%	22.22%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%			50.00%	0.00%	5.56%
Increase soil biodiversity	13	30.77%	30.77%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%			23.08%	7.69%	0.00%
Reduce soil erosion	7	28.57%	42.86%	14.29%	0.00%	0.00%			14.29%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil pollution	4	0.00%	25.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%			75.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil salinization											
Reduce soil acidification	8	0.00%	12.50%	0.00%	12.50%	0.00%			50.00%	0.00%	12.50%
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems											
Improve water quality	12	0.00%	8.33%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%			75.00%	0.00%	8.33%
Reduce the incidence of weeds											
Increasing load carrying capacity											

Table A7.4. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective pest and disease control practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for wheat production in Flanders (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Pests alerts	Crop diversification	Trap crops	Increase soil invertebrates biodiversity	Use of biostimulants and mycorrhiza, etc.	Use of pesticides	Ploughing	Alelopathic crops. such as Brassicae	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	18	5.56%		5.56%			22.22%		16.67%	50.00%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	19	5.26%		15.79%			0.00%		15.79%	52.63%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	20	35.00%		10.00%			50.00%		0.00%	0.00%
Increase soil organic matter content	17	5.88%		17.65%			5.88%		11.76%	58.82%
Improve soil structure	17	11.76%		17.65%			5.88%		17.65%	41.18%
Increase soil biodiversity	13	15.38%		23.08%			7.69%		15.38%	23.08%
Reduce soil erosion	7	28.57%		14.29%			0.00%		28.57%	28.57%
Reduce soil pollution	4	25.00%		25.00%			0.00%		25.00%	25.00%
Reduce soil salinization										
Reduce soil acidification	8	12.50%		12.50%			12.50%		0.00%	62.50%
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems										
Improve water quality	12	8.33%		25.00%			0.00%		8.33%	50.00%
Reduce the incidence of weeds										
Increasing load carrying capacity										

A8. POTATO, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY

Problems and objectives for action

The stakeholders interviewed in the German Continental potato case study do not perceive, on average, any agronomic **problems** as being of high or very high severity (Table 2). The most severe problems, perceived on average as of a medium-high severity, are rainfall scarcity and high weed pressure, closely followed by the low and/or variable yields and the high incidence of pests and fungal diseases. On the other hand, the less severe problems for stakeholders are water pollution, the development of resistance to plant protection products, soil acidification, the low number of earthworms in the soil and the low soil microbial biodiversity.

The assessment of the priority given by stakeholders to different **objectives** for addressing the agronomic problems in the German Continental potato case study (Table 3) points at reducing the incidence of weeds, mobilizing soil nutrients during the plant growth stage and reducing the incidence of pests and diseases as the most urgent needs, followed by increasing soil fertility and soil organic matter content. These results are qualitatively very similar to those in the German Continental wheat case study but the wheat stakeholders give a greater importance to improving soil structure and increasing soil organic matter content and biodiversity than potato stakeholders do.

Identification of farming practices

Regarding **tillage practices**, results in Table A8.1 show that the respondents choose different tillage practices as the most adequate one depending on the end-users' need to be fulfilled (objectives). As in other case studies, stakeholders' answer highlight once more the controversy between the use of conventional tillage and less intensive tillage practice. Conventional tillage is the tillage practice selected by more stakeholders as the most effective for objectives such as reducing the incidence of pests and diseases, reducing soil acidification and mobilising soil nutrients. On the other hand, minimum tillage is the most selected tillage practice to increase soil biodiversity and fertility, improve soil structure and water infiltration and reduce soil erosion. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 4 and Table 24) confirm these findings, as respondents provide the highest ranking score to minimum tillage, closely followed by conventional tillage and, to a lesser extent, no tillage with application of herbicides.

The interviewed stakeholders think that the implementation of more sustainable tillage practices in potato production in the area of study is diffculted by the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness, the lack of profitability and their complexity even if technical advice is available (Table 5). On the other hand, none of the interviewed stakeholders perceive these tillage practices as incompatible with other farming practices. Regarding the effectiveness of more sustainable tillage practices when integrated within different cropping systems, the majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that they would be equally effective under both organic and conventional farming (Table 6), but more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 7) and similarly, or even more, effective under irrigation than under rainfed conditions (Table 8).

With respect to **fertilization practices**, the interviewed stakeholders choose different alternatives as the most effective for each users' needs (objectives) in potato production in the area (Table A8.2). Green manure is the most selected alternative to improve soil structure and water infiltration, to increase soil biodiversity and to reduce the incidence of weeds as well as soil pollution and acidification. The addition of solid organic matter is the most chosen fertilization practice to increase soil organic matter content and soil fertility and to improve soil structure, while incorporating crop residues in the soil is the most chosen one to reduce soil erosion and the use of biostimulants, biofertilizers, mycorrhizas and new generation fertilisers is the most selected alternative to mobilise soil nutrients and to reduce the incidence of pests and diseases. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 9 and Table 24) confirm these findings as the respondents give the highest ranking score to the use of green manure, followed by the addition of soil organic matter/manures and the use of biostimulants, biofertilizers, etc.

Turning to the barriers for the implementation of more sustainable fertilization practices in potato production, the interviewed stakeholders point at the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness and to the complexity of their implementation, even if technical advice is available, as the major difficulties, as well as to the lack of tradition in the region and the lack of enabling regulation (Table 10). Regarding the effectiveness of more sustainable fertilization practices when integrated within different cropping systems, the majority of the interviewed stakeholders thinks that they are equally or even more effective under organic production (Table 11). A majority also thinks that they would be more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 12) and that their effectiveness is similar, or even greater, under irrigation than under rainfed conditions (Table 13).

Table A8.1. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective tillage practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for potato production in Germany (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Conventional tillage	Tillage according level curves	Shallow tillage	Minimum tillage (reduced tillage frequency)	No tillage with herbicides	No tillage without herbicides (mechanical weed control)	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	7	28.57%	0.00%	0.00%	28.57%	0.00%	14.29%	14.29%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	9	44.44%	0.00%	0.00%	22.22%	0.00%	11.11%	11.11%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	8	62.50%	0.00%	0.00%	12.50%	0.00%	0.00%	25.00%
Increase soil organic matter content	6	0.00%	0.00%	33.33%	16.67%	16.67%	0.00%	16.67%
Improve soil structure	5	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	40.00%	20.00%	0.00%	20.00%
Increase soil biodiversity	4	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil erosion	4	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil pollution	2	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%
Reduce soil salinization								
Reduce soil acidification	2	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	3	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	66.67%	0.00%	0.00%	33.33%
Improve water quality								
Reduce the incidence of weeds	11	18.18%	0.00%	9.09%	0.00%	45.45%	18.18%	9.09%
Increasing load carrying capacity								

Regarding **soil conservation practices**, results in Table A8.3 show that the interviewed stakeholders choose different soil conservation practices as the most adequate one depending on the end-users' need to be fulfilled (objectives), although crop diversification and vegetation covers (natural or cultivated) are the most selected alternatives for increasing soil organic matter and improving water infiltration. Crop diversification is selected as the best alternative for objectives such as reducing the incidence of pests and diseases, increasing soil biodiversity and reducing soil pollution. On the other hand, soil vegetation covers are selected as the most effective soil conservation practice to improve soil structure, to increase soil fertility and to reduce the incidence of weeds. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 14 and Table 24) confirm these findings as crop diversification receives the same ranking score than vegetation covers (natural or cultivated), nearly doubling the ranking score given to the use of catch crops that is the third highest ranked practice.

Again, the interviewed stakeholders think that the implementation of more sustainable soil conservation practices in potato production in the area of study is mostly diffculted by the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness and the complexity of their implementation even with adequate technical advice (Table 15). In relation with the integration of more sustainable soil conservation practices within different cropping systems, the majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that they are equally effective under organic than under conventional farming (Table 16). Again, a majority of respondents perceived them as more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 17) and that their effectiveness is similar, or even greater, under irrigation than under rainfed conditions (Table 18).

Last, with respect to **pest and disease control practices**, results in Table A8.4 show that the interviewed stakeholders choose different pest and disease control practices as the most adequate one depending on the end-users' need to be fulfilled (objectives). Crop diversification is the alternative more selected as the most effective one to mobilise soil nutrients, reduce soil erosion and increase soil fertility. Crop diversification and increasing invertebrates biodiversity are equally selected as the most adequate alternatives to improve soil structure and to increase soil biodiversity. Additionally, the use of biostimulants, mycorrhiza, biofertilizers, etc. are selected as the best option to increase soil organic matter, while the use of pesticides are selected as the best alternative to reduce the incidence of pests and diseases and of weeds. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 19 and Table 24) confirm these findings as respondents give the highest possible score ranking to crop diversification, followed by increasing soil invertebrates biodiversity and using pesticides.

Turning to the barriers for the implementation of more sustainable pest and diseases control practices in potato production, the interviewed stakeholders point at the complexity of their implementation, even if technical advice is available, and the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness, as the major difficulties (Table 20). About a fifth of the respondents also point at the lack of enabling legislation. Regarding the integration of more sustainable pest control practices within different cropping systems, a majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that they are equally effective under organic production than under conventional farming (Table 21) and that their effectiveness is similar under both rainfed and irrigated conditions (Table 23). Last, they think that they would be more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 22).

Table A8.2. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective fertilization practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for potato production in Germany (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Incorporating crops residues into the soil	Addition of solid organic matter/manures	Use of green manure	Combination of manure and mineral fertilizers	Precision agriculture to optimise fertilization	Use of biostimulants, biofertilizers, etc.	Addition of slurries	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	6	0.00%	50.00%	16.67%	16.67%	0.00%	16.67%		0.00%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	9	11.11%	11.11%	22.22%	11.11%	11.11%	33.33%		0.00%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	7	14.29%	14.29%	14.29%	0.00%	0.00%	28.57%		28.57%
Increase soil organic matter content	6	16.67%	66.67%	0.00%	0.00%	16.67%	0.00%		0.00%
Improve soil structure	5	20.00%	40.00%	40.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%		0.00%
Increase soil biodiversity	4	25.00%	0.00%	50.00%	25.00%	0.00%	0.00%		0.00%
Reduce soil erosion	4	50.00%	25.00%	25.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%		0.00%
Reduce soil pollution	2	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%		0.00%
Reduce soil salinization									
Reduce soil acidification	2	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%		0.00%
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	3	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%		0.00%
Improve water quality									
Reduce the incidence of weeds	10	0.00%	0.00%	60.00%	10.00%	10.00%	10.00%		10.00%
Increasing load carrying capacity									

Table A8.3. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective soil conservation practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for potato production in Germany (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Mulching (with crushed offcuts from pruning, etc.)	Maintain vegetation cover (natural or cover crops)	Maintain strips of vegetation between lines	Hedges or natural vegetation on the edges of the plots	Erosion barriers or margins with vegetation	Addition of organic matter	Crop diversification	Use of catch crops to reduce N/P leaching	Avoiding plant protection products	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	6	16.67%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%			16.67%	0.00%	16.67%	0.00%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	9	11.11%	22.22%	0.00%	0.00%			22.22%	22.22%	0.00%	22.22%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	7	0.00%	14.29%	14.29%	0.00%			42.86%	0.00%	0.00%	28.57%
Increase soil organic matter content	6	16.67%	33.33%	0.00%	0.00%			33.33%	16.67%	0.00%	0.00%
Improve soil structure	5	20.00%	60.00%	0.00%	0.00%			20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Increase soil biodiversity	4	0.00%	25.00%	0.00%	0.00%			50.00%	0.00%	25.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil erosion	4	0.00%	25.00%	0.00%	0.00%			25.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil pollution	2	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%			50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil salinization											
Reduce soil acidification	2	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%			0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	3	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	0.00%			33.33%	33.33%	0.00%	0.00%
Improve water quality											
Reduce the incidence of weeds	10	10.00%	40.00%	0.00%	0.00%			30.00%	0.00%	0.00%	20.00%
Increasing load carrying capacity											

Table A8.4. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective pest and disease control practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for potato production in Germany (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Pests alerts	Crop diversification	Trap crops	Increase soil invertebrates biodiversity	Use of biostimulants and mycorrhiza, etc.	Use of pesticides	Ploughing	Alelopathic crops. such as Brassicae	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	6	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	16.67%	0.00%	33.33%		0.00%	0.00%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	8	0.00%	62.50%	0.00%	12.50%	25.00%	0.00%		0.00%	0.00%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	7	0.00%	14.29%	14.29%	28.57%	0.00%	28.57%		14.29%	0.00%
Increase soil organic matter content	5	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	20.00%	60.00%	0.00%		0.00%	0.00%
Improve soil structure	5	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%	0.00%		0.00%	0.00%
Increase soil biodiversity	4	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%		0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil erosion	3	0.00%	66.67%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%		0.00%	33.33%
Reduce soil pollution	1	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%		0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil salinization										
Reduce soil acidification	1	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%		0.00%	0.00%
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	3	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%		0.00%	33.33%
Improve water quality										
Reduce the incidence of weeds	9	0.00%	44.44%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	55.56%		0.00%	0.00%
Increasing load carrying capacity										

A9. WHEAT, CONTINENTAL, GERMANY

Problems and objectives for action

The stakeholders interviewed in the German Continental wheat case study do not perceive, on average, any agronomic **problems** as being of high or very high severity (Table 2). The most severe problems, perceived on average as of a medium-low severity, are rainfall scarcity and high weed pressure, closely followed by the low and/or variable yields. On the other hand, the less severe problems for stakeholders are soil acidification, soil erosion, the loss of organic matter, the low soil fertility, the low number of earthworms in the soil and the low soil microbial biodiversity.

The assessment of the priority given by stakeholders to different **objectives** for addressing the agronomic problems in the German Continental wheat case study (Table 3) points at reducing the incidence of weeds, increasing soil biodiversity, improving soil structure and increasing soil organic matter content as the most urgent needs, followed by increasing soil fertility, mobilizing soil nutrients during the plant growth stage and reducing the incidence of pests and diseases. These results are qualitatively very similar to those in the German Continental potato case study but the potato stakeholders give less importance to improving soil structure and increasing soil organic matter content and biodiversity than wheat stakeholders do.

Identification of farming practices

Regarding **tillage practices**, results in Table A9.1 show that the respondents choose different tillage practices as the most adequate one depending on the end-users' need to be fulfilled (objectives). Minimum tillage is the most selected tillage practice for the majority of the objectives, such as improving soil structure, mobilising soil nutrients, increasing soil fertility and biodiversity and reducing soil acidification and erosion. In most cases, the second most selected alternative are shallow tillage and no tillage. No tillage with application of herbicides is the most selected alternative to reduce the incidence of weeds. On the other hand, conventional tillage is selected by more stakeholders as the most effective to reduce the incidence of pests and diseases, and the second most effective for weed control and to reduce soil acidification. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 4 and Table 24) confirm these findings, as respondents provide the highest ranking score to minimum tillage, followed by conventional tillage and no tillage with application of herbicides.

The interviewed stakeholders think that the implementation of more sustainable tillage practices in wheat production in the area of study is difficulted because the existing farm machinery does not support these type of practices, because the cost are too high, due to the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness and because of the lack of adequate technical support from the government (Table 5). On the other hand, none of the interviewed stakeholders perceive these tillage practices as incompatible with other farming practices and the majority think that they are easy to implement if adequate technical advice is available. Regarding the effectiveness of more sustainable tillage practices when integrated within different cropping systems, the majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that they are equally or even more effective under conventional farming than under organic production (Table 6), but more effective

when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 7) and equally effective under irrigation than under rainfed conditions (Table 8).

With respect to **fertilization practices**, the interviewed stakeholders choose different alternatives as the most effective for each users' needs (objectives) in potato production in the area (Table A9.2). Green manure is the most selected alternative to improve soil structure and water infiltration and to reduce soil erosion and soil pollution. The addition of solid organic matter is the most chosen fertilization practice to increase soil organic matter content and soil fertility and to improve soil structure, to increase soil biodiversity and to mobilise soil nutrients. Incorporating crop residues in the soil is the most chosen one to reduce the incidence of pests and diseases, while precision agriculture techniques is selected as the most effective alternative to reduce soil pollution, together with the use of green manure. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 9 and Table 24) confirm these findings as the respondents give the highest ranking score to the addition of soil organic matter/manures and the use of green manure, followed, to a lesser extent, by incorporating crop residues to the soil.

Turning to the barriers for the implementation of more sustainable fertilization practices in wheat production, the interviewed stakeholders point at the lack of adequate technical support from the government and the lack of profitability (Table 10). On the other hand, the majority of the stakeholders perceive them as easy to implement. Regarding the effectiveness of more sustainable fertilization practices when integrated within different cropping systems, the majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that they are equally or even more effective under conventional farming than under organic production (Table 11). A majority also thinks that they would be more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 12) and that their effectiveness is similar under irrigation than under rainfed conditions (Table 13).

Table A9.1. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective tillage practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for wheat production in Germany (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Conventional tillage	Tillage according level curves	Shallow tillage	Minimum tillage (reduced tillage frequency)	No tillage with herbicides	No tillage without herbicides (mechanical weed control)	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	7	14.29%	0.00%	28.57%	57.14%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	5	20.00%	20.00%	0.00%	60.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	5	80.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Increase soil organic matter content	7	0.00%	0.00%	28.57%	14.29%	28.57%	14.29%	14.29%
Improve soil structure	6	0.00%	16.67%	0.00%	83.33%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Increase soil biodiversity	7	0.00%	0.00%	14.29%	57.14%	0.00%	28.57%	0.00%
Reduce soil erosion	4	0.00%	0.00%	25.00%	50.00%	25.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil pollution	4	25.00%	0.00%	25.00%	0.00%	25.00%	25.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil salinization								
Reduce soil acidification	3	33.33%	0.00%	0.00%	66.67%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	4	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	25.00%	25.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Improve water quality								
Reduce the incidence of weeds	6	33.33%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	66.67%	0.00%	0.00%
Increasing load carrying capacity								

Regarding **soil conservation practices**, results in Table A9.3 show that the interviewed stakeholders select crop diversification as the most effective soil conservation practice for all the identified end-users' need (objectives), while soil vegetation covers is the second most selected alternative for many objectives, such as reducing the incidence of pests and diseases and weeds, increasing soil organic matter content, reducing soil pollution and acidification and soil erosion. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 14 and Table 24) confirm these findings as crop diversification receives the highest possible ranking score, tripling the ranking score given to vegetation covers (natural or cultivated).

Again, the interviewed stakeholders think that the implementation of more sustainable soil conservation practices in wheat production in the area of study is mostly difficulted by the complexity of their implementation even with adequate technical advice and their high costs (Table 15). In relation with the integration of more sustainable soil conservation practices within different cropping systems, the majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that they are equally effective under organic than under conventional farming (Table 16). Again, a majority of respondents perceived them as more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 17) and that their effectiveness is similar under irrigation than under rainfed conditions (Table 18).

Last, with respect to **pest and disease control practices**, results in Table A9.4 show that the interviewed stakeholders choose different pest and disease control practices as the most adequate one depending on the end-users' need to be fulfilled (objectives). However, crop diversification is the alternative more selected as the most effective one for the majority of objectives: to increase soil organic matter content and fertility, to improve soil structure and water infiltration, to increase soil biodiversity and to reduce soil acidification, pollution and erosion, and to reduce the incidence of weeds. Pest alerts and increasing invertebrates biodiversity are equally selected as the most adequate alternatives to reduce the incidence of pests and diseases, while the use of biostimulants, mycorrhiza, biofertilizers, etc. is the most selected alternative to mobilise soil nutrients. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 19 and Table 24) confirm these findings as respondents give the highest possible score ranking to crop diversification, followed by increasing soil invertebrates biodiversity.

Turning to the barriers for the implementation of more sustainable pest and diseases control practices in wheat production, the interviewed stakeholders point at their high costs as the major difficulty, followed by the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness (Table 20). The vast majority think that they are easy to implement with adequate technical advice and that they are not incompatible with other farming practices. Regarding the integration of more sustainable pest control practices within different cropping systems, a majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that they are equally effective under organic production than under conventional farming (Table 21) and that their effectiveness is similar under both rainfed and irrigated conditions (Table 23). Again, stakeholders think that they would be more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 22).

Table A9.2. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective fertilization practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for wheat production in Germany (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Incorporating crops residues into the soil	Addition of solid organic matter/manures	Use of green manure	Combination of manure and mineral fertilizers	Precision agriculture to optimise fertilization	Use of biostimulants, biofertilizers, etc.	Addition of slurries	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	7	0.00%	71.43%	14.29%	0.00%	14.29%	0.00%		0.00%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	5	0.00%	40.00%	20.00%	20.00%	20.00%	0.00%		0.00%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	5	80.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%		0.00%
Increase soil organic matter content	7	0.00%	85.71%	0.00%	14.29%	0.00%	0.00%		0.00%
Improve soil structure	6	16.67%	33.33%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%		0.00%
Increase soil biodiversity	7	0.00%	57.14%	42.86%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%		0.00%
Reduce soil erosion	4	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%		0.00%
Reduce soil pollution	4	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%		0.00%
Reduce soil salinization									
Reduce soil acidification	3	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	33.33%	33.33%	0.00%		0.00%
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	4	25.00%	0.00%	75.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%		0.00%
Improve water quality									
Reduce the incidence of weeds	6	33.33%	0.00%	16.67%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%		16.67%
Increasing load carrying capacity									

Table A9.3. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective soil conservation practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for wheat production in Germany (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Mulching (with crushed offcuts from pruning, etc.)	Maintain vegetation cover (natural or cover crops)	Maintain strips of vegetation between lines	Hedges or natural vegetation on the edges of the plots	Erosion barriers or margins with vegetation	Addition of organic matter	Crop diversification	Use of catch crops to reduce N/P leaching	Avoiding plant protection products	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	6	0.00%	0.00%	16.67%	0.00%			83.33%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	5	0.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%			60.00%	0.00%	0.00%	20.00%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	4	0.00%	25.00%	0.00%	0.00%			75.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Increase soil organic matter content	6	0.00%	33.33%	16.67%	0.00%			50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Improve soil structure	5	0.00%	20.00%	20.00%	0.00%			40.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Increase soil biodiversity	6	0.00%	0.00%	16.67%	16.67%			66.67%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil erosion	4	0.00%	25.00%	25.00%	0.00%			50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil pollution	4	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%			50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil salinization											
Reduce soil acidification	2	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%			50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	4	0.00%	0.00%	25.00%	0.00%			75.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Improve water quality											
Reduce the incidence of weeds	5	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%	0.00%			60.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Increasing load carrying capacity											

Table A9.4. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective pest and disease control practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for wheat production in Germany (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Pests alerts	Crop diversification	Trap crops	Increase soil invertebrates biodiversity	Use of biostimulants and mycorrhiza, etc.	Use of pesticides	Ploughing	Alelopathic crops. such as Brassicae	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	4	0.00%	75.00%	0.00%	25.00%	0.00%	0.00%		0.00%	0.00%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	4	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	25.00%	50.00%	0.00%		0.00%	25.00%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	2	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%		0.00%	0.00%
Increase soil organic matter content	4	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%		0.00%	50.00%
Improve soil structure	4	0.00%	75.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%		0.00%	25.00%
Increase soil biodiversity	5	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%	20.00%		0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil erosion	3	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%		0.00%	66.67%
Reduce soil pollution	2	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%		0.00%	50.00%
Reduce soil salinization										
Reduce soil acidification	1	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%		0.00%	0.00%
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	2	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%		0.00%	0.00%
Improve water quality										
Reduce the incidence of weeds	4	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%		0.00%	0.00%
Increasing load carrying capacity										

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A10. POTATO, NEMORAL (ESTONIA)

Problems and objectives for action

The stakeholders interviewed in the Estonian Nemoral potato case study do not identify any agronomic **problems** as being of high or very high severity (Table 2). The most severe problems, perceived, on average, as of a medium-low severity, are rainfall scarcity in the growing period and the low and/or variable yields, followed by the high incidence of fungal diseases and soil compaction. On the other hand, the less severe problems for stakeholders are water pollution by leaching or run-off of nutrients and low presence of beneficial invertebrates or insects in the soil (Table 2).

The assessment of the priority given by the Estonian stakeholders to different **objectives** for addressing the agronomic problems in the Belgian Atlantic central wheat case study (Table 3) points at increasing soil structure to improve aeration, water retention and rooting and increasing soil organic matter content as the most urgent needs, followed by mobilizing soil nutrients during plant growth, increasing soil fertility and reducing the incidence of pests and diseases.

Identification of farming practices

Concerning **tillage practices**, values in Table A10.1 show that Estonian respondents choose different tillage practices as the most adequate one depending on the end-users' need to be fulfilled (objectives). As in other case studies, stakeholders' answer highlight once more the controversy between the use of conventional tillage and less intensive tillage practice. Conventional tillage is the tillage practice selected by more stakeholders as the most effective for the majority for objectives such as increasing soil fertility, reducing the incidence of pests and disease, improving soil structure and water infiltration and reducing the incidence of weeds, commonly followed by minimum tillage as the second most selected alternative. On the other hand, minimum tillage is the most selected tillage practice increase soil organic matter content and reduce soil erosion. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 4 and Table 24) confirm these findings, as respondents provide the highest ranking score to conventional tillage, while minimum tillage gets the highest second ranking score.

The majority interviewed stakeholders consider that the implementation of more sustainable tillage practices in potato production in the area of study is not diffculted by any specific problems. However, about a quarter of respondents point at the incompatibility with other farming practices and their higher costs (Table 5). Regarding the effectiveness of more sustainable tillage practices when integrated within different cropping systems, the majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that they are equally or more effective under conventional farming that under organic farming (Table 6), but more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 7) and equally or more effective under irrigation than under rainfed conditions (Table 8).

With respect to **fertilization practices**, the surveyed stakeholders think that green manure is the most effective alternative to satisfy most of the identified end users' needs in potato production in the area (Table A10.2). Green manure is the most selected fertilization alternative to improve soil structure, increase soil biodiversity and fertility, reduce soil erosion and pollution, reduce incidence of weeds and increase the load carrying capacity, usually followed by the addition of solid organic matter, which is the most selected alternative to increase soil organic matter content and fertility to reduce soil erosion. Additionally, the use of precision agriculture techniques is the most selected fertilization practice to mobilize soil nutrients during potato plant growth and to reduce soil pollution, while the use of biostimulants, biofertilizers, etc. is the second most selected fertilization alternative to mobilise soil nutrients and to reduce soil erosion. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 9 and Table 24) confirm the above findings as the respondents give the highest ranking score to the use of green manure, followed by the addition of soil organic matter/manures.

Turning to the barriers for the implementation of more sustainable fertilization practices in potato production, the interviewed Estonian stakeholders point at the lack of tradition and the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness as the most important obstacles to be faced for a greater diffusion of these practices (Table 10). Regarding the effectiveness of more sustainable fertilization practices when integrated within different cropping systems, the majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that they are equally effective under organic and conventional farming (Table 11). A majority of respondents think that they would be more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 12) and that their effectiveness is greater under irrigation than under rainfed conditions (Table 13).

Relating to **soil conservation practices**, results in Table A10.3 show that a majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that crop diversification crops is the most effective soil conservation alternative for most of the objectives. Crop diversification is the most selected soil conservation alternative for objectives such as improving soil structure, reducing the incidence of weeds and the incidence of pests and diseases, reducing soil erosion and mobilizing soil nutrients during plant growth. The addition of organic matter is the most selected alternative to increase soil organic matter content and soil biodiversity. Additionally, avoiding the use of plant protection products is the most selected alternative to reduce pollution. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 14 and Table 24) confirm these findings, as crop diversification receives a ranking score that doubles that of the second highest ranked practice, the addition of organic matter that was also selected as one of the preferred fertilization practices.

Again, the interviewed stakeholders believe that the application of more sustainable soil conservation practices in potato production in the area of study is mostly diffculted by the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness. Less about a 20-25% of the respondents think that the lack of adequate governmental support on technical issues, the lack of tradition in the region and the high costs are also relevant barriers to a wider diffusion of these (Table 15). Regarding the integration of more sustainable soil conservation practices within different cropping systems, a vast majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that they are equally effective under organic and conventional farming (Table 16). Most of the respondents also believe that they would be more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 17) and that their effectiveness is similar or even greater under irrigation than under rainfed conditions (Table 18).

To finish, relating to **pest and disease control practices**, results in Table A10.4 show that most of the interviewed stakeholders think that crop diversification are the most effective alternative to reach most end users' objectives, such as to increase soil biodiversity, fertility and soil organic matter content, mobilize soil nutrients during the potato plant growth period, reduce soil erosion and improve soil structure. On the other hand, using pesticides is the most selected alternative to reduce the incidence of pest and diseases and to improve soil structure. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 19 and Table 24) confirm these findings as respondents give the highest possible score ranking to pests alerts, almost tripling the ranking score given to the use of pesticides.

A majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that the implementation of more innovative pest control practices in potato production in the area is diffculted by lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness and their higher cost (Table 20). On the other hand, a significant number of respondents thinks that they are easy to implement practices if adequate technical advice is provided. Concerning the integration of more sustainable pest control practices within different cropping systems, a majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that they are equally effective under organic and conventional farming (Table 21) and that their effectiveness would be greater in diversified cropping system (Table 22) , while they perceive that their effectiveness is similar or even greater under irrigation than under rainfed conditions (Table 23).

Table A10.1. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective tillage practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for potato production in Estonia (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Conventional tillage	Tillage according level curves	Shallow tillage	Minimum tillage (reduced tillage frequency)	No tillage with herbicides	No tillage without herbicides (mechanical weed control)	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	14	21.43%	7.14%	7.14%	7.14%	7.14%	7.14%	35.71%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	12	25.00%	16.67%	0.00%	25.00%	8.33%	8.33%	8.33%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	13	61.54%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	7.69%	0.00%	15.38%
Increase soil organic matter content	14	14.29%	0.00%	14.29%	35.71%	7.14%	7.14%	21.43%
Improve soil structure	14	57.14%	0.00%	0.00%	14.29%	7.14%	0.00%	7.14%
Increase soil biodiversity	12	33.33%	0.00%	0.00%	16.67%	8.33%	25.00%	16.67%
Reduce soil erosion	7	0.00%	14.29%	0.00%	57.14%	0.00%	0.00%	14.29%
Reduce soil pollution	4	25.00%	0.00%	0.00%	25.00%	0.00%	0.00%	25.00%
Reduce soil salinization								
Reduce soil acidification								
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	10	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	10.00%	20.00%	0.00%	20.00%
Improve water quality								
Reduce the incidence of weeds	11	72.73%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	9.09%	9.09%	9.09%
Increasing load carrying capacity	5	20.00%	0.00%	20.00%	20.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%

Table A10.2. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective fertilization practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for potato production in Estonia (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Incorporating crops residues into the soil	Addition of solid organic matter/manures	Use of green manure	Combination of manure and mineral fertilizers	Precision agriculture to optimise fertilization	Use of biostimulants, biofertilizers, etc.	Addition of slurries	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	13	0.00%	30.77%	30.77%	15.38%	7.69%	0.00%	0.00%	7.69%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	11	0.00%	0.00%	9.09%	27.27%	36.36%	27.27%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	12	8.33%	0.00%	8.33%	8.33%	16.67%	25.00%	0.00%	25.00%
Increase soil organic matter content	13	7.69%	61.54%	30.77%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Improve soil structure	13	0.00%	30.77%	53.85%	0.00%	7.69%	0.00%	0.00%	7.69%
Increase soil biodiversity	11	9.09%	18.18%	45.45%	0.00%	0.00%	27.27%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil erosion	6	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	16.67%	0.00%	0.00%	33.33%
Reduce soil pollution	4	0.00%	25.00%	25.00%	0.00%	25.00%	0.00%	0.00%	25.00%
Reduce soil salinization									
Reduce soil acidification									
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	9	0.00%	0.00%	44.44%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	55.56%
Improve water quality									
Reduce the incidence of weeds	10	10.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	40.00%
Increasing load carrying capacity	4	25.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	25.00%

Table A10.3. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective soil conservation practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for potato production in Estonia (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Mulching (with crushed offcuts from pruning, etc.)	Maintain vegetation cover (natural or cover crops)	Maintain strips of vegetation between lines	Hedges or natural vegetation on the edges of the plots	Erosion barriers or margins with vegetation	Addition of organic matter	Crop diversification	Use of catch crops to reduce N/P leaching	Avoiding plant protection products	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	13						38.46%	53.85%		0.00%	0.00%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	11						18.18%	81.82%		0.00%	0.00%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	12						0.00%	75.00%		8.33%	8.33%
Increase soil organic matter content	13						69.23%	30.77%		0.00%	0.00%
Improve soil structure	13						7.69%	92.31%		0.00%	0.00%
Increase soil biodiversity	11						45.45%	27.27%		27.27%	0.00%
Reduce soil erosion	6						16.67%	83.33%		0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil pollution	4						0.00%	25.00%		50.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil salinization											
Reduce soil acidification											
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	9						22.22%	66.67%		0.00%	11.11%
Improve water quality											
Reduce the incidence of weeds	10						0.00%	90.00%		0.00%	10.00%
Increasing load carrying capacity	4						25.00%	50.00%		0.00%	0.00%

Table A10.4. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective pest and disease control practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for potato production in Estonia (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Pests alerts	Crop diversification	Trap crops	Increase soil invertebrates biodiversity	Use of biostimulants and mycorrhiza, etc.	Use of pesticides	Ploughing	Alelopathic crops. such as Brassicae	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	13	0.00%	76.92%				0.00%	0.00%		15.38%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	11	0.00%	81.82%				0.00%	0.00%		18.18%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	12	16.67%	16.67%				58.33%	0.00%		0.00%
Increase soil organic matter content	13	0.00%	92.31%				0.00%	0.00%		0.00%
Improve soil structure	13	0.00%	53.85%				7.69%	15.38%		15.38%
Increase soil biodiversity	11	0.00%	100.00%				0.00%	0.00%		0.00%
Reduce soil erosion	6	0.00%	83.33%				0.00%	0.00%		0.00%
Reduce soil pollution	4	50.00%	25.00%				0.00%	0.00%		0.00%
Reduce soil salinization										
Reduce soil acidification										
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	9	0.00%	66.67%				0.00%	11.11%		11.11%
Improve water quality										
Reduce the incidence of weeds	10	0.00%	50.00%				40.00%	10.00%		0.00%
Increasing load carrying capacity	4	0.00%	50.00%				0.00%	25.00%		0.00%

A11. POTATO, BOREAL (FINLAND)

Problems and objectives for action

The stakeholders interviewed in the Finish potato case study do not perceive any agronomic **problems** as being of high severity (Table 2). The most severe problems, perceived on average as of a medium-high severity, are the scarcity of rainfall during the growing period, the loss of organic matter and soil compaction. There is also some concern with soil waterlogging, fungal diseases, low soil microbial biodiversity and low soil fertility. On the other hand, the less severe problems for stakeholders are the incidence of pests, water pollution from nutrients and the abuse of pest control products.

The assessment of the priority given by stakeholders to different **objectives** for addressing the agronomic problems in the Finish potato case study (Table 3) points at the improvement of soil structure to increase aeration, water retention and favour plant rooting as the most urgent need, followed by the increase in the soil organic matter content, in soil fertility and in soil biodiversity and the mobilization of soil nutrients.

Identification of farming practices

Regarding **tillage practices**, results in Table A11.1 show that the interviewed stakeholders have very divergent views of the role that tillage practices can play in fulfilling end-users' needs (objectives). First, for most objectives, a significant number of respondents think that tillage practices are not effective to reach each objective. Second, there is clear choice of conventional intensive tillage as the most effective tillage practice to reduce the incidence of pests and disease and control weeds. Last, for other objectives, respondents select different types of less intensive tillage, such as shallow tillage, reduced tillage intensity or no tillage with mechanical weed control, as the most adequate tillage practices to increase soil fertility, biodiversity and organic matter content, mobilise soil nutrients and reduce soil erosion and soil pollution. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 4 and Table 24) confirm these findings by highlighting the little effectiveness given by respondents to tillage practices to solve the agronomic problems of the crop, followed by reducing tillage frequency (minimum tillage) and, to a lesser extent, by conventional intensive tillage and no tillage without herbicide application.

The interviewed stakeholders think that the implementation of more sustainable tillage practices in potato production in the area of study is difficulted by the lack of tradition and farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness (Table 5). Other relevant barriers indicated are their lack of profitability, their incompatibility with other farming practices and with the existing farm machinery. On the other hand, stakeholders do not perceive these tillage practices as difficult to implement. Regarding the effectiveness of more sustainable tillage practices when integrated within different cropping systems, the interviewed stakeholders have again different perceptions that seem to come from the different importance that they give to each agronomic problem. However, in general they seem to agree that they are equally effective under organic and

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conventional farming (Table 6) and under rainfed and irrigated conditions (Table 8), but more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 7).

Table A11.1. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective tillage practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for potato production in Finland (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Conventional tillage	Tillage according level curves	Shallow tillage	Minimum tillage (reduced tillage frequency)	No tillage with herbicides	No tillage without herbicides (mechanical weed control)	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	27	7.41%	0.00%	11.11%	25.93%	0.00%	7.41%	40.74%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	22	18.18%	0.00%	22.73%	18.18%	0.00%	13.64%	18.18%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	17	41.18%	0.00%	0.00%	5.88%	0.00%	11.76%	29.41%
Increase soil organic matter content	30	6.67%	0.00%	23.33%	20.00%	6.67%	13.33%	26.67%
Improve soil structure	28	14.29%	7.14%	10.71%	17.86%	3.57%	14.29%	32.14%
Increase soil biodiversity	20	0.00%	0.00%	15.00%	20.00%	0.00%	25.00%	35.00%
Reduce soil erosion	19	5.26%	0.00%	10.53%	31.58%	5.26%	21.05%	21.05%
Reduce soil pollution	5	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	40.00%	20.00%
Reduce soil salinization								
Reduce soil acidification								
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	20	30.00%	0.00%	5.00%	5.00%	0.00%	5.00%	55.00%
Improve water quality	12	8.33%	8.33%	8.33%	16.67%	16.67%	25.00%	8.33%
Reduce the incidence of weeds	10	70.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	10.00%	10.00%	10.00%
Increasing load carrying capacity	15	0.00%	0.00%	6.67%	33.33%	6.67%	13.33%	20.00%

With respect to **fertilization practices**, there seems to be a greater consensus than in the case of tillage practices (Table A11.2). The addition of solid organic matter and/or the use of green manure are identified as the most effective fertilization practices. However, the optimisation of the fertilization using precision agriculture techniques is also identified as an effective fertilization practice to mobilise soil nutrients and to reduce water pollution. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 9 and Table 24) confirm these findings as the addition of solid organic matter and the use of green manure receive much higher ranking scores than other fertilization practices.

Turning to the barriers for the implementation of more sustainable fertilization practices in potato production, the interviewed stakeholders point at the lack of tradition and farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness as major difficulties (Table 10). Other relevant barriers indicated are their lack of profitability, their incompatibility with other farming practices and with the existing farm machinery. On the other hand, only a minority of stakeholders perceive these fertilization practices as difficult to implement.

Regarding the effectiveness of more sustainable fertilization practices when integrated within different cropping systems, the interviewed stakeholders have again differing perceptions: there is not a clear consensus about their effectiveness when integrated under organic and conventional farming (Table 11) or under rainfed with respect to irrigated conditions (Table 13), but a majority of respondents perceived them as more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 12).

Regarding **soil conservation practices**, results in Table A11.3 show that the interviewed stakeholders think that crop diversification is the best alternative for soil conservation, followed by the addition of organic matter, which is only the preferred alternative in order to increase soil organic matter content and to reduce soil pollution. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 14 and Table 24) confirm these findings as crop diversification receives a ranking score that doubles that of the second highest ranked practice, which is the addition of solid organic matter, which was also selected as the preferred fertilization practice.

Again, the interviewed stakeholders think that the implementation of more sustainable soil conservation practices in potato production in the area of study is diffculted by the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness and the lack of tradition (Table 15). Other relevant barriers indicated are their lack of profitability and the incompatibility of crop diversification practices with the existing farm machinery. On the other hand, stakeholders do not perceive these tillage practices as difficult to implement if proper technical advice is available.

In relation with the integration of more sustainable soil conservation practices within different cropping systems, the interviewed stakeholders have again different perceptions. However, in general they seem to agree that they are equally or more effective under organic than under conventional farming (Table 16) and under irrigation (Table 18), but more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 17).

Last, with respect to **pest and disease control practices**, results in Table A11.4 show that the vast majority of interviewed stakeholders think that crop diversification are the most effective alternative. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 19 and Table 24) confirm these

findings as respondents have given the highest possible score raking to this practice. Again, the interviewed stakeholders think that the implementation of more innovative pest control practices in potato production is diffculted by the lack of tradition and farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness and, to a lesser extent, by their cost and lack of profitability (Table 20). Regarding the integration of more sustainable pest control practices within different cropping systems, the interviewed stakeholders seem to agree that they are equally effective under organic and conventional farming (Table 21) and under rainfed and irrigated conditions (Table 23), but clearly more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 22).

Table A11.2. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective fertilization practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for potato production in Finland (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Incorporating crops residues into the soil	Addition of solid organic matter/manures	Use of green manure	Combination of manure and mineral fertilizers	Precision agriculture to optimise fertilization	Use of biostimulants, biofertilizers, etc.	Addition of slurries	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	27	0.00%	51.85%	22.22%	14.81%	7.41%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	22	4.55%	13.64%	13.64%	27.27%	31.82%	4.55%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	17	17.65%	11.76%	0.00%	11.76%	11.76%	5.88%	0.00%	29.41%
Increase soil organic matter content	30	6.67%	56.67%	26.67%	3.33%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Improve soil structure	28	3.57%	32.14%	57.14%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	3.57%
Increase soil biodiversity	20	5.00%	60.00%	35.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil erosion	19	5.26%	21.05%	63.16%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	10.53%
Reduce soil pollution	5	20.00%	20.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	40.00%
Reduce soil salinization									
Reduce soil acidification									
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	20	5.00%	35.00%	40.00%	5.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	15.00%
Improve water quality	12	8.33%	8.33%	25.00%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	0.00%	16.67%
Reduce the incidence of weeds	10	10.00%	30.00%	30.00%	0.00%	30.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Increasing load carrying capacity	15	6.67%	40.00%	46.67%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

Table A11.3. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective soil conservation practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for potato production in Finland (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Mulching (with crushed offcuts from pruning, etc.)	Maintain vegetation cover (natural or cover crops)	Maintain strips of vegetation between lines	Hedges or natural vegetation on the edges of the plots	Erosion barriers or margins with vegetation	Addition of organic matter	Crop diversification	Use of catch crops to reduce N/P leaching	Avoiding plant protection products	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	27						37.04%	55.56%		0.00%	3.70%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	22						22.73%	63.64%		0.00%	13.64%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	17						0.00%	88.24%		0.00%	0.00%
Increase soil organic matter content	30						56.67%	33.33%		3.33%	0.00%
Improve soil structure	28						21.43%	67.86%		3.57%	7.14%
Increase soil biodiversity	20						15.00%	80.00%		5.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil erosion	19						36.84%	63.16%		0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil pollution	5						40.00%	0.00%		40.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil salinization											
Reduce soil acidification											
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	20						25.00%	65.00%		0.00%	10.00%
Improve water quality	12						16.67%	66.67%		0.00%	16.67%
Reduce the incidence of weeds	10						10.00%	90.00%		0.00%	0.00%
Increasing load carrying capacity	15						33.33%	66.67%		0.00%	0.00%

Table A11.4. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective pest and disease control practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for potato production in Finland (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Pests alerts	Crop diversification	Trap crops	Increase soil invertebrates biodiversity	Use of biostimulants and mycorrhiza	Use of pesticides	Ploughing	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	27	0.00%	70.37%				3.70%	3.70%	11.11%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	22	4.55%	54.55%				4.55%	22.73%	9.09%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	17	5.88%	41.18%				29.41%	5.88%	0.00%
Increase soil organic matter content	30	0.00%	83.33%				0.00%	3.33%	6.67%
Improve soil structure	28	0.00%	82.14%				0.00%	7.14%	7.14%
Increase soil biodiversity	20	0.00%	100.00%				0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil erosion	19	0.00%	94.74%				0.00%	0.00%	5.26%
Reduce soil pollution	5	0.00%	60.00%				0.00%	0.00%	20.00%
Reduce soil salinization									
Reduce soil acidification									
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	20	0.00%	55.00%				0.00%	20.00%	20.00%
Improve water quality	12	0.00%	83.33%				0.00%	0.00%	8.33%
Reduce the incidence of weeds	10	0.00%	80.00%				0.00%	20.00%	0.00%
Increasing load carrying capacity	15	0.00%	93.33%				0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

A12. WHEAT, BOREAL (FINLAND)

Problems and objectives for action

The stakeholders interviewed in the Finish wheat case study do not perceive, on average, any agronomic **problems** as being of high or very high severity (Table 2). The most severe problems, perceived on average as of a medium-high severity, are soil compaction, low and/or variable yields, soil waterlogging and rainfall scarcity during the growing period. There is also some concern with the low soil microbial biodiversity, the loss of organic matter and the low presence of invertebrates/insects/earthworms in the soil. On the other hand, the less severe problems for stakeholders are the incidence of pests, the abuse of pest control products and water pollution from nutrients. In general, these results are quite similar to those for the Finish potato case study.

The priority given by stakeholders to different **objectives** for addressing the agronomic problems in the Finish wheat case study (Table 3) points at the improvement of soil structure to increase aeration, water retention and favour plant rooting as the most urgent need, followed by the increase in soil fertility, in soil biodiversity and in soil organic matter content, as well as the mobilization of soil nutrients. These results are qualitatively very similar to those in the Finish potato case study but the quantitative assessment of the importance of those objectives is greater here.

Identification of farming practices

Regarding **tillage practices**, results in Table A12.1 show that the respondents choose different tillage practices as the most adequate one depending on the end-users' need to be fulfilled (objectives). First, conventional intensive tillage is the tillage practice selected by more stakeholders in order to reduce the incidence of pests and disease and control weeds. Second, shallow tillage and minimum tillage as the most chosen practices to increase soil fertility, and organic matter content, mobilise soil nutrients and improve soil structure. Third, no tillage without application of herbicides is chosen as the best alternative to reduce soil pollution but also to reduce soil erosion and increase soil biodiversity, in these two last cases with little difference with other conservation tillage options (shallow, minimum or no tillage with herbicides application). Last, the results suggest that there is not a clear consensus regarding which role can tillage practices play to improve water infiltration and reduce soil waterlogging. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 4 and Table 24) confirm these findings, as respondents provide the highest ranking score to shallow tillage, followed by minimum tillage and no tillage without herbicides with the same scoring.

The interviewed stakeholders think that the implementation of more sustainable tillage practices in wheat production in the area of study is diffculted by the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness and of adequate machinery for some tillage practices (Table 5). Other relevant barriers indicated are the lack of tradition in the area and the perceived lack of profitability. On the other hand, stakeholders do not perceive these tillage practices as difficult to implement with proper technical advice. Regarding the effectiveness of more sustainable tillage practices

when integrated within different cropping systems, the interviewed stakeholders seem to agree that they are equally effective under organic and conventional farming (Table 6), but more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 7) and under rainfed conditions (Table 8).

With respect to **fertilization practices**, there is a much greater consensus than in the case of tillage practices (Table A12.2). The use of green manure and the addition of solid organic matter are identified as the most effective fertilization practices. The first one is selected as the most adequate fertilization practices for most objective, with the exception of increasing soil fertility and organic matter content and mobilising soil nutrients when the second one is chosen by more stakeholders. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 9 and Table 24) confirm these findings as the use of green manure and, to a lesser extent, the addition of solid organic matter receive the highest ranking scores.

Turning to the barriers for the implementation of more sustainable fertilization practices in potato production, the interviewed stakeholders point at the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness, the lack of tradition and the lack of profitability as major difficulties (Table 10). On the other hand, only a minority of stakeholders perceive these tillage practices as difficult to implement. Regarding the effectiveness of more sustainable fertilization practices when integrated within different cropping systems, the majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that their effectiveness is similar when integrated under organic and conventional farming or even greater under organic farming (Table 11). They also think that is similar under both rainfed and irrigated conditions or even greater under rainfed production (Table 13). Again, a majority of respondents perceived them as more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 12).

Regarding **soil conservation practices**, results in Table A12.3 show that the interviewed stakeholders think that crop diversification is the best alternative for soil conservation for many of the objectives, followed by the use of catch crops and the addition of organic matter. The addition of organic matter is perceived as the most effective alternative to increase soil organic matter content, while the use of catch crops and avoiding the use of plant protection products are selected as the most effective practices to reduce soil pollution and water pollution respectively. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 14 and Table 24) confirm these findings as crop diversification receives a ranking score that doubles that of the second highest ranked practice, which is the addition of solid organic matter, which was also selected as one of the preferred fertilization practices.

Again, the interviewed stakeholders think that the implementation of more sustainable soil conservation practices in potato production in the area of study is diffculted by the lack of farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness and the lack of tradition (Table 15). Other relevant barriers indicated are their lack of profitability and the incompatibility of crop diversification practices with the existing farm machinery. On the other hand, stakeholders do not perceive these tillage practices as difficult to implement if proper technical advice is available. In relation with the integration of more sustainable soil conservation practices within different cropping systems, the interviewed stakeholders think that they are equally effective under organic than under conventional farming (Table 16). They also think that their effectiveness is similar under both rainfed and irrigated conditions or even greater under rainfed production

(Table 18). Again, a majority of respondents perceived them as more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 17).

Last, with respect to **pest and disease control practices**, results in Table A12.4 show that the vast majority of interviewed stakeholders think that crop diversification are the most effective alternative. The results from the multicriteria assessment (Table 19 and Table 24) confirm these findings as respondents have given the highest possible score ranking to this practice. Again, the interviewed stakeholders think that the implementation of more innovative pest control practices in potato production is difficulted by the lack of tradition and farmers' knowledge regarding their effectiveness and, to a lesser extent, by their cost and lack of profitability (Table 20). Regarding the integration of more sustainable pest control practices within different cropping systems, a majority of the interviewed stakeholders think that they are equally effective under organic and conventional farming (Table 21) and that their effectiveness is similar under both rainfed and irrigated conditions or even greater under rainfed production (Table 23). Last, they think that they would be more effective when integrated within a diversified cropping system (Table 22).

Table A12.1. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective tillage practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for wheat production in Finland (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Conventional tillage	Tillage according level curves	Shallow tillage	Minimum tillage (reduced tillage frequency)	No tillage with herbicides	No tillage without herbicides (mechanical weed control)	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	35	2.86%	0.00%	40.00%	8.57%	14.29%	11.43%	22.86%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	31	3.23%	0.00%	51.61%	9.68%	9.68%	6.45%	12.90%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	19	52.63%	5.26%	15.79%	5.26%	5.26%	5.26%	5.26%
Increase soil organic matter content	34	0.00%	0.00%	32.35%	32.35%	5.88%	11.76%	14.71%
Improve soil structure	41	14.63%	4.88%	26.83%	12.20%	12.20%	12.20%	14.63%
Increase soil biodiversity	29	0.00%	0.00%	20.69%	27.59%	13.79%	34.48%	0.00%
Reduce soil erosion	15	0.00%	6.67%	13.33%	20.00%	20.00%	26.67%	6.67%
Reduce soil pollution	15	0.00%	0.00%	13.33%	13.33%	0.00%	46.67%	13.33%
Reduce soil salinization								
Reduce soil acidification								
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	29	20.69%	6.90%	17.24%	6.90%	10.34%	13.79%	24.14%
Improve water quality	21	0.00%	9.52%	23.81%	23.81%	14.29%	14.29%	9.52%
Reduce the incidence of weeds	16	43.75%	6.25%	18.75%	0.00%	18.75%	6.25%	6.25%
Increasing load carrying capacity	26	7.69%	0.00%	34.62%	19.23%	15.38%	7.69%	15.38%

Table A12.2. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective fertilization practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for wheat production in Finland (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Incorporating crops residues into the soil	Addition of solid organic matter/manures	Use of green manure	Combination of manure and mineral fertilizers	Precision agriculture to optimise fertilization	Use of biostimulants, biofertilizers, etc.	Addition of slurries	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	32	9.38%	40.63%	37.50%	12.50%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	28	0.00%	35.71%	17.86%	14.29%	10.71%	14.29%	3.57%	0.00%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	16	18.75%	6.25%	31.25%	12.50%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	25.00%
Increase soil organic matter content	33	12.12%	51.52%	36.36%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Improve soil structure	37	8.11%	24.32%	62.16%	2.70%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	2.70%
Increase soil biodiversity	27	7.41%	25.93%	66.67%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil erosion	14	7.14%	7.14%	85.71%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil pollution	14	7.14%	7.14%	64.29%	0.00%	14.29%	0.00%	0.00%	7.14%
Reduce soil salinization									
Reduce soil acidification									
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	27	7.41%	18.52%	59.26%	3.70%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	11.11%
Improve water quality	18	5.56%	5.56%	55.56%	0.00%	27.78%	0.00%	0.00%	5.56%
Reduce the incidence of weeds	13	15.38%	0.00%	38.46%	7.69%	23.08%	0.00%	0.00%	15.38%
Increasing load carrying capacity	24	8.33%	12.50%	58.33%	8.33%	0.00%	4.17%	0.00%	8.33%

Table A12.3. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective soil conservation practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for wheat production in Finland (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Mulching (with crushed offcuts from pruning, etc.)	Maintain vegetation cover (natural or cover crops)	Maintain strips of vegetation between lines	Hedges or natural vegetation on the edges of the plots	Erosion barriers or margins with vegetation	Addition of organic matter	Crop diversification	Use of catch crops to reduce N/P leaching	Avoiding plant protection products	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	31						22.58%	61.29%	9.68%	6.45%	0.00%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	27						29.63%	33.33%	33.33%	0.00%	3.70%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	15						0.00%	73.33%	0.00%	6.67%	13.33%
Increase soil organic matter content	32						59.38%	31.25%	6.25%	3.13%	0.00%
Improve soil structure	36						19.44%	66.67%	8.33%	2.78%	2.78%
Increase soil biodiversity	26						11.54%	73.08%	11.54%	3.85%	0.00%
Reduce soil erosion	14						0.00%	64.29%	35.71%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil pollution	14						0.00%	21.43%	28.57%	42.86%	7.14%
Reduce soil salinization											
Reduce soil acidification											
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	26						7.69%	73.08%	11.54%	0.00%	7.69%
Improve water quality	17						5.88%	29.41%	41.18%	17.65%	5.88%
Reduce the incidence of weeds	12						0.00%	66.67%	16.67%	0.00%	16.67%
Increasing load carrying capacity	23						17.39%	65.22%	13.04%	0.00%	4.35%

Table A12.4. Stakeholders' identification of the most effective pest and disease control practices to achieve the objectives previously identified as of the highest priority for wheat production in Finland (percentage of stakeholders that selected each practice)

OBJECTIVES	Number of answers	Pests alerts	Crop diversification	Trap crops	Increase soil invertebrates biodiversity	Use of biostimulants and mycorrhiza, etc.	Use of pesticides	Ploughing	None of these is effective to achieve this objective
Increase soil fertility	31	0.00%	87.10%				6.45%	0.00%	6.45%
Mobilize soil nutrients during plant growth	27	0.00%	74.07%				0.00%	3.70%	22.22%
Reduce the incidence of pests and diseases	15	0.00%	73.33%				20.00%	6.67%	0.00%
Increase soil organic matter content	32	0.00%	90.63%				0.00%	0.00%	9.38%
Improve soil structure	36	0.00%	88.89%				2.78%	2.78%	5.56%
Increase soil biodiversity	26	0.00%	96.15%				0.00%	0.00%	3.85%
Reduce soil erosion	14	0.00%	100.00%				0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Reduce soil pollution	14	7.14%	78.57%				0.00%	7.14%	7.14%
Reduce soil salinization									
Reduce soil acidification									
Improve water infiltration / drainage systems	26	0.00%	73.08%				0.00%	7.69%	19.23%
Improve water quality	17	0.00%	76.47%				0.00%	0.00%	23.53%
Reduce the incidence of weeds	12	0.00%	58.33%				0.00%	25.00%	16.67%
Increasing load carrying capacity	23	0.00%	82.61%				0.00%	0.00%	13.04%

Annex 2: Outcomes of discussion groups in relation with the survey to stakeholders

Discussion groups of the Mediterranean South pedoclimatic region

Two discussion groups were organized in the Mediterranean South region, one on potato (case study 1) and the other on wheat production (case study 2). Due to the Covid-19 outbreak in March and the consequent prohibition of in-person events, the discussion groups were postponed and later organized online in September 2020. The first discussion group, focused on potato production, was held on September 15th 2020, while the second one, focused on wheat production, was held on September 16th 2020. 16 stakeholders with different profiles and backgrounds participated, including five farmers, a couple of technician advisors and other researchers with various expertise. Both discussion groups lasted about one hour each.

The objective of these discussion meetings was to identify the main agronomic problems faced by the various European farming systems and the related needs of end-users in the Mediterranean south region of the EU, as well as to identify suitable and effective farming practices to meet such needs. After a short introduction of the overall project, conducted by the regional coordinator Raúl Zornoza, the most relevant results from the surveys conducted to stakeholders and end-users, were presented by Alicia Morugán, researcher in SoildiverAgro, and Javier Calatrava, leader of Task 2.1. Participants in the meeting were asked whether they agreed with the surveys' results in terms of the problems and end-users' needs identified, the effectiveness of farming practices to help improve agricultural production in the area and the potential for their implementation.

During the discussion group on potato production, participants in the meeting were explained that the most several agronomical problems in potato production identified in the survey are the loss of organic matter and soil biodiversity, followed by soil compaction, results that were fully supported by them. Regarding the most suitable and effective farming practices identified in the survey, the participants agreed with the need to reduce tillage intensity, add solid organic matter and diversify crop productions, but some of them highlighted the complexity of implementing these practices without expert technical advice. On the other hand, some attendees showed their discrepancies with the suitability of green manure application on potato orchards.

During the second discussion group on wheat production, the main agronomic problems identified in the survey, loss of the organic matter, soil compaction and soil erosion, were confirmed by participants. The discussion focused particularly on the importance of soil erosion in wheat production in this region. The farming practices suggested by survey results, minimum tillage, addition of organic matter, soil vegetation covers and crop rotations, were fully supported by the participants. One of the farmers participants, explained that these could optimally be complemented by soil conservation structures, such as terraces ditches and ponds to prevent soil erosion, which were not highlighted by survey respondents. The survey also put forward the "lack of farmers' knowledge" and "lack of tradition" as the major reasons for the limited adoption of sustainable soil management practices in

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wheat production in the study area. Farm size was also pointed out by some participants as a barrier for the implementation of some effective farming practices, such as crop diversification.

Discussion group of the Lusitanian pedoclimatic region

On March 11, 2020, 18:00, a discussion group with the farmers of the Lusitanian area was organized in Xinzo de Limia. This meeting was attended by more than thirty farmers, as well as two representatives of agricultural product companies, two technicians and two members of agricultural organizations, plus several members of the SoildiverAgro project from the University of Vigo and a representative of FEUGA.

At the beginning of the act, which would last about two hours, there was a small presentation of the SoildiverAgro. The project members and the objectives were presented, and the different stages of the project were outlined so that farmers were clear about their role in the SoildiverAgro. After that presentation, the results of the surveys carried out before the meeting were presented, and, at the same time, a discussion of those results began and the farmers were able to express their opinions about the results of the surveys. This part of the discussion group can be summarized in the following paragraphs.

There was a general consensus in relation to the most serious problems of both wheat and potatoes. In other words, farmers agreed that the high incidence of pests was the most serious problem for wheat, while for potatoes the most severe issue was the low or variable yield. Both crops presented as the second problem in order of importance, according to the surveys and according to the farmers present, the inadequate drainage of the soil, which translates into flooded soils during specific periods of the year. The farmers attending the meeting also pointed out other problems that were not reflected in the surveys. For the potato case, for example, they indicated that it is a crop that has a low final price, while its seed has a variable price and its quality is not optimal. They also spoke of problems related to the distribution of the harvested product, since there is only one way to market it, sometimes there are problems with the health of the product (a distributor present said that), or that it undergoes very severe quality controls compared to those of the products that are imported, so they cannot be economically competitive. In addition, they pointed out that a kind of monopoly has been established: a company takes over all production and is able to manage prices at convenience. Regarding wheat, they pointed out as drawbacks the acidity of the soil, the price of the seed and of the inputs, the increase in adventitiousness in the fields without crop rotations and the climatic variability. They also argued problems related to compost: they need to store it for some periods, which generates fines from the administration.

The farmers present also agreed with the priorities indicated by the surveys for the crops to be productive and profitable. Thus, for potato crop the main objective is to reduce the incidence of pests and diseases, try to mobilize the nutrients from the soil during the growing season and, in general, improve soil conditions (fertility, structure, biodiversity...). Regarding wheat crops, the highest priority

should be to mobilize the nutrients present in the soil at the right time (during the growth of the plant), but it is also important to improve the fertility of the soil in general and to control the diseases and pests. Some farmers present specified that it is essential to establish the control of the potato nematode as a main objective (something that was already included in the survey in a more global way). They also indicated that it would be interesting to find specific agrochemicals to treat specific problems, instead of applying pesticides in a systematic way, as well as functional alert systems. Others, however, stated that against a mildew infestation, for example, prevention treatments are essential and once present in the crop this problem has a difficult solution.

When talking about the types of tillage the results of the surveys are the same for both crops (potatoes and wheat). The majority of the farmers surveyed would opt for a conventional tillage, but as the second most chosen answer it is indicated that there is no effective tillage to achieve the proposed objectives. And, for both crops, this was the opinion of many of the farmers present that indicated that conventional tillage works for some pests, but not for others.

In the case of fertilization, in the surveys the participants indicated that there is no effective system for fertilizing potato crops. This option was chosen by most of the respondents. In the second place, the surveyed farmers placed the fertilization with solid organic matter (manure) and, the third place, the use of precision fertilizers. The case of wheat is a bit different, and most of those surveyed considered that fertilizing with manure is the best option. But secondly (by very little difference), farmers ticked the option of "none of the [fertilization methods] listed is effective". As a third option, a significant part of the respondents elected the use of green manures. Those present in the discussion group pointed out that the fertilization can bring associated problems, especially in the case of potatoes. For example, one of the farmers indicated that, when importing organic fertilizer, foreign species of weeds can be introduced into the crop, so it is better to make this type of fertilizer with material from the area or altered through a composting process. Others mentioned that the greenest areas, the best fertilized, tend to have a higher incidence of mildew.

When examining the results of the surveys related to the most effective conservation practices, there was consensus between the results obtained through the surveys and the opinions of those present. For both potato and wheat crops, farmers believe that the most important thing is to diversify crops. But there are problems associated with rotations: the farmers do not know very well which crops are suitable for the area; there is no processing industry that allows them to easily commercialize new crops; they have waterlogging and temperature problems, so an adequate irrigation plan would be necessary; and the farm fields are very small, not very convenient for rotations.

In the case of practices related to pest control, there was also a consensus and, both from the surveys and the opinions of the farmers present in the meeting, it is deduced that the diversification of crops, as well as the use of pesticides, are crucial. It is important to note that a good part of the respondents believed that none of the indicated practices is effective (it is the second option chosen, both for farmers who cultivate wheat and for those who cultivate potatoes).

Finally, in the surveys the farmers were asked to indicate, in their opinion, what was the biggest problem when implementing new agricultural techniques. Most noted that these new techniques often involve difficult tasks to perform without technical advice. They also claim a lack of knowledge about the effectiveness of the practices, lack of tradition in the region, and, fourthly, inadequate or insufficient support from the government in technical matters. However, the individuals present did not agree with these results and pointed out that the main problem is the latter: the lack of support from the administration. Moreover, they indicated, once again, that there is no industry that takes over the processing of new crops (in the case of introducing new plants for rotations, for example).

Discussion groups of the Atlantic Central pedoclimatic region

Two discussion groups were organized in the Atlantic Central region, one on vegetable and one on arable crops. Due to the Covid-19 outbreak in March and the consequent prohibition of live events, the discussion groups were postponed and later organized online. Given this format, the meetings were shortened to about 1,5 h and the overall agenda prepared for the regional stakeholder meetings needed to be scaled down. Both meetings thus focused on the case studies' setup, i.e., on the management practices to be implemented.

The first discussion group, on vegetables cultivation, was held on May 19th 2020. In addition to all Belgian research partners (from ILVO, PSKW and Inagro), 14 stakeholders with different profiles and backgrounds participated, including farmers, industry advisors, policy officers and other researchers with various expertise. After a short overall introduction to the project, some general conclusions of the survey were presented and discussed. Drought and lack of irrigation water were confirmed as the main agronomic problems, at least for this and the previous year. Someone mentioned the high priority attributed in the survey to improving soil fertility to be in contrast with the elevated concentrations of macronutrients usually measured. Others replied that soil fertility should be interpreted wider than just chemical. Soil organic matter (SOM) content and soil biodiversity indeed are often low, while the ample presence of soil fungi may reduce soil fertility. The survey also put forward a "lack of farmers' knowledge" as a reason for limited adoption of good soil management practices. Participants stated that many farm advisors are employed by input suppliers, hence they don't inform about SOM or mycorrhizae. Moreover, improving soil quality is a complex problem without simple, straightforward solutions, which may restrain advisors from tackling it. By contrast, most farmers are thought to be aware of the importance of SOM, even though increasing it is not easy and can only be achieved in the long term (which is partly due to prevailing legislation on manuring).

The second discussion group, on arable cropping, was held on June 30th, 2020, also in online format. Again, all Belgian research partners participated, together with 15 stakeholders (farmers, farm advisors, policy officers and researchers). A reduced agenda, as in the other discussion group, was followed, starting with a short overall introduction to the project, a discussion of the survey results for arable farming and the discussion about the experimental design. For potato growing, the soil problems given the highest priority in the survey were increasing SOM, improving soil structure and

soil fertility. Among the management techniques mentioned to tackle these problems, addition of organic matter/manure and using cover crops received most votes in the survey. Concerning cover crops, it was remarked that the effect of sowing a cover crop after October 1st is very small. However, in the Belgian field trials rather the effect on a potato crop of cover crops installed in the rotation in the years before will be studied.

Discussion group of the Continental pedoclimatic region

The discussion group on the Continental pedoclimatic region case studies was held online on the 3rd of November 2020. The results of the survey to stakeholders on wheat and potato were presented and discussed with attendants.

Participants agree with the identified problems (weed, pests, low precipitation rates and variable yields both in the case of potato and wheat) and objectives (weed control, mobilisation of nutrients, reduction of pests, increase of soil fertility and organic matter in the case of potato; weed control, mobilisation of nutrients, reduction of pests, increase of soil fertility and organic matter and supporting soil biota in the case of wheat).

Regarding farming practices in potato, the discussion focused on the need to reduce herbicides and fungicides. Avoiding their use is not possible because of the risk of total loss of harvest. Generally, a reduction is difficult, also for insecticides. Also, a reduction of fertilizers in potato is very difficult, especially for organic farmers due to technical reasons. According to good agricultural practice, nutrients, which are removed by harvesting, have to be substituted by fertilizers. In the case of wheat, the discussion focused on the control of weeds, being the most relevant in this area Black Foxtail (*Alopecurus myosuroides*), which can be mechanically controlled by harrow. There was a general agreement on the lack of farmers' knowledge about more sustainable farming practices, such as, for example, the use of soil animals acting antagonistically against soil-borne pests in potato.

Participants that were also survey respondents provided general feedback on the questionnaire, claiming that:

- Many issues in the questionnaire are very complex and only partly covered by the given answers.
- Each season new challenges are faced, which raise new questions for farmers. Such seasonal aspects are not considered in the questionnaire.
- In some cases, farmers missed the possibility to give more than one answer. Often the combination of measures particularly promising.
- Some farmers had difficulties to answer because of very complex problems, which are not monocausal but multifactorial.

- The distribution of ranking values or at least the addition of standard errors of the given answers would deliver more information than just a mean value. For instance, a mean value of 3 can be based on 4 answers with value 3 or on 2 answers with value 5 plus 2 answers with value 1.
- The selection of ranking values is based on the subjective perception of farmers. Consequently, the result can vary quite widely.

Discussion group of the Nemoral region

The discussion group was originally planned for March 2020. However, because of the restriction connected with the declaration of national emergency because of the COVID-19 outbreak, the discussion groups were postponed in Estonia until easing of restriction in the summer of 2020. As stakeholders, especially farmers, had previously stated a strong preference towards face-to-face discussion, instead of virtual one, it was decided to conduct the discussion group as in-person meetings after the restrictions for gatherings were lifted. Consequently, the discussion group took place on July 3rd in Lalli village, Kehtna municipality, Estonia and focused on organic farming. There were 18 participants in the meeting, including 16 farmers and 2 researchers.

The aim of the discussion group was to introduce the project, validate the previously collected survey results, and collect their feedback on the main agronomic and soil management problems and possible farming practices to address them, plus other input for subsequent field experiments in the Nemoral region. As a longer field visit was incorporated to the meeting, the discussion on the survey results was shortened from the originally suggested 4-hour time frame. The discussion involved an introduction of the project made by Estonian regional coordinator Merrit Shanskiy and subsequently the main emphasis was on discussion of agronomic problems in organic farming and possibilities to mitigate those sustainably.

In the survey results, the rainfall scarcity, low and variable yields, soil compaction, fungal diseases, low soil fertility had been identified as the biggest agronomic challenges and improvement of soil structure for aeration, water retention and rooting, increase of soil organic matter content, mobilization of soil nutrients during plant growth and increase of soil fertility had been prioritized to address those problems. In the discussion group, the main issue that was raised by organic farmers was the soil fertility and agreement was that this should be number one priority. Participants discussed about the need to determine the soil fertility with simple methods for producers, farmers on fields (on sites) in order to select suitable management and tillage practices. Therefore, the lack of knowledge of effectiveness of their practices was considered a big challenge confirming the results of the potato farmers' survey.

The organic producers pointed out that they would like to have more knowledge and deeper understanding about relationships and management of soil biodiversity and its functions. The question

was raised how do they determine if they have enough soil biodiversity on their fields. The discussion on fertilization practices raised the specific issues on the liming fertilizers and agents and need for knowledge on those, because the parent material of major agricultural soils in Estonia are different sandstones and that requires regular liming of agricultural soils.

In discussion of the management issues and the planned research, actually a political issue was raised. The major concern for organic producers in Estonia is right now the conditions to fulfil the EU level requirement for Green Deal. The questions were raised what it means for actual farmers in terms of requirements for soil managements, costs etc. The concern was that if the EU agriculture will be even more subsidized and Estonian organic farmers will lose the EU market for production.

Discussion group of the Boreal region

The Finnish discussion group was held in 5th of March 2020 at Tuusula hotel Krapihovi. Nine project members 9 participated, including all Finnish partners from Luke, Tyynelä and Kilpiö farms and Petla. From the several invited stakeholders, 13 participated: 5 farmers, 2 researchers and 6 other stakeholders, such as representatives of farmers' organization or organic producers' association, agricultural advisory organizations and input producers. First, the SoildiverAgro project was presented to the stakeholders, and the participants were motivated to be involved in the multi-actor approach of the project. The results of the WP2 survey for Finland were presented and discussed in three small groups of which two focused on the wheat production and one on potato production.

Regarding the discussion on the survey results, the main agronomic problems identified in the survey were confirmed in the discussion: soil compaction and loss of organic matter. The discussion concerning wheat production emphasized the importance of physical, chemical and biological conditions of soil also for the productivity. Especially the large fluctuation in rain and in the hydrology of soil was seen to cause problems for the potato production. In potato production the problems differ between the different types of production: early potatoes, starch potato, and cooking potato. Especially using monocultures of early spring potato and lack of crop-rotation was seen problematic.

The management practices suggested by survey results were discussed. In the wheat production the suggested practices by survey, shallow and minimum tillage, use of green manure and crop diversification, were seen as good solutions, but also drawbacks, such as soil compaction were perceived. This is important especially in organic production. Importance to solve water economy problems was emphasized. Continuous vegetation cover was highlighted to prevent erosion and leaching problems as well as supporting the microbial biodiversity in the root zone. However, in organic production the difficulty of weed management associated with minimum tillage practices was identified. Long term solutions with crop rotations were stressed. In the case of potato production, the suggested practices by survey were the use of green manure, adding organic matter and crop diversification. Green manuring and reducing tillage frequency were perceived to complement each other. The shortage of field area on the farm level was seen as a challenge of crop diversification. Also,

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the machinery that supports only potato cultivation leads to the need of using contractors that increases the cost of production. Last, learning and training of new farming practices was identified as a challenge for farmers and advisers to adopt cultivation practices that support soil biodiversity and increase the fertility of agricultural soils.